

Nur Gizem Yalçın

Re-politicising the Circular Economy

A Multi-Dimensional Critique
with Discourses, Power, and Art

Nur Gizem Yalçın

Re-politicising the Circular Economy: A Multi-Dimensional Critique with Discourses, Power, and Art

Dissertation, Ghent University & Brandenburg University of Technology (2025)

Cover design

Juliane Höhle

Lay-out & print

Reproduct, Ghent, Belgium

Copyright © 2025 NG Yalçın

Re-politicising the Circular Economy:

A Multi-Dimensional Critique with Discourses, Power, and Art

PhD Thesis

to obtain the joint PhD degree

from the Faculty of Political and Social Sciences of Ghent University for the *award of the academic degree of Doctor of Political Sciences*

and

from the Faculty of Economics, Law and Social Sciences of Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Seftenberg for the *award of the academic degree of Doctor of Economics and Social Sciences*

by

Nur Gizem Yalçın, MSc

born on 2 April 1994

Supervisor: Prof Dr Erik Paredis

Ghent University

Co-supervisor: Prof Dr Melanie Jaeger-Erben

Brandenburg University of Technology

Members of the doctoral committee

Prof Dr Ferdi De Ville

Ghent University

Prof Dr Thomas Block

Ghent University

Prof Dr Roh Pin Lee

Brandenburg University of Technology

Prof Dr Jacob Hasselbalch

Copenhagen Business School

Prof Dr Kris Bachus

University of Antwerp

C-PlaNeT
CIRCULAR PLASTICS NETWORK
FOR TRAINING

b-tu
Brandenburgische
Technische Universität
Cottbus - Senftenberg

Table of Contents

Summary	7
Samenvatting	8
Zusammenfassung	9
Publications part of this cumulative dissertation and authorship contributions	10
Chapter 1 <i>Introduction and Interpretive Research Design</i>	11
1.1. Critical friends with the Circular Economy in a validity challenge period	12
1.2. Opening-up the depoliticised circularity in the EU	14
1.3. Socio-political transitions to CE.....	17
1.3.1. Discourses and politics	17
1.3.2. Power and politics	18
1.4. Research questions	19
1.5. Interpretive research design	21
1.6. Implications of the interpretive approach on the research design	22
1.6.1. C-PlaNeT context	22
1.6.2. Techniques for generating data	24
Chapter 2 <i>Contested discourses of a circular plastics economy in Europe: prioritising material, economy, or society?</i>	27
Abstract	28
2.1. Introduction	29
2.2. Research design and methodology.....	30
2.3. Discourses of Circular Plastics Economy in Europe.....	32
2.3.1. Plastic fantastic	32
2.3.2. Circular economy will fly us to the moon	34
2.3.3. Even plastic flowers are dead in this system	36
2.4. Discussion	40
2.5. Conclusion	42
Chapter 3 <i>Packaged science? Incumbent strategies of science capture from a power perspective</i>	43
Abstract	44
3.1. Introduction	45
3.2. Theoretical framework	46
3.3. Methodology	49
3.4. The Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation Case	50
3.5. Findings.....	51
3.5.1. Epistemic strategy	51
3.5.2. Institutional strategy	55
3.5.3. Political strategy	58
3.6. Discussion	62
3.7. Conclusion	64

Chapter 4 <i>In search of a relational circular economy through art: the case of NaturArchy</i>	65
Abstract	66
4.1. Introduction	67
4.2. Complex systems and CE	68
4.3. Relational paradigm	70
4.4. Why arts and NaturArchy?	71
4.5. Methodology	72
4.6. Findings	73
4.6.1. Relational approaches to ontology	73
4.6.2. Relational approaches to epistemology	75
4.6.3. Relational approaches to ethics	77
4.7. Discussion	80
4.8. Conclusion	83
Chapter 5 <i>Discussion and Conclusion</i>	84
5.1. Discussion and conclusion	85
<i>RQ1: What are the main discourses on the CE in the EU? How can they be critically analysed and understood?</i>	85
<i>RQ2: How do certain interpretations of the CE become dominant, and why?</i>	87
<i>RQ3: What are the alternatives to dominant approaches to CE? Specifically, how can relational thinking inspire alternative forms of CE?</i>	88
<i>ORQ: How can the circular economy be opened up as a site of socio-political reconfiguration?</i>	90
5.2. Theoretical contributions	93
5.3. Empirical contributions	94
5.4. Implications for policy and governance	94
5.5. Limitations and directions for future research	95
References	97

Acknowledgements

These past years, with my PhD, I planted many seeds into my life garden: seeds of learning, unlearning, questioning, inspiration, adaptation, recalibration, creativity, and imagination. I felt awe and wonder with the readings, ideas, and academic insights; curiosity, confusion, and excitement with the research I carried out; anger, grief, hope, and frustration over systemic injustices and world events; bittersweetness and connection through solidarity. I worked hard in the garden, cared proactively, enjoyed the greenery and the blue sky, lovely sunshine and puffy clouds, and of course, I got wet in the rain and felt cold sometimes, but most of the time, I admired the beauty of the blossoms.

I also planted seeds of co-creation together with my colleagues, for which I would like to express my gratitude here. I would like to thank my supervisor, *Erik*, for welcoming me to Ghent, for his attentive and open-hearted support, availability, flexibility, also care and solidarity in the other aspects of life. And to my co-supervisor *Melanie*, for providing creative feedback, sharing papers in the right direction, and supporting my progress. I would like to thank my colleagues at CDO, *Juliane, Irma, Jonas, Kasper, Alexander, Kim, Lucas, Thomas, Gert, Katrien, Charlotte*, and *Maarten* for creating a critical but safe scholarly space and enjoyable fellowship. Thank you all for thinking, discussing, reflecting, celebrating, cooking, and singing together! Thank you, *Irma*, for our talks about the books of Brene Brown; *Jonas*, for your company during my first months in Ghent and co-organising the art workshop in Berlin; and *Kasper*, for co-authoring our short paper in the smoothest way possible with *Machteld*. And thank you, *Juliane*, for being a lovely and caring friend with whom we share the little excitements in our conversations and walks. I will continue to cherish your joyful heart and, of course, amazing art projects.

I also would like to thank colleagues at C-PlaNeT, *Fernando, Mubarik, Rita, Priyanka, Namrata, Dixit, Amir, Bahman, Manon, Heather, Alejandro, Ehsan, Maria, Francesca*, and *Christina* for the colourful get-togethers, high-quality presentations, challenging but rewarding inter-disciplinary exchanges as well as fun social activities and dinners at NTEs. I will always remember the becoming stories of our children's book, diving into each other's childhoods in 12 different countries, shaped by diverse cultures, values, and systems, and co-creating this special and amusing project.

I would like to thank *Machteld, Leo* and *Abe* for co-organising NEST (2021) and the webinar series together in a seamless way, having fun and putting quality work together. Also, *Wouter* and *Dieter* for our collaboration during my short internship with the City of Ghent.

Next to the scholarly co-creation, I would like to thank my precious family and friends for the seeds of contentment: for always being by my side with their generous love, care, time, attention, encouragement, companionship, endless support and pride, despite the distances of thousands of kilometres. To my family, *Arif, Nurdan, Mustafa, Gizay, Nurcan, Balanur, Ismail, Sıla* and my friends, *Şifa, Büşra, Alican, Murat, Begüm, Seniha, Sema, Şeyma, Sevda, Zeynep, Deniz, Hacer, Saraç, Nisa, Şeyda*, and *Özlem*: I cannot thank you enough for attending to the garden of my life with planting seeds of warmth for deep connections, wonder to explore further, courage to take brave steps, tranquillity to reflect, joy and compassion to live a meaningful life. Thank you also for making sure that these seeds get enough love, water and sunshine to bloom. This PhD is only one of the blossoms from the garden we cared for together.

To many colourful blossoms of life to admire together!

Nur Gizem

Gent, July 2025

Summary

This dissertation offers a critical, interpretive exploration of the Circular Economy (CE) as it unfolds within European Union (EU) policy and governance. While the CE has gained increasing prominence as a response to ecological crises and resource inefficiencies, its dominant policy framing often reflects a technocratic, market-oriented, and depoliticised narrative, risking the reproduction of socio-ecological injustices. This thesis adopts the position of a “critical friend to CE”, engaged with its transformative potential, yet questioning how it is imagined, institutionalised, and contested across discursive, political, and cultural domains.

Grounded in interpretive methodology and informed by discourse theory and critical power analysis, the thesis investigates the discursive constructions, institutional dynamics, and embedded power relations shaping circular transitions in Europe. It is guided by one overarching research question: *How can the circular economy be opened up as a site of socio-political reconfiguration?* Which is addressed by three sub-research questions: (1) What are the different discourses on the CE in the EU? How can they be critically analysed and understood? (2) How do certain interpretations become dominant, and why? (3) What are the alternatives to dominant approaches to CE? Specifically, how can relational thinking inspire alternative forms of CE?

Through a series of empirical case studies, the thesis unpacks how meaning, authority, and influence operate in circular transitions. Chapter 2 identifies and analyses three competing discourses in the European circular plastics debate centred on material efficiency, economic opportunity, and socio-ecological transformation. It shows how discursive struggles shape policy direction, actor positioning, and circular futures. Chapter 3 interrogates the strategies employed by incumbent actors to consolidate influence and close down debate. It deepens this analysis by exploring science capture in the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation, illustrating how epistemic authority is contested and shaped by power. Chapter 4 explores the NaturArchy art-science project as a site for alternative knowledge production and relational thinking, offering a more care-based and pluralistic vision of circularity.

The research was conducted within the interdisciplinary C-PlaNeT (Circular Plastics Network for Training) project, which informed the thesis's reflexive engagement with dominant assumptions in CE research and governance. Methodologically, the research employed abductive reasoning and qualitative methods, including discourse analysis, expert interviews, document and media analysis, and field observations, integrated through an interpretive, intertextual approach.

The thesis contributes to CE and sustainability transitions scholarship by foregrounding the political, epistemological, and ethical dimensions of circularity. It argues for a re-politicised CE, one that foregrounds justice, complexity, and pluralism, and is shaped through democratic negotiation rather than technocratic closure. . By unpacking the interplay of discourse, power, and imagination, the thesis opens pathways toward more inclusive and transformative forms of circularity.

Samenvatting

Deze dissertatie biedt een kritische, interpretatieve verkenning van de circulaire economie (CE) zoals die zich ontwikkelt binnen het beleid en bestuur van de Europese Unie (EU). Hoewel de CE aan belang wint als antwoord op ecologische crises en inefficiënt gebruik van hulpbronnen, weerspiegelt het dominante beleidskader vaak een technocratisch, marktgericht en gede-politiseerd narratief, met het risico dat bestaande sociaal-ecologische ongelijkheden worden bestendig. Dit proefschrift positioneert zich als een kritische vriend van de CE: betrokken bij het transformatieve potentieel ervan, maar tegelijk onderzoekend naar hoe de CE wordt voorgesteld, geïnstitutionaliseerd en gecontesteerd in discursieve, politieke en culturele domeinen.

Gebaseerd op een interpretatieve methodologie en geïnformeerd door discursustheorie en kritische machtsanalyse, onderzoekt dit proefschrift de discursieve constructies, institutionele dynamieken en machtsverhoudingen die circulaire transitie in Europa vormgeven. De centrale onderzoeksvraag luidt: hoe kan de circulaire economie worden opengesteld als plek voor sociaal-politieke herconfiguratie? Deze vraag wordt beantwoord aan de hand van drie deelvragen: (1) welke verschillende discourses over de CE bestaan er in de EU, en hoe kunnen deze kritisch worden geanalyseerd en begrepen? (2) hoe worden bepaalde interpretaties dominant, en waarom? (3) welke alternatieven bestaan er voor dominante benaderingen van de CE, en hoe kan relationeel denken bijdragen aan andere vormen van circulariteit?

Aan de hand van een reeks empirische casestudies onderzoekt het proefschrift hoe betekenis, autoriteit en invloed functioneren in circulaire transitie. Hoofdstuk 2 identificeert en analyseert drie concurrerende discourses in het Europese debat over circulaire kunststoffen, gericht op materiaalefficiëntie, economische kansen en sociaal-ecologische transformatie. Het laat zien hoe discursieve strijd de beleidsrichting, de positionering van actoren en de invulling van circulariteit beïnvloedt. Hoofdstuk 3 onderzoekt de strategieën van gevestigde actoren om invloed te behouden en debat te beperken. Daarbij wordt specifiek gekeken naar het fenomeen van 'science capture' in de context van de EU-verordening voor verpakking en verpakkingsafval, waarbij wordt geanalyseerd hoe epistemische autoriteit wordt bevochten en door macht wordt gevormd. Hoofdstuk 4 onderzoekt het kunst-wetenschapsproject NaturArchy als een plek voor alternatieve kennisproductie en relationeel denken, en laat een meer zorgzame en pluralistische benadering van circulariteit zien.

Het onderzoek vond plaats binnen het interdisciplinaire C-PlaNeT (Circular Plastics Network for Training)-project, wat bijdroeg aan een reflexieve benadering van dominante aannames in CE-onderzoek en -governance. Methodologisch is gewerkt met abductieve redenering en kwalitatieve methoden, waaronder discoursanalyse, expertinterviews, document- en media-analyse, en veldobservatie, samengebracht in een interpretatieve, intertekstuele benadering.

Het proefschrift levert een bijdrage aan de literatuur over circulaire economie en duurzaamheidstransities door de politieke, epistemologische en ethische dimensies van circulariteit centraal te stellen. Het pleit voor een CE die recht doet aan rechtvaardigheid, complexiteit en pluralisme, en die wordt vormgegeven via democratisch debat in plaats van technocratische besluitvorming. Door de interactie tussen discours, macht en verbeelding te analyseren, opent het onderzoek mogelijkheden voor meer inclusieve en transformatieve vormen van circulariteit.

Zusammenfassung

Diese Dissertation bietet eine kritische, interpretative Untersuchung der Kreislaufwirtschaft (Circular Economy, CE) in ihrer Ausgestaltung innerhalb der Politik und Governance der Europäischen Union (EU). Obwohl die CE zunehmend an Bedeutung als Antwort auf ökologische Krisen und Ressourceneffizienzverluste gewinnt, spiegelt ihre dominante politische Rahmung häufig ein technokratisches, marktorientiertes und entpolitisiertes Narrativ wider, wodurch das Risiko besteht, dass bestehende sozioökologische Ungleichheiten fortgeschrieben werden. Die Arbeit positioniert sich als kritischer Begleiter der CE: Sie ist engagiert im Hinblick auf ihr transformatives Potenzial, stellt jedoch die Frage, wie die CE in diskursiven, politischen und kulturellen Kontexten vorgestellt, institutionalisiert und umkämpft wird.

Auf der Grundlage einer interpretativen Methodologie, die durch Diskurstheorie und kritische Machtanalysen informiert ist, untersucht die Dissertation die diskursiven Konstruktionen, institutionellen Dynamiken und zugrunde liegenden Machtverhältnisse, welche zirkuläre Übergänge in Europa prägen. Die Arbeit wird durch eine zentrale Forschungsfrage geleitet: Wie kann die Kreislaufwirtschaft als Ort sozio-politischer Neugestaltung geöffnet werden? Diese Frage wird durch drei Teilfragen weiter konkretisiert: (1) Welche unterschiedlichen Diskurse über die CE existieren in der EU und wie können sie kritisch analysiert und verstanden werden? (2) Wie werden bestimmte Interpretationen dominant und warum? (3) Welche Alternativen zu dominanten Ansätzen der CE bestehen und wie kann relationales Denken alternative Formen der Kreislaufwirtschaft anregen?

Anhand einer Reihe empirischer Fallstudien wird aufgezeigt, wie Bedeutung, Autorität und Einfluss in zirkulären Transformationsprozessen wirken. Kapitel 2 identifiziert und analysiert drei konkurrierende Diskurse in der europäischen Debatte über zirkuläre Kunststoffe, die sich auf Materialeffizienz, wirtschaftliche Chancen und sozioökologische Transformation konzentrieren. Es wird dargestellt, wie diskursive Auseinandersetzungen politische Ausrichtungen, die Positionierung von Akteuren und Vorstellungen zirkulärer Zukünfte beeinflussen. Kapitel 3 untersucht die Strategien etablierter Akteure zur Sicherung ihres Einflusses und zur Begrenzung von Debatten. Im Zentrum steht dabei das Phänomen des „Science Capture“ im Kontext der EU-Verordnung über Verpackungen und Verpackungsabfälle. Es wird analysiert, wie epistemische Autorität umkämpft ist und durch Machtstrukturen geformt wird. Kapitel 4 untersucht das Kunst- und Wissenschaftsprojekt NaturArchy als Ort alternativer Wissensproduktion und relationalen Denkens. Es wird eine fürsorgeorientierte und pluralistische Perspektive auf Zirkularität entwickelt.

Die Forschung wurde im Rahmen des interdisziplinären Projekts C-PlaNeT (Circular Plastics Network for Training) durchgeführt, das die reflexive Auseinandersetzung mit dominanten Annahmen in der CE-Forschung und -Governance unterstützt hat. Methodisch basiert die Arbeit auf abduktivem Denken und qualitativen Methoden, darunter Diskursanalyse, Expertinnen- und Experteninterviews, Dokumenten- und Medienanalysen sowie Feldbeobachtungen. Diese Methoden wurden in einem interpretativen und intertextuellen Ansatz miteinander verbunden.

Die Dissertation leistet einen Beitrag zur Forschung über Kreislaufwirtschaft und Nachhaltigkeitstransformationen, indem sie die politischen, epistemologischen und ethischen Dimensionen der Zirkularität in den Vordergrund rückt. Sie spricht sich für eine repolitisierte Kreislaufwirtschaft aus, die auf Gerechtigkeit, Komplexität und Pluralität beruht und durch demokratische Aushandlungsprozesse anstelle technokratischer Schließungen gestaltet wird. Durch die Analyse des Zusammenspiels von Diskurs, Macht und Imagination eröffnet die Arbeit neue Perspektiven für inklusivere und transformativere Formen zirkulärer Ökonomien.

Publications part of this cumulative dissertation and authorship contributions

Publication	Declaration of Authorship
<p>Yalçın N.G., Paredis E. & Jaeger-Erben M. (2023)</p> <p>Contested discourses of a circular plastics economy in Europe: prioritizing material, economy, or society?, <i>Environmental Politics</i>, Volume 33, Issue 2.</p>	<p>Nur Gizem Yalcin took the lead in the research design and data collection of the manuscript. Erik Paredis provided substantial input in the development of the methods and analyses of the data. Melanie Jaeger-Erben provided substantial input during the interpretation of the results and both co-authors critically reviewed the text. Writing the first draft, finalisation, and submission of the manuscript is done by Nur Gizem Yalcin.</p>
<p>Yalçın N.G., Paredis E., Jaeger-Erben, M. (2025)</p> <p>Packaged science? Incumbent strategies of science capture from a power perspective, <i>Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions</i>, Volume 54, 100931, ISSN 2210-4224.</p>	<p>Nur Gizem Yalcin took the lead in the formulation of the scientific problem, development of key methods, integration of theoretical framework, collecting data, analysis of the data, writing the first draft, finalisation, and submission of the manuscript. Erik Paredis Melanie Jaeger-Erben provided input during the interpretation of the results and critically reviewed the text.</p>
<p>Yalçın, N.G. (2025)</p> <p>In search of a relational circular economy through art: the case of NaturArchy</p> <p>Under review (<i>Journal of Sustainability Science</i>, Springer)</p>	<p>Sole author</p>

Chapter 1

Introduction and Interpretive Research Design

1.1. Critical friends with the Circular Economy in a validity challenge period

The concept of the Circular Economy (CE) has become a central pillar of contemporary sustainability policy. As a response to the environmental impacts and economic inefficiencies of the dominant linear model, characterised by extraction, production, consumption, and disposal, a CE proposes a regenerative system in which resource loops are closed, waste is minimised, and value is retained through practices such as reuse, repair, remanufacturing, and recycling. It is frequently positioned as a transformative agenda that can address critical challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, material scarcity, and economic resilience (EC, 2020).

In recent years, the CE has established itself as an institutional priority in the European Union (EU), underpinning key strategies, including the Circular Economy Action Plan, Green Deal and most recently, the Clean Industrial Deal (EC, 2020a; EC, 2020b; EC, 2025). It is favoured for its potential to generate green jobs, secure access to critical materials, and decouple growth from environmental degradation (EC, 2020b). Industry 4.0 technologies have further advanced the CE's reach, enabling digital optimisation of circular flows (Pagoropoulos et al., 2017). Frameworks such as ReSOLVE and the 9R hierarchy have become instrumental in structuring circular strategies, policies, roadmaps, and business frameworks (European Commission, 2015; Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2013).

CE builds on a wide-ranging intellectual and practical history, incorporating concepts from both Western and non-Western traditions (Friant et al, 2020). The first phase of circularity thinking, spanning from 1945 to 1980, is referred to as the "preamble stage" (Blomsma and Brennan, 2017). This period was defined by growing global awareness of ecological limits and the adverse environmental impacts of industrial activity. Influential publications such as Hardin's *The Tragedy of the Commons* (1968), Meadows et al.'s *Limits to Growth* (1972), and Catton's *Overshoot* (1980) laid the intellectual foundation for future sustainability thinking by highlighting the finite nature of Earth's resources. Simultaneously, this era saw the emergence of diverse, often radical, economic paradigms that challenged mainstream growth-oriented models. These included Buddhist economics (Schumacher, 1973), ecological economics (Georgescu-Roegen, 1971; Daly, 1977), and political ecology (Gorz, 1980), each offering alternative visions of development rooted in sufficiency and equity. Kenneth Boulding's seminal essay, *The Economics of the Coming Spaceship Earth* (1966), stands out as an early precursor to CE thinking, introducing the concept of a "spaceman economy" in which waste outputs are continuously reintegrated as inputs, a vision that resonates strongly with contemporary circularity ideals. These early thinkers demonstrated a robust awareness of planetary boundaries and prefigured many of the core issues that continue to challenge the circular economy today, including decoupling, rebound effects, resource justice, and the imperative of sufficiency (Blomsma & Brennan, 2017; Reike et al., 2018).

In parallel, this era also saw the development of technical approaches to waste management, forming the basis for what has retrospectively been termed "Circularity 1.0" (Friant et al, 2020). These strategies largely approached waste as a discrete problem to be solved using end-of-pipe technologies and infrastructure-based solutions (Reike et al., 2018). While these innovations laid critical groundwork for modern recycling systems and waste stream management, they remained narrow in scope, focusing on material throughput rather than engagement with the growing recognition of underlying systemic problems.

The subsequent period, labelled Circularity 2.0 (1980–2010), corresponds to what Blomsma and Brennan (2017) describe as an “excitement period,” characterized by a surge of interest in reimagining waste as a resource. It was during this time that Pearce and Turner (1989) formally introduced the term “circular economy,” marking a conceptual turning point. Building on this foundation, numerous related frameworks and business models emerged, including industrial ecology (Frosch & Gallopoulos, 1989), industrial symbiosis (Chertow, 2000), and product-service systems (Goedkoop et al., 1999). Drawing inspiration from ecological processes, these approaches sought to redesign industrial systems to mimic natural ecosystems by closing loops between production and consumption. However, despite their ecological rhetoric, these innovations often unfolded within a market-driven paradigm dominated by neoliberal governance models, emphasizing efficiency and economic viability over systemic transformation (Reike et al, 2018).

Although Circularity 2.0 introduced important technological and operational innovations, it fell short of engaging deeply with critical socio-ecological concerns (Friant et al, 2020). Key issues such as environmental justice, sufficiency, and the rebound effect received limited attention. Most of the efforts during this period were directed toward optimizing resource use and increasing efficiency within existing economic systems, rather than challenging the structures driving unsustainable production and consumption.

The third phase, Circularity 3.0 (1990–present), marks a shift toward more integrated and systemic approaches to resource management, production, and consumption (Friant et al, 2020). This period aligns with the post-Rio (1992) sustainability agenda and has seen the rise of a range of CE-related frameworks that link ecological design with long-term societal goals. Influential concepts emerging during this phase include cradle to cradle (McDonough & Braungart, 2002), the performance economy (Stahel, 2010), and natural capitalism (Hawken et al., 1999). These models advocate for a transition from linear to regenerative systems, emphasising sustainability, circular design principles, and system-wide thinking.

However, from 2013 onwards, the concept of the CE has also entered what Blomsma and Brennan (2017) term a “validity challenge” period. This period has been marked by substantial critical social sciences research that examined CE’s theoretical foundations, principles, and implementation at micro, meso, macro levels (Ghisselini et al, 2016, Blomsma and Brennan, 2017) reviewed different definitions and conceptualisations (Kircherr et al, 2017, Merli et al, 2018, Reike et al, 2018), explored various ways CE relates to sustainability (Geissdeorfer et al, 2017, Murray et al, 2017), and brought substantial criticism in the overlooked social and political aspects (Hobson et al, 2016).

Critical social scientists highlighted how CE discourses in the EU tend to depoliticise both policy and industrial interventions (Niskanen et al., 2020), as well as the roles of consumers (Hobson & Lynch, 2016), and recycling practices (Vonk, 2018). This depoliticisation is often linked to the way CE is framed, as a managerial, technocratic, and seemingly neutral issue (Niskanen et al., 2020). Such representations are criticised for reinforcing CE as an eco-modernist project (Fitch-Roy et al., 2019), effectively sidelining more transformative approaches that might challenge the dominant social, economic and environmental paradigms (Gregson et al., 2015; Hobson & Lynch, 2016).

If discussions around the CE continue to rely on idealised notions of eco-modernism without incorporating a robust socio-political and ecological justice perspective, the concept risks losing both its social credibility and broader systemic relevance (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2021). It might lead to relocation of environmental problems across different geographies and timescales, reinforcing growing inequalities and injustices, rather than offering genuine solutions (Hobson & Lynch, 2016).

To avoid this outcome in the validity challenge period, this thesis aims to open up a critical socio-political debate to challenge, question, and pluralise the EU circularity narratives, policy, and practice through an interpretative lens grounded in discourse and power analysis. It adopts the stance of a "critical friend" to the CE: one that is supportive of the CE's aspirations but also committed to asking difficult questions about its assumptions, implications, and limitations. It is a position that values the CE's potential to inspire and catalyse transformative change while also recognising that its success depends not only on its wider adaptation, but also on the kinds of economic, social, and political choices that underpin it. To take up the role of a critical friend means remaining attentive to both the promises and the pitfalls of circularity. It involves deeper engagement with the political, ethical, and social dimensions of circularity transitions and asking what is at stake in how it is framed, which strategies are prioritised, and which alternatives may be overlooked. This is particularly important at a time when the CE is becoming increasingly institutionalised and when its narrative is shaping regulatory frameworks, public and private investment decisions, and collective visions of the future. In this context, the following part examines how the CE has developed mostly as a depoliticised policy agenda in the EU, which reinforced a technocratic focus and overlooked the socio-political aspects. This sets the stage for a deeper engagement with the socio-political dimensions of CE transitions and the approach taken in this thesis.

1.2. Opening-up the depoliticised circularity in the EU

Despite the transformative potential that the CE aspires to embody, its dominant articulation within the EU policy frameworks reflects a significantly depoliticised agenda. This version of the CE, while rhetorically ambitious, often maintains continuity with existing power structures, economic frameworks, and governance logics, thus falls into the risk of amplifying existing socio-ecological injustices (Ashton et al, 2022). The heroic narrative of the CE (Lazarevic and Valve, 2017) that widely circulates in EU strategies and business discourse rests on a vision of systemic change without conflict, in which diverse stakeholders align seamlessly around innovation, competitiveness, and sustainability, and ecological transition occurs without disruption to incumbent institutions. This depoliticised framing manifests itself in several ways. For the purpose of this dissertation and based on the literature on the politics of the CE (e.g. Hobson & Lynch, 2016; Kovacic et al., 2020; Friant et al., 2020; Leipold, 2021; Ampe, 2022; Simoens, 2022; Hendriks, 2024), these can be summarised in the following points: the promotion of a win-win agenda, the sidelining of contested knowledge, a reliance on techno-managerial solutions, a privileging of market-based mechanisms, and the neglect of socio-ecological justice concerns.

First, the CE in the EU showcases a win-win agenda, emphasising the potential for forming policy alliances by shifting the narrative from focusing on "trade-offs," "constraints," and "limitations" to highlighting the creation of "synergies" and "opportunities" (Leipold, 2021). By emphasising the continuous use of resources

through principles like recycling, remanufacturing, and reuse, the CE aims to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation. It transforms uncertainties surrounding waste management into opportunities, enables the creation of new business models with innovative designs and maintains the value of materials within the economy. The win-win agenda of the CE removes the "buts" and "ifs", and instead, emphasises the potential benefits it presents (Kovacic et al, 2020).

Second, this win-win logic is maintained by sidelining contested knowledge and uncertainty, for example, on rebound effects, absolute decoupling and growth. The feasibility of achieving decoupling where economic growth occurs alongside an absolute reduction in environmental pressures, is challenged by many (e.g. Hickel and Kallis, 2019; Bauwens, 2021). The empirical evidence supporting absolute decoupling is limited, and relying solely on technological advancements and efficiency improvements may be insufficient to achieve the desired environmental outcomes (Hartley et al, 2020). This scepticism aligns with critiques suggesting that efficiency gains often lead to the rebound effect, where reduced resource use per unit leads to increased overall consumption, thereby offsetting environmental benefits (Zink and Geyer, 2017). These structural limitations challenge the CE's promises but are often absent from the EU's official narratives.

Third, the circularity in the EU is deeply embedded in a techno-managerial, eco-modernist rationality. An ecomodernist agenda posits that through technological advancements and improved management practices, such as eco-innovation and the development of circular business models aimed at enhancing resource efficiency and reducing waste, economic growth can be decoupled from environmental degradation (Leipold, 2021). The emphasis on technological solutions depoliticises circularity efforts by framing environmental issues and economic reorganisations as technical, straightforward and neutral problems rather than matters requiring political and societal engagement (Niskanen et al., 2020). It also risks displacing problems across geographies and time, rather than addressing their root causes (Hobson & Lynch, 2016).

Fourth, the CE has been portrayed as offering a solution that balances economic efficiencies with ecological concerns that will be driven by market principles (Mah, 2021). Private industry is seen as a dynamic site of innovation and entrepreneurial opportunity, expected to generate circular value through competitive advantage, economic incentives or self-regulation, with public authorities playing more of a supporting role (Volker et al., 2020; Kirchherr et al., 2018). Citizens are framed fundamentally as consumers or users of reconfigured and partially dematerialised circular models (Hobson and Lynch, 2016). This perspective reduces complex socio-environmental challenges to individual responsibility rather than addressing underlying systemic factors. By limiting the role of individuals to making sustainable choices within existing consumption patterns, the CE framework also overlooks the potential for citizens to be active agents of systemic change (Rask, 2022).

Fifth, a techno-managerial and eco-modernist CE that relies on market mechanisms and adapts a narrow focus on technical fixes neglects the broader socio-economic-ecological transformations required for genuine transitions. CE models lack a strong justice component, failing to address how the benefits and costs of circular practices are distributed across different communities (Schroder et al., 2020). The current depoliticised, economy-first model of circularity has instilled social and environmental burdens disproportionately across the globe, with countries of the Global South and vulnerable communities often

bearing the highest costs and receiving the least benefits (Mathai et al., 2021). Circular justice often aligns with neoliberal approaches that prioritise the unrestricted pursuit of individual self-interest, job creation, the safeguarding of private property rights, and the freedom of personal choice rather than focusing on issues related to recognitional, distributive or procedural justice (Aston et al., 2022).

Taken together, these five dimensions constitute what can be termed a depoliticised circularity: a strategic construction of the CE that maintains the appearance of consensus while foreclosing deeper questions of power, politics, and transformation. This agenda envisions a transformative yet unspecified future, offering little insight into how to challenge established institutional structures, path dependencies, and systemic lock-ins (Simoens et al, 2022), risking consolidating the very systems they purport to transform (Pansera et al., 2021).

This thesis challenges the narrow, technocratic visions in depoliticised CE agendas and joins the critical social science voices in the need to re-politicise the dominant technocratic approaches, to avoid perpetuating the socio-ecological injustices, and to catalyse CE's transformative potential. Genovese and Pansera (2020) state that the “biggest shortcoming of the CE discourse is represented by its apolitical framing” and call for “opening up a debate to deconstruct the increasingly hegemonic discourse of CE based on a technocratic approach and reconstruct it by embedding normative and political dimensions” (p.1). They position CE at a “crossroad” that currently aligns with technocratic eco-modernism but underline that there is not only an opportunity, but a pressing need to harness the transformative appeal embedded in the CE towards new paradigms that acknowledge both environmental constraints and social boundaries to growth.

Responsible Innovation scholars Inigo and Blok (2019) look at how processes of anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness can support re-politicisation and building socio-ethical foundations of CE. Several scholars warn that unless CE is addressed in all its complexity as a socio-political concept, it might face unintended consequences on vulnerable people and communities that replicate or reinforce socio-ecological injustice patterns of discrimination, alienation, and exploitation along racial, class, gender, and other social lines, for example using Global South as a resource extraction and waste disposal frontier (Zwiers et al, 2020; Mah, 2021; Friant et al, 2023; Schroeder, 2021). Other rich insights come from environmental governance studies (Friant, Vermeulen, and Salomone 2020; Korhonen, Honkasalo, and Seppälä, 2018), STS field (Kovacic, Strand, and Völker 2019) and post-normal science scholars (Giampietro and Funtowicz 2020).

In their short commentary on politicising the CE, Pansera et al (2021) highlight the critical role of re-politicisation in transitioning to just and responsible futures, stating that successful transitions towards a sustainable CE not only depend on new technologies but also on the reconfiguration of governance and knowledge processes. They underline the uncertainty and complexity surrounding opening- up the socio-political dynamics of the CE:

“We are very much aware that engaging in a re-politicisation of the CE would also entail the generation of what Rayner (2012) defined as ‘uncomfortable knowledge’ associated with irreducible uncertainty and epistemic pluralism, especially when dealing with ‘wicked problems’. But we also think that promoting responsible science and innovation requires engaging with political controversies and conflict negotiation.” (Pansera et al, 2021).

In this thesis, I took the challenge to re-politicise the CE by engaging with uncomfortable knowledge and asking difficult questions, with an aim to challenge technocratic approaches, avoid the reinforcement of socio-ecological injustices, and unlock CE's capacity for genuine transformation: Whose visions of the CE dominate, and why? Which assumptions underpin them? What alternative visions are being excluded? What is the role of science in such a transition? Which stakeholder groups are included, in which roles, and which are excluded and why? Who wins and who loses from these transitions? Re-politicisation in this thesis has been approached as “opening up” the narrow, depoliticised agenda of the EU CE by bringing attention to the socio-political dynamics. I use Stirling's (2008) “opening-up” as revealing and engaging with plural perspectives, uncertainties, complexities, and contestations, resisting dominant technocratic, unitary, prescriptive agendas, and reconfiguring the CE as a socio-political space of contestation, imagination, and transformation. In the next section, I turn to discourse and power analysis to open-up CE as a process of socio-political reconfiguration in the next section.

1.3. Socio-political transitions to CE

1.3.1. Discourses and politics

In the context of circular transitions, the politics of change are not limited to institutional structures or material interests, they are also embedded in the ways problems and solutions are framed through language. Discourse, in this sense, is not merely descriptive but constitutive: it shapes what is seen as problematic, what kinds of interventions are considered legitimate, who is positioned as responsible, and what forms of knowledge or action are legitimised (Hajer, 1995; Dryzek, 2005; Fischer & Gottweis, 2012). Discourse analysis thus offers a vital lens for understanding the socio-political dynamics of the CE, particularly as the concept becomes more embedded in policy and institutional practice.

In this thesis, discourse is understood in line with Hajer (1995: 44) as “an ensemble of ideas, concepts, and categorisations that are produced, reproduced, and transformed in a particular set of practices”. Discourses are powerful structuring forces in articulating competing visions of the future, coordinating collective action, and influencing the perceived legitimacy of governance approaches (Lawhon & Murphy, 2012; Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016). The discursive politics of CE are especially salient given its contested nature. As the CE travels across sectors and scales—from EU strategies to industry roadmaps and local initiatives—it is continuously reframed through competing discourses that reflect different assumptions about sustainability, governance, transformation, and human-nature relations (Feindt & Oels, 2005; Hajer & Versteeg, 2005; Wittmayer et al., 2019).

Different actors, governments, industry groups, civil society organisations, and researchers, draw on distinct *storylines* to frame what the CE means, why it is needed, and how it should be pursued. These *storylines* do more than describe; they create coherent narratives, enabling coalitions of actors to align around particular interpretations and policy agendas (Hajer, 1995; van Hulst, 2012). Such *discourse coalitions* play a powerful role in politics and governance. When a particular discourse gains traction, it can not only shape institutional priorities, regulatory instruments, and funding structures, but also marginalise alternative interpretations that do not align with dominant storylines (Leipold & Winkel, 2016). In the context of CE, this has led to the institutionalisation of specific visions, particularly those centred on technological innovation and economic

growth, while sidelining more radical imaginaries focused on sufficiency, justice, or post-growth transitions (Valenzuela & Böhm, 2017; Hobson & Lynch, 2016).

Yet, as Hajer and Versteeg (2005) emphasise, discourse analysis is not merely about mapping competing narratives. It is also a means of uncovering how power operates in determining why some discourses achieve hegemony while others are excluded from societal imaginations and policymaking. Through the lens of discourse, CE emerges not simply as a sustainability framework but as a political project: one that configures the boundaries of legitimate debate, defines the terms of transformation, and influences the directionality of socio-technical change (Voß & Freeman, 2016; Stirling, 2008).

Understanding the CE as a discursive field thus requires sustained attention to how language constructs meaning, how coalitions are formed around certain interpretations, and how these interpretations become institutionalised. As the CE continues to evolve, so too must the critical scrutiny of how it is being narrated, by whom, and to what ends. These insights set the stage for the next section, which examines how *power* operates not only in discourse but in the broader political dynamics of circular transitions.

1.3.2. Power and politics

While discourse reveals how meanings of the CE are constructed and contested, understanding the politics of CE transitions also requires attention to how power operates through institutions, actors, and systems of knowledge. An actor's capacity to establish themselves as a powerful figure within a given political debate is shaped by continuously making strategic decisions about whether, when, where, and how to align with a particular position (Leipold and Winkel, 2016). Actors exercise reinforcing, innovative, or transformative power to either maintain, adapt, or radically alter production and consumption systems (Avelino, 2011).

Power is conceptualised in unnumerable ways however, this thesis builds on two primary conceptualisations of power (Sovacool and Brisbois, 2019): agent-centred power, which views power as the capacity of specific actors to influence others through authority, coercion, or persuasion. It assumes that power is something that actors (e.g., corporations and policymakers) possess and exercise to achieve their objectives. And structure-centred power, which emphasises that power is embedded in institutions, norms, and systems, shaping behaviour in ways that are often invisible or taken for granted. Rather than being directly wielded by individuals, power operates through rules, laws, and social conventions that constrain and enable actions.

These two forms of power are not mutually exclusive; rather, they interact in complex ways. In this thesis, I use Lukes' three faces of power as a comprehensive framework that shows how agent- and structure-centred power operates in entanglement within the political and social contexts. In his seminal work *Power: A Radical View* (1974), Lukes introduces a three-dimensional view that captures the visible, hidden, and invisible aspects of power. The first face of power refers to observable decision-making, where power is exercised when an actor successfully influences decisions in open conflicts, such as in legislative debates or policy-making processes. The second face of power involves agenda-setting and non-decision-making, where powerful actors prevent certain issues from even reaching the decision-making arena, often by controlling institutional rules or public discourse. Lukes expands this further with the third face of power, which

emphasises ideological control and preference shaping, where power operates through influencing the beliefs, values, and norms that shape individuals' perceptions. By integrating these three dimensions, Lukes' framework provides a nuanced understanding of power, highlighting both overt political struggles and the more subtle, systemic ways in which power is employed.

All in all, this thesis examines how power is exercised and reproduced in the framing, governance, epistemic authority, and institutionalisation of CE in Europe. By tracing how certain actors and ideas gain prominence while others are marginalised, it shows the CE as a socio-political project, one shaped by asymmetries of power to define problems, influence agendas, reinforce interests, and determine outcomes. Transitions, in this view, are arenas of contestation in which social, economic, and ecological futures are actively negotiated.

1.4. Research questions

This thesis opens up the critical socio-political debate to repoliticise the CE with an aim to challenge, question, and pluralise the debate, to support the CE's transformative potential, and keep it socio-ecologically relevant and credible in the ongoing validity challenge period. It emphasises the need to engage with a plurality of ideas, discourses, and alternative perspectives, critically interrogating the underlying assumptions and power dynamics that shape CE governance. It asks the following over-arching question, investigated through three sub-questions:

ORQ: How can the circular economy be opened up as a site of socio-political reconfiguration?

In this thesis, “opening-up” is used as a way to uncover and engage with pluralities, uncertainties, complexities, and conflicts (Stirling, 2008). It involves *challenging* the prevailing eco-modernist orientation that emphasises consensus and market-driven solutions, often at the expense of acknowledging contestation, structural inequality, and power struggles (Pansera, 2021) and *reconfiguring* the CE as a socio-political space of contestation, imagination and transformation (Friant, 2024). In doing so, the thesis emphasises the need to engage with a diversity of ideas, discourses, and alternative perspectives, critically interrogating the underlying assumptions and power dynamics that shape CE governance. In this thesis, I particularly focus on *discursive opening, epistemic and institutional opening, and ontological and ethical opening with three sub-questions*. I study these extensive interrelated openings in specific ways, addressing the research calls from various scholars as briefly covered below.

RQ1: What are the different discourses on the CE in the EU? How can they be critically analysed and understood?

RQ1 targets the *discursive opening* of the CE by pluralising its meanings and interrogating the political visions embedded in language, metaphors, and narratives. Several influential research papers have been published in the CE field with a focus on discourses. Friant et al, (2020; 2021) developed a discourse typology on the CE based on the level of complexity and capacity of capitalism to overcome resource limits and decouple ecological degradation from economic growth. Simoens (2022) looked at the discursive dynamics that shaped German Packaging Act in “trading radical for incremental change”. These scholars,

among others (Ampe et al, 2019; Leipold et al, 2022) called for further use of discursive lens to disrupt the win-win, neutral approach to CE and show contestation (Kovacic et al, 2020), pluralise CE imaginaries (Friant et al, 2020) and demonstrate the discursive directionality (Leipold, 2021).

Chapter 2 addresses these calls with a discourse analysis approach to the case study of plastics. It explores the political nature of the circular plastics economy in Europe, focusing on contested narratives that influence policy and societal perspectives. Using discourse analysis, it identifies three divergent discourses based on their primary focus: material efficiency; externalities of the plastics economy; and socio-ecological implications. The analysis reveals how the framing of problems, proposed solutions, and actor positioning reflect diverse priorities, assumptions, and power dynamics. Each discourse brings into view a different set of priorities for the future, assumptions (e.g. consumers' role and human-nature relations), and actor coalitions, and each implies a different directionality for policy and practice. Together, they reflect the underlying diversity of meaning within the CE and the political struggle over how circularity is enacted.

RQ2: How do certain interpretations become dominant, and why?

RQ2 targets **epistemic and institutional opening** by looking at the role of science in political decision-making mechanisms and unpacks the structural mechanisms that close down alternative pathways. In “Lessons, narratives, and research directions for a sustainable circular economy” (Leipold et al, 2022), 54 CE academics from social sciences, natural sciences and engineering disciplines developed a shared research agenda, including a priority area on the role of science in supporting CE development. They called for investigating the role of CE knowledge in political contexts, when questions of negotiation and decision-making power are involved.

Chapter 3 addresses these calls by illuminating how power operates through epistemic authority to close down alternative visions and reinforce dominant techno-economic pathways. It explores RQ2 from a power perspective with a detailed case study of the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation. It dives into how packaging industry incumbents target science for policymaking mechanisms to strategically close down the CE debates to manufacture consent for techno-managerial solutions, positioning them as common sense, while dismissing alternative pathways as radical or unrealistic. It shows how by embedding their interests in political institutions and legal frameworks, and controlling access to key resources and data, incumbents ensure that transitions proceed in ways that preserve their economic and political dominance. The study highlights how these actors exploit visible, hidden, and invisible power dynamics to maintain dominant approaches to CE and marginalise transformative ideas. It further refers to the institutional, discursive, economic, and regulatory structures that reinforce incumbent dominance and calls for greater scrutiny of incumbency dynamics and proactive measures to counteract science capture in policymaking.

RQ3: What are the alternatives to dominant approaches to CE? Specifically, how can relational thinking inspire alternative forms of CE?

RQ3 targets **ontological and ethical opening** by exploring relational approaches as one of the many alternatives that reimagines CE. Many academics have called for and proposed alternatives, such as a

“circular humansphere” (Schroder et al, 2020), a “careful circularity” (Morow and Davies, 2021), a “sustainable circular society” (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2020; Friant et al, 2020), a “convivial CE” (Genovese and Pansera, 2020), and a “post-growth CE” (Bauwens 2021) as more inclusive, democratic, and eco-centric approaches to circularity. Recently, Jaeger-Erben et al (2025) called for exploring CE as a relational challenge, reimagining relationships within society, among businesses, and between society and the natural world.

Chapter 4 addresses these calls through an exploratory approach to relationality with a case study of the NaturArchy sci-art project. It delves into how relational thinking can serve as an alternative to dominant CE approaches by bridging human-nature divides and deepening the understanding of complexity knowledge and action within CE. Through an analysis of the NaturArchy project, the study illustrates how relational approaches challenge reductionist paradigms that rely on quantification, control, and techno-managerial solutions, instead fostering a more integrated and justice-oriented perspective on human-nature interdependencies. By integrating relational ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics, the research highlights the potential of art-science collaborations to disrupt hierarchical worldviews, incorporate diverse knowledge systems, recognise non-human agency, and embrace uncertainty. In doing so, it advocates for a relational CE that moves beyond the growth-driven and extractivist logic of mainstream CE models, promoting a system based on interdependence, care, and socio-ecological justice.

1.5. Interpretive research design

In this thesis, I adopt an interpretive research philosophy grounded in post-positivist and constructivist traditions (Hajer, 1995; Yanow & Schwartz-Shea, 2015). A defining characteristic of interpretivist approaches is their ground in an anti-foundationalist ontology to varying degrees (Bevir and Rhodes, 2002). Within this tradition, researchers assert that reality is not something “out there to be discovered” but constructed through social or discursive processes. This perspective holds that social phenomena cannot be understood in isolation from the interpretations assigned to them, instead, these interpretations actively shape outcomes. The meanings attached to social phenomena are fundamental and can only be comprehended within specific discourses or contexts. Therefore, research should prioritise identifying these discourses or contexts and analysing the interpretations and meanings they attribute to social phenomena. This understanding aligns with the concept of the “double hermeneutic,” where individuals interpret their world, and researchers interpret these interpretations (Furlong and Marsh, 2010).

Interpretivist scientists acknowledge that they operate within particular discourses and contexts. This awareness of the social embeddedness of knowledge brings responsibility in engaging with reflexivity (Smith & Stirling, 2013). Reflexivity involves actively reflecting on and engaging with how researchers' own processes of understanding influence the knowledge claims made in research. It also involves identifying and comprehending the context, including which concerns are considered, by whom, and for what reasons (Stirling, 2006).

Ampe et al. (2025) differentiate between *reflectiveness* and *reflexivity* in sustainability transitions research, building on Goeminne (2012) and Stirling (2006). *Reflectiveness* acknowledges the inherent imperfections and biases in knowledge production due to unintended influences in research design and execution. It

encourages multi-, inter-, and transdisciplinary approaches to anticipate and address the broader societal implications of technological innovations. While achieving complete neutrality is aspirational, reflectiveness aims to integrate diverse knowledge for a comprehensive understanding of technology's societal impact.

Reflexivity, on the other hand, focuses on the researcher's embeddedness in their socio-cultural context. It challenges the idea of objective science by recognising that personal values and positionality shape research outcomes. Reflexivity involves introspection, prompting researchers to examine how their perspectives influence their work. Reflexivity acknowledges that complete neutrality is unattainable and instead promotes openness and modesty in navigating the complexities of knowledge production. Unlike reflectiveness, which sees situatedness as a challenge to neutrality, reflexivity sees it as a fundamental and constitutive aspect of scientific knowledge (Goeminne, 2012).

While reflexivity can be achieved to some extent, it does not offer an objective, detached meta-perspective from which to approach matters neutrally (Stirling, 2006). Engaging with diverse frameworks, considering various stakeholder perspectives, and undertaking reflexive exercises can enhance reflexive awareness. However, the inherent incompleteness of reflexivity cannot be eliminated, though it can be encountered and navigated; it cannot be overcome simply by acquiring more knowledge. Unlike the reflective approach, which treats reflexivity as a structured, conscious, and organised activity, true reflexivity resists such instrumentalisation and demands humility and openness (Ampe et al, 2025).

Acknowledging the responsibility of reflexivity in the spirit of humility and openness, the following section engages with the implications of an interpretive approach to my research design: the context of the C-PlaNeT project and consortium, and techniques of generating data.

1.6. Implications of the interpretive approach on the research design

1.6.1. C-PlaNeT context

My interpretive research approach has been shaped not only by epistemological commitments but also by the interdisciplinary context in which this research took place. This work was conducted within the C-PlaNeT (Circular Plastics Network for Training), which is a project funded by the European Union in the framework of the H2020 Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions – Innovative Training Networks (H2020 MSCA ITN). C-PlaNeT is a consortium of universities, research institutions and companies located in Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, Austria, United Kingdom, Switzerland, Denmark and Greece. C-PlaNeT aspires that a “sustainable future for plastics is possible when all the different actors in the value chain collaborate, interact, challenge and complement each other.”¹ It aims to decouple plastics from fossil resources, design for circularity in terms of both materials and products, involve consumers as stakeholders, develop efficient recycling technologies, and apply systems thinking in overarching circular strategies.

The C-PlaNeT consortium is largely composed of natural scientists, engineers, and industrial partners with a technically oriented approach to CE. I have realised that technology is viewed as a neutral tool, with its

¹ <https://www.c-planet.eu/objectives>

societal impact determined solely by how individuals or societies choose to use it to advance circularity. In this view, ethical or social consequences are attributed to the actions and intentions of users rather than being inherent to the technology itself and are consequently left outside the discussion. It becomes the role of social scientists to address political, economic, psychological, and other societal barriers to ensure that technologies achieve their full potential. As one of the three early-stage researchers with a background in interpretive social science, I occupied a somewhat unusual position: simultaneously embedded within and intellectually distant from the dominant logics that structured the project's technical orientation and assumed role of a political scientist. Rather than being a neutral backdrop, this context profoundly shaped how I approached the research and what it meant to study the CE critically from within.

Being situated in this environment gave me access to an insider's view of how the CE was being defined, operationalised, and institutionalised in the name of technological innovation and industrial transformation. Social and political questions, such as justice, responsibility, and governance, were often backgrounded in favour of technical solutions such as chemical recycling or digital tracking systems. These silences and framings became valuable empirical material, revealing which narratives gained traction, which were marginalised, and how scientific authority and innovation agendas were organised around specific visions of circularity.

In this context, starting my PhD with a discourse analysis in the circular plastics economy to foster the debate for plural perspectives, visions on the problems, causes, proposed solutions, and future imaginations was a good first step from my perspective. Diving deeper into the assumptions behind different discourses, actors' positioning in the debate, and the directionality of these choices to policy and practice, opened up the critical debate and created reflexive moments in the positionality of my own and that of many other researchers in the consortium. Following up on that with a power lens to dive deeper into the interests and strategies of different actors brought forward interesting political discussions. These moments were particularly shared after the presentation of my PhD research in Eindhoven (October 2022) on the politics of CE and different discourses, followed by a role-play workshop on different discourses identified in Chapter 2. The role-playing workshop encouraged members of the consortium to think more critically about controversies, power, and interests surrounding the CE and to see situations from a different perspective. Openness to learning, curiosity, mutual respect, and trust among members played critical roles in these reflexive engagements.

The C-PlaNeT context sharpened my core motivations for undertaking this research: to open up the CE to a greater plurality of ideas and values; to challenge the technocratic tendencies of CE knowledge and governance; to address the power dynamics embedded in institutional transitions; and to advocate for more inclusive and democratically accountable societal and political decision-making. The interpretive approach allowed me to hold space for complexity and contradiction, rather than collapsing these into consensus. It enabled me to surface the assumptions, exclusions, and contestations that underlie CE transitions in the EU, and to do so from a position of engaged critique.

1.6.2. Techniques for generating data

My interpretive research directly influenced how I generated empirical material. I followed an abductive logic, which is characterised by an iterative and recursive process where researchers move back and forth between empirical data and theoretical frameworks to refine their understanding (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012). Unlike deductive reasoning, which derives specific conclusions from general premises, or inductive reasoning, which formulates generalisations from specific observations, abductive logic begins with puzzling or surprising observations and seeks plausible explanations (Peirce, 1931-1958; Peirce, 1992). In the context of interpretive research, abduction ensures a non-linear and flexible approach that adapts as new insights emerge. It encourages openness and reflexivity, which are crucial for navigating the complexity of qualitative data (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). The data collection methods in this approach are designed to capture deep, contextual insights and involve engaging directly with participants' lived experiences. In my PhD, I used four methods to collect data:

- 1. Interviews:** I conducted semi-structured interviews to allow participants to express their views on their own terms. This approach provided rich, in-depth data that captured personal insights and experiences.
- 2. Document Analysis:** I examined policy documents, position papers, reports, and other relevant documents to uncover the meanings and narratives constructed within specific political or organizational contexts. This helped to gain a deeper understanding of the context in which these narratives were formed.
- 3. Media Analysis:** I critically examined media content, such as news articles, panel debates and broadcasts to explore how particular topics were framed and interpreted within public discourses. This method helped me identify dominant narratives and discursive patterns that shaped public perceptions.
- 4. Field Notes:** Throughout my research, I recorded my reflections, observations, and experiences. This introspective process enhanced my reflexivity and helped me develop a deeper contextual understanding of the study.

The data collection processes for each chapter started with media and document analysis to get an overview of the topic and identify influential actors. For Chapters 2 and 5, this continued with semi-structured, online, recorded, confidential interviews, starting with the identified actors and continuing with the snowballing approach. After completing a round of interviews, I revisited the documents to help contextualise and better understand some of the interviewees' statements. Additionally, I attended various public and private events, including meetings, workshops, conferences, and seminars about CE and sustainability transitions. During these events, I observed how different actors and researchers discussed these topics, recording my observations in field notes for later analysis. By combining these four qualitative methods, I developed an *intertextual* perspective that informed the analyses presented in Chapters 2, 3, and 5. I preferred the term *intertextuality* over *triangulation* because triangulation involves using two known data points to determine a

third unknown point, aiming to reveal an objective "truth" (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012). In contrast, as an interpretive researcher, I focused on exploring diverse understandings of the subject under study. I began by identifying variations in interpretations and then analysed these differences intertextually across various methods of data collection, diverse theories and frameworks, and input from multiple researchers (such as peers) (Schwartz-Shea, 2006).

Reflecting on my abductive approach further, I can give the study in Chapter 3 as an example. While conducting semi-structured interviews for the study on Chapter 2, our conversation with a business association representative piqued my interest. She was repeatedly positioning the industry association as an upholder of scientific knowledge:

"In *-name of the business association-* we produce facts, the European Commission always come to us for data. (...) We are very proud that we produce the facts. It helps a lot within the discussions with the European Commission, this credibility. (...) So, we have been influential in a positive way, I would say, because we create lots of facts and figures and data and studies. We bring that perspective to the discussion in an open, transparent way."

The interviewee framed the association's role as one of scientific credibility, contrasting this with policymakers and civil society actors who were dismissed as lacking rigour. This interview created a new lens for me to look at the policy discussions surrounding the CE in terms of agency given to the industry and the business actors, their positioning in these debates, and how scientific authority is constructed and mobilised in CE policy debates.

Soon after, I observed similar dynamics in panel discussions and public commentary surrounding the EU's Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), where industry actors frequently accused the Commission of being "unscientific," presenting their own commissioned studies as more robust alternatives. This recurring narrative led me to investigate how science is instrumentalised by incumbent actors to shape CE policy, a phenomenon I later analysed as a form of science capture in Chapter 4.

To make sense of these dynamics, I drew on literature that critically examines the political use of expertise. Two texts were particularly influential: Saltelli et al.'s (2022) *Science, the Endless Frontier of Regulatory Capture* and Laurens' (2018) *Lobbyists and Bureaucrats in Brussels*. These helped frame the strategies I was observing as more than lobbying: they involved layered forms of epistemic, institutional, and political influence.

In this way, Chapter 3 emerged not through a linear design but from a surprising empirical moment that prompted sustained theoretical and empirical inquiry. It exemplifies the abductive and interpretive logic underpinning this thesis, a continuous, reflective movement between fieldwork and theory to make sense of complex, contested realities within the politics of CE governance.

This chapter has established the conceptual and methodological groundwork for the thesis by critically engaging with the CE as both a policy ideal and a contested socio-political project. I have positioned this research as a "critical friend" to the CE, committed to its transformative potential, yet attentive to the

assumptions, exclusions, and power dynamics that shape its implementation. The interpretive research design and methodological commitments outlined here provide the foundation for the empirical chapters that follow. Chapter 2 investigates the discursive politics of the European circular plastics economy, identifying competing narratives and the visions of circularity they promote. Chapter 3 explores how incumbent actors strategically stabilise dominant approaches and foreclose alternative pathways. It deepens this inquiry by analysing how scientific authority is shaped and mobilised in the form of science capture in the case of the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation. Chapter 4 turns toward alternative imaginaries, exploring how art-science collaborations such as NaturArchy can inspire relational and justice-oriented visions of circularity. Finally, Chapter 5 brings these threads together, offering a critical synthesis of the findings and reflecting on their broader theoretical, methodological, and policy implications. In tracing these diverse yet interconnected perspectives, the thesis contributes to re-politicising circularity by opening space for critical debate and rethinking the CE as a dynamic socio-political project. It calls for an approach that embraces complexity, foregrounds power and plurality, and cultivates more inclusive, reflexive, and transformative pathways toward circular futures.

Chapter 2

Contested discourses of a circular plastics economy in Europe: prioritising material, economy, or society?

Abstract

The European Union has made the development of a circular economy one of the central ambitions of its Green Deal, in which plastics are a defined priority. The current policies, however, have drawn criticism that the narrow focus on techno-innovation opportunities and economic growth falls short of addressing multifaceted socio-ecological challenges, overlooks trade-offs between proposed solutions, and conceals conflicts of interest among different actors. This paper contributes to opening up the critical political debate on the circular plastics economy using discourse analysis. Looking at how arguments are framed, which priorities are defined, and how actors take positions, we identify three circular plastics economy discourses in Europe: 'Plastic fantastic' (material-focused), 'Circular economy will fly us to the moon' (plastics economy-focused), and 'Even plastic flowers are dead in this system' (socio-ecological systems-focused). Our paper demonstrates that the circular plastics economy is inherently political and is actively imagined, built, and created through discursive mechanisms.

This chapter is published as *Yalçın N.G., Paredis E. & Jaeger-Erben M. (2023) Contested discourses of a circular plastics economy in Europe: prioritising material, economy, or society?, Environmental Politics, Volume 33, Issue 2.*

2.1. Introduction

Plastics are omnipresent in today's world. Because of their durability, lightweight and flexibility in design, they became the primary choice for a broad range of applications. But the rapid increase in global plastic use over the last decades has also drawn wide attention to the negative impacts of plastics, such as marine pollution and their carbon footprint. The European Union's (EU) ambition of developing a circular economy (CE) by 2050, where plastic is one of the priority areas, might open alternative ways to address these concerns but also evokes a series of new questions.

CE has become “an indispensable part of the new EU industrial strategy” in the Green Deal (EC, 2020) and gained its place in policy, business, and academia as a collection of ideas and strategies. It has been shaped within a nexus thinking in the EU, where a win-win logic for both economy and environment has framed challenges as opportunities and waste as resources (Kovacic et al, 2020). Although proponents of the CE argue that this way of thinking leads to increased efficiencies, critics problematise the reductionist approach that results in trading transformative agendas for incremental change (Simoens and Leipold, 2021; Ampe et al, 2019). It is argued that the focus on opportunities for synergy silences the trade-offs and leaves room for simplistic ideas driven by techno-managerialism (Genovese and Pansera, 2021).

The uncontroversy created through the urgency of the environmental crisis and the mandate of continued economic growth promotes a depoliticised CE where societal and political implications, such as issues of justice and power relations, are often overlooked (Hobson and Lynch, 2016). However, in the last few years, the social sciences literature on CE has brought increasing evidence that socio-political dynamics make a substantial difference in which circular economy and society becomes possible (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2021). It is highlighted that embracing the complexity of the CE is crucial for opening up room for diverging perspectives and promoting more just and responsible futures (Friant et al, 2020).

Several scholars looked at diverging discourses on the CE. Such analyses are significant because they politicise the debate through demonstrating the plurality of ideas about what the CE entails and showing how discursive rationalities give directionality to outcomes, policies, and institutions (Hajer and Versteeg, 2005). For example, Friant et al. (2020) identified four discourses of CE that are distinguished through, on the one hand, a holistic or segmented view on social, economic, technological, and political considerations and, on the other hand, actors' positions on the role of techno-innovations in socio-ecological challenges. Similarly, Bauwens et al. (2020) developed scenarios that reveal how different conceptualisations of the CE, based on the nature of their technologies and the configuration of the governance regime, lead to contrasting circular futures.

Uncovering how different actors from industry, policy, civil society, and research are actively positioning themselves and others in discursive categories is also crucial to re-politicise the CE debate (Hajer and Versteeg, 2005). In the case of plastics, Palm et al (2021) looked at policy narratives in the EU Plastics Strategy and identified four narratives at play: fossil feedstock dependency, resource inefficiency, pollution, and toxicity, each with a different group of victims, villains, and heroes. Tilsted et al (2022) showed how petrochemical incumbents strategically use their discursive power to accommodate pressures and to position themselves as solution providers. Mah (2021) argued that corporations across the plastics value chain

included circularity in their agendas but used these strategies to intensify future markets of risky technologies and unsustainable plastics.

Building on the work of previous scholars, this paper responds to calls for more reflexive research on the CE that fosters a plurality of views (Kovacic et al, 2020; Friant et al, 2020). It aims to explore different discourses of the CE with a focus on plastics in Europe to unveil how the circular plastics economy (CPE) is inherently political and is actively imagined, built, and created through discursive mechanisms. Our findings present commonalities and divergences of the discourses based on how arguments are framed, how actors positioned themselves and others; and which future pathways have been presented. It also engages in a discussion on how discourse analysis contributes to the re-politicisation of the CPE debate. It does so by reflecting on what Hajer and Versteeg (2005) formulate as the contributions of discourse analysis to environmental politics: uncovering the contested notion of nature; showing how discourses shape policy priorities; exposing hidden assumptions and judgements; and demonstrating how power and knowledge intertwine.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2.2 introduces the research design, sources of data, and the analytical framework. Section 2.3 presents the three discourses, which are characterised by the following narratives: 'Plastic fantastic', 'Circular economy will fly us to the moon', and 'Even plastic flowers are dead in this system'. After the empirical analysis, Section 2.4 presents the discussion before concluding the paper with several remarks.

2.2. Research design and methodology

This study applies the interpretive tradition in the social sciences (Foucault, 1982, Dryzek, 1997). This tradition assumes that realities are multiple and socially constructed: people make sense of their particular understanding of a phenomenon by telling stories and communicating with narratives (Hajer and Versteeg, 2005). We use the Argumentative Discourse Analysis approach by Hajer (1995), where he defines discourses as “an ensemble of ideas, concepts and categories through which meaning is given to social and physical phenomena, and which is produced and reproduced through an identifiable set of practices” (p.67). In this paper, we see discourses not as sole linguistic tools but as political processes in which a meaning-making process has the capacity to shape social practices, shift power balances, and impact institutions and policies (Hajer, 2006).

We use discourse analysis both as a theoretical and an analytical framework that allows us to track how arguments are framed, how problems and solutions are defined, which strategies are developed, and which future pathways have been presented (Hajer, 2006). Tracing the argumentative rationality brought into the discussions on CPE by different actors let us construct three discourses based on the scope of their emphasis: 'Plastic fantastic' (material-focused), 'Circular economy will fly us to the moon' (plastics economy-focused), and 'Even plastic flowers are dead in this system' (socio-ecological systems-focused). We present our analysis starting from the material level, expanding through the plastics economy level, and lastly to socio-ecological systems level.

Each discourse is presented in three parts: the first part introduces storylines, or “condensed statements summarising complex narratives” (Hajer, 2006:69). Storylines consist of how plastics, CE, the single-use

plastics (SUP) ban, and problems and solutions are portrayed in a particular discourse. We use words in *italics* to refer to the *short hands* in discussions: the main arguments used by discourse actors that assumes everybody else will understand what is meant (Hajer, 2006:69). Second, we present discourse coalitions, namely groups of actors who share a particular set of storylines. We then present assigned roles and positions of actors in each discourse. And finally, we show how the future is being imagined with diverse priorities and strategies, which we refer to as the future vision.

Our data collection ended in March 2022 and is based on document analysis, media, and interviews. We followed a fourfold process. First, to identify the actors who are actively engaging in the CPE debate we used the European news service EURACTIV. The platform delivers various actor positions with informed opinion pieces, interviews and reports specialising in EU policies. For our paper, we focused on the news articles under the Energy and Environment division. The commentaries provided a strong empirical base for our analysis which was expanded through the official websites of the identified actors. As a second step, we collected the reports, position papers, and policy documents that mention circular plastics from these websites, using a snowballing approach.

Third, we used podcasts, online recordings of webinars, conferences, and panel discussions on CPE as sites of argumentative exchange to better understand not only the narratives but also the positioning of the actors themselves and others (Hajer, 2006). Fourth, we conducted seven in-depth interviews that enabled us to cross-check our findings (Hajer, 2006). Participants were selected from active industry associations, governmental institutions, and civil society organisations, based on the commentaries from EURACTIV (see Table 1).

Numeric Code	Affiliation	Date
Interviewee 1 (I1)	European Environmental Bureau	08/06/2021
Interviewee 2 (I2)	Break Free From Plastic	11/06/2021
Interviewee 3 (I3)	Recycling Network Benelux	14/06/2021
Interviewee 4 (I4)	Plastics Europe	15/06/2021
Interviewee 5 (I5)	Pack4Food	22/06/2021
Interviewee 6 (I6)	European Youth Forum	25/06/2021
Interviewee 7 (I7)	European Parliament (The Greens)	25/06/2021

Table 1. Actors interviewed for insights

As a next step, we analysed our data against a coding scheme using NVivo. We adopted an abductive logic (Yanow, 2006) following previous interpretivist publications in CE (e.g. Ampe et al, 2019). This means that first, we started deconstructing different interpretations based on our prior knowledge of CE and plastics in an open coding phase, marking striking and relevant arguments under ten topics (Table 2-A). After having an overview, we created a workable coding scheme to look for the building blocks of a discourse and came up with a final list of eight codes (Table 2-B). In total ~700 documents were coded and analysed. As a third step, we combined analytical codes with thematic codes which led us to construct three discourses presented in three subcategories (Table 2-C). The process of building three discourses

was discussed with the authors of this paper several times to establish rigour, transparency, and representation.

A - Open coding topics	B - Coding scheme for discourse analysis	C – Integration of the findings
Production	Approach to plastic	Storylines Main arguments and metaphors
Consumption	Approach to CE	
Pollution	Approach to SUP	
Plastic waste trade	Problems	
Bioplastics	Causes	
Fossil-fuel dependency		
Toxicity	Positioning of actors	Actors Discourse coalitions
International treaty	and roles	
Recycling		Future vision
Pandemic	Future imaginaries Strategies and priorities	

Table 2. Overview of the coding, analysis, and integration of the findings.

2.3. Discourses of Circular Plastics Economy in Europe

This section presents the analysis of the three discourses in three parts: storylines, actor roles and positioning, and the future vision. A comparative summary is provided in Table 3 at the end of the section.

2.3.1. Plastic fantastic

2.3.1.1. Storylines: The first storyline of this discourse refers to plastics as an excellent material that “can be developed with any combination of properties to accommodate almost any application one can think of” (Plastics Europe, 2022b). Attractive properties of lightweight, durability, and flexibility in design make plastics the number one choice to meet demands of society, from staying connected to playing sports, from eating fresh food to being treated in hospitals: thus making daily lives easier, safer, healthier, and more mobile (SusChem, 2020). This central idea inspires the name of this discourse.

According to this storyline, plastics are *synonyms for resource efficiency* and are *game changers* in a resource-efficient, climate-neutral, and competitive CE in Europe (I4). Thus, it is crucial to extract the highest value in use and make sure these materials are recovered afterwards. Recycling comes out as the number one priority to keep the maximum possible resources in circles (I4). The *front-running* waste logistics, recycling, and collection schemes in Europe have been supported by the actors of this discourse to create a momentum for recyclers who are “at the forefront of making plastics circular” (Plastic Recyclers Europe, 2018).

The second storyline addresses plastic littering, which is considered to be a result of the irresponsible behaviour of consumers. Littering is seen as problematic not only because of the environmental damage it causes but also because valuable materials are getting lost in nature. Proponents of this discourse oppose any strong measures, such as bans or taxes (I5), and instead stress the need to educate consumers. The

SUP directive is harshly criticised under this storyline as a gratuitous ban: blame should not be on the material itself but on the ignorance of consumers.

“Europe voted for the SUP directive in 2019. At this moment, member states are translating this directive into national legislation to ban or reduce certain plastics. I find it a pity that this directive exists. Those plastics have functions, they protect quality and hygiene. I think they should have put more emphasis on the attitude of the consumers” (15).

“If you go about the thought process that we need to reduce the plastic production just because there is littering, you are making a shortcut. Many people look from one side but forget the bigger picture. For this little problem, plastics are demonised, and we need to find solutions to this urgently” (14).

The second quote above brings us to the third storyline that problematises the *demonisation* of plastics. It is argued that there is a need to do *plastics rehab* in society (Ragaert, 2019) and to think beyond *environmental folklore* (Acaroglu, 2013). Environmental folklore refers to people’s desire to protect the environment based on their experiences within society “that are mostly the stories people take for granted and are not based on any scientific framework” (Acaroglu, 2013). It is underlined that the misperceptions around plastics should be addressed by *turning to science* (14). Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) is the most referred scientific tool to quantify multiple environmental impact categories including greenhouse gas emissions, human and ecological toxicity, and energy use. Numerous LCAs are used in this storyline to “bust a bunch of myths” (Acaroglu, 2013) and to demonstrate the comparative environmental advantage of plastics against other materials.

An example of the comparative LCAs referenced in this discourse is the study by the consultancy Trucost (2016). The report looks at the substitution of plastics with paper, cotton and glass in packaging and consumer products with the same performance. The main finding states that switching to alternatives would increase the environmental costs over three times and requires four times more materials by weight (p.7). The report concludes that the visible impacts of plastics on the environment are mostly the after-use phase, which overshadows manufacturing, energy use, and transportation stages, where plastics outperform other materials. This conclusion is frequently used in invitations to *end the blind war* against plastics in this storyline.

Lastly, it is claimed that the Covid-19 pandemic positively affected the public image of plastics and their *essential roles* for protection and hygiene, after being discredited in the last years because of pollution (14). What is criticised is that the call from European Plastics Converters for postponement and lifting of the ban on SUP items is dismissed by the EU, risking the health and safety of millions of people.

2.3.1.2. Actor roles and positioning: Actors of this discourse coalition are predominantly plastic producers, waste management companies, and plastic-applying organisations. Active ones include Plastics Europe, Plastic Recyclers Europe, and European Plastic Converters.

This discourse positions the plastics industry as committed to making changes toward CE (14). They have been investing and innovating in cutting emissions and reducing waste for a long time and now, according to this discourse, the plastic industry has committed itself to circularity (Plastics Europe, 2022a). Industry

associations are producing facts and data transparently to support science-based policymaking and to better communicate the benefits of plastics to the public (14).

On the other hand, consumers are mostly seen as irresponsible and ignorant in this discourse. It is the responsibility of policymakers to address the littering habits and promote recycling practices among the wider public, as well as improve the efficiency of collection, sorting, and recycling facilities. Civil society is called to “stop being emotional and spreading false information; instead, they should listen to science and try to see the bigger picture” (14). Training of all stakeholders is needed to acknowledge the essential role of plastics in addressing society’s largest challenges (Plastics Europe, 2022a).

2.3.1.3. Future vision: This discourse frames CPE as a circularity at the material level.

According to this discourse, the production of plastics will increase to meet the demands of growing populations and economies (14). Plastic will be the champion material that maximises efficiency and ensures sustainability while meeting the growth of the automotive, packaging, and housing sectors. Further advancements in its material properties will help the fight against food waste through functional packaging; better insulating buildings will keep increasing energy prices low and reducing the weight of cars will decrease the use of oil.

This discourse prioritises regaining the competitive advantage of the European plastic industry as value chains increasingly move to Asia. It will leverage its strengths in cutting-edge innovations in recycling technologies, alternative feedstock, intelligent materials, and renewable energy resources for manufacturing. Plastic producers already planned significant investments in chemical recycling technologies of EUR 7.2 billion for 2030 (Plastics Europe, 2022b). It is trusted that this *game-changing* technology will complement mechanical recycling by treating waste streams that are either landfilled or incinerated; and will provide high-quality recycled feedstock for food-contact and pharmaceutical packaging (Plastics Europe, 2022b).

According to this discourse, the commitments of the industry will need to be backed by an open mindset for innovation and respect for the technological neutrality principle (15). Policymakers will need to create a supportive environment to embrace the developments in the plastics value chain and foster fair competition between the EU and other regions. A flexible balance is also important for an international treaty to avoid *regrettable substitutions* (Plastics Europe, 2022a).

2.3.2. Circular economy will fly us to the moon

2.3.2.1. Storylines: The first storyline in this discourse addresses the fundamental flaws in the current linear plastics economy and its *negative externalities*. Although plastics are seen as the “ubiquitous workhorse material of the modern economy” (EMF, 2016:1), it is argued that “the way plastics are currently produced, used, and discarded fails to capture the economic benefits of a more circular approach and harms the environment” (EC, 2018:3). Actors of this discourse often report quantitative modelling results to support their ideas with numbers: 95% of the material value of plastic packaging, which is expected to be around USD 80-120 billion, is lost to the economy after a very short-use cycle, every year (EMF, 2016). The annual cost of GHG from plastic production is rated to be USD 40 billion (EMF, 2016). 150 million metric tons of plastics are estimated to be in the oceans, and if not addressed, there could be more plastic than fish by 2050 (EMF, 2020). The sheer weight of *externalities* creates momentum toward *the ultimate solution*: making

the plastics economy circular with *moon-shot innovations*, which are targeted initiatives with a high potential for impact at scale (EMF, 2016). This central idea inspires the name of this discourse.

“It is now widely recognised that a circular economy approach is the only solution that can match the scale of the plastic pollution problem. It allows us to redesign the entire plastics system to not only overcome this global challenge, but to do so in a way that allows us to build better growth and create solutions at speed and scale“ (EMF, 2020:4).

The second storyline presents CE as a *win-win* scenario: it promotes growth, creates jobs, and decouples economic activity from the consumption of finite resources. A USD 706 billion economic opportunity has been projected from the shift to a circular model where the value and utility of products are retained and waste is designed out (EMF, 2016). It is argued that applying CE principles across the EU economy has the potential to increase the EU GDP by an additional 0.5% by 2030 and creating around 700,000 new jobs (EC, 2020). Moreover, proponents of this storyline argue that the CE can also address resource security concerns that are exacerbated as a result of Covid-19 and the Ukraine War.

As a *regenerative growth model*, according to this storyline, CE not only treats the inefficiencies of the current plastics economy but also addresses the root causes of many global challenges like marine pollution and biodiversity loss (EMF, 2020). Striking images of suffering animals and damaged ecosystems affected by plastic pollution captured public attention globally and created a demand for policy action. Particularly, single-use items that are commonly found on beaches are targeted at the European level, and the SUP directive is welcomed in this storyline as being “a much needed and timely action” (I3).

The third storyline underlines that innovation is the essential component to create the conditions under which a CPE can flourish: developing new technologies and business models are key to *turning today's challenges into opportunities* (EC, 2018). It is argued that an efficient CPE requires reorganising the ways of production and consumption and demands action from every actor in the plastics value chain. Thus, actors of this discourse put greater importance in collaborative initiatives and business networks (e.g. EMF Global Commitment Network, Circular Plastics Alliance).

According to this storyline, it is necessary to reject the false dichotomy of upstream and downstream innovation strategies (EMF, 2020). Designers and recyclers should realise that there is *no silver bullet solution* to transform the current plastics economy, so joint efforts are needed. In addition to creating an effective after-use plastics economy, actors in this storyline put growing emphasis on considering elimination, reusability, durability, and repairability before material circulation. As 80% of a product's environmental impact is determined at the design phase, moving upstream would treat the root cause of the pollution problem and prevent waste from being created in the first place (EMF,2020).

2.3.2.2. Actor roles and positioning: The discourse coalition predominantly consists of the European Commission, business consultancies, and plastic appliance organisations. Key actors include European Agencies, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, and McKinsey & Company.

This discourse underlines that shifting from a linear to a CPE requires collaborative action, but businesses are the key players as determinants of the market (EMF, 2016). *Untapped opportunities* wait for the ones that already embrace change: there is a *clear business case* in the progressive and irreversible transition to a CE

(EMF, 2016). Businesses that act fast to capitalise on novel models, designs and methods will *stay ahead of the curve*. On the other hand, businesses that get stuck in traditional linear models will face economic and reputational threats (EMF, 2016).

This discourse puts the responsibility on policymakers to create significant incentives for circular business models to remove the cost advantage of linear practices. Policies should empower consumers/users and ensure they receive trustworthy guidance to make informed choices. According to this discourse, consumers are already aware of the problem and play a catalytic role in shifting the CPE through engaging with sharing models, refill stations, and return schemes. Civil society actors nicely complete the picture by spreading awareness about plastic pollution and organising clean-up campaigns.

2.3.2.3. Future vision: This discourse frames CPE as a question of circularity at an economy-wide level.

According to this discourse, businesses will drive the transitions with *moon-shot innovations* towards the *new normal of circularity* (EMF, 2016). Pathbreaking developments like chemical marking, digital product passports, as well as advances in e-commerce and delivery services will foster novel activities. The potential of digital technologies will be utilised for a smarter CE to track and map data on resources, value chains, and product information. Digital technologies will not only accelerate smart circularity but also the dematerialisation of the European economy.

Actors of this discourse are working to develop improved modelling tools, metrics, and indicators to clear the blurred view of opportunities of a CPE. Policymakers will create advanced certification schemes and trustworthy labelling for the areas of confusion (e.g. biodegradable plastics) to initiate consistency, fair competition between businesses, and better consumer experience. Collection systems will be harmonised, and recycling capacity in Europe will be modernised to stimulate the market expansion for secondary materials. Chemical recycling will be used to complement mechanical recycling in hard-to-tackle waste streams and food-grade applications.

Decarbonization targets under the European Green Deal and the Paris Climate Agreement are taken seriously by the actors of this discourse, not only to reduce GHG emissions but also to decrease European dependence abroad. Extensive efforts will be needed to make novel technologies, such as capture and storage of CO₂ (CCS) and electrified steam crackers, cost competitive.

2.3.3. Even plastic flowers are dead in this system

2.3.3.1. Storylines: The first storyline of this discourse refers to plastics as unnatural, oil-based products which are “the tangible face of the climate crisis” and “the fastest growing pollutant in the world” (I2). The actors of this discourse stress that humanity is currently operating outside the safe planetary boundaries for chemical pollution, with plastic pollution as a particular issue of high concern (Persson et al, 2022). It is argued that these *seemingly cheap materials* have tremendous non-quantified costs to society and the environment (Rethink Plastic, 2021). This central idea inspires the name of this discourse.

This storyline problematizes the overwhelming volumes of global plastics production and the fact that production is projected to triple by 2050 (Persson et al, 2022). Referring to the ongoing expansion of production capacity by the petrochemical industry, it is argued that there is a pursuit for a *deeper carbon lock-in* with plastics (Bauer and Fontenit, 2021). As a result of ambitious global targets of decarbonisation,

oil and petrochemical industries are now “betting their future growth prospects on demand for plastics” (Carbon Tracker, 2020:1). However, this is seen as contradictory to the Paris Agreement and European net-zero ambitions of 2050 (I2).

The second storyline is based on criticism of the business-centred and technocratic CE strategies. According to the actors of this discourse, *business-led circularity is a myth*: corporations with vested interests in making profits should not have the leading role in addressing social and environmental problems (Mah, 2021). By shifting the perception of waste from the concern of environmental policy to economic opportunity in CE policy frameworks, the European Commission gave considerable agency to incumbent industrial actors (Leipold, 2021). It is argued that some of these actors might turn CE into a “technocratic project for future-proofing capitalism against environmental threats” (Mah, 2021:3).

The third storyline underlines that the impacts of plastics are spread across society but disproportionately fall on the poor and vulnerable communities in the world. One particular area of concern is the irresponsible and toxic plastic waste trade, which is also referred to as *waste colonialism* (Liboiron, 2021) where European countries are criticised for shifting the burden of their overconsumption in the forms of waste, pollution, and toxicity to vulnerable communities “whilst touting themselves as environmental leaders” (GAIA, 2019:10).

“It ends in the yards of waste pickers, who are left to deal with the problem that wealthy countries have failed to solve. Exporting countries send their recycling overseas without knowing or caring whether it is recycled or not, what the environmental and health impacts are, or who is bearing the brunt of these effects. What matter is that whatever they manage to export counted toward their recycling rates” (GAIA, 2019:11).

This storyline celebrates the advances in a global plastics treaty at the latest UN Environment Assembly resolution (UNEA-5.2). It is seen as a unique opportunity to build progressive coordination and partnership between countries to address present and inter-generational environmental injustices. Internationally binding instruments that tackle the full lifecycle of plastics with measures to reduce unnecessary production and consumption will be welcomed. According to the actors of this discourse, the process itself, whether being an inclusive, right-based one or not, will decide the ambition of the treaty (Rethink Plastic, 2022).

The last storyline in this discourse raises scepticism on how the CE can lead to sustainability. It refers to the CE as something *necessary but not sufficient* (I2). Actors question one of the foundations of the European CE Agenda, namely the possibility of absolute decoupling of economic growth from environmental pressures and resource consumption. This discourse underlines the problem of entropy and points out that only around 12% of the material input was recycled in the EU in 2019 at the scale of the whole economy (EEA, 2021). Matching the recycled material to the input processes or extending the durability and longevity of products would create a very *slow economy instead of a continuously growing one* (ZWE, 2020).

2.3.3.2. Actor roles and positioning: The actor coalition of this discourse predominantly consists of civil society organisations, research institutes, and several local governments. Key actors include Break Free From Plastics Movement, Rethink Plastic Alliance, Zero Waste Europe and City of Amsterdam.

Actors of this discourse lack confidence in industrial actors. They argue that industry lobbyists use their technical expertise, economic power, and access to the highest levels to push their agendas in political

circles (I2). Therefore, capacity building for policymakers to put strong regulatory frameworks and enforcement in place is needed. This is crucial to ensure that not only economic but also social and environmental aspects are addressed fairly, distant from *hypocritic promises* (I2).

In terms of policy, recent developments at the European level have been found promising. For example, explicit reduction targets for packaging in the second CE Action Plan and the right to repair in the European Green Deal have been welcomed after 40 years of end-of-pipe focused waste legislation (I7). Despite this, there is scepticism about the dichotomy between the policies and the action: EU policymakers are invited to *walk the talk* for a transformative change through legislative measures and targeted action (Friant et al, 2021).

Lastly, actors of this discourse champion the actions of civil society. Especially the successful campaigns of the global network Break Free From Plastic have been celebrated for directing significant attention of people, politicians and businesses to the *plastic crisis*. It is argued that these campaigns have led to creating *new frames of accountability*: putting the industry on the defensive and environmentalists on the offensive (I7).

2.3.3.3. Future vision: This discourse frames CPE as a question of circularity at level of socio-ecological systems.

According to this discourse, *expensive distractions* to the CE, such as CCS and chemical recycling should be avoided: investing in CCS for municipal waste incinerators might exacerbate a lock-in in incinerators, while chemical recycling (i.e. plastic to fuel or chemicals) might reinforce a linear economy. Biobased plastics might play an important role in a fossil-free future, but clear definitions are needed to avoid *green-washing*. Because of potential land conflicts, food security issues, and colonization histories, environmental justice should be prioritised while promoting bio-plastic alternatives.

Actors of this discourse call for absolute reductions in resource extraction, production, and consumption to downsize the socio-economic metabolism and lower the pressure on the planet (ZWE, 2020). Sufficiency-oriented lives are favoured over materialistic, consumption-oriented lifestyles. It is argued that an increasing number of people are willing to move into a more fulfilling way of living, which is based on wellbeing instead of throughput (I6). Changing the “everyday normal” is an important part of this systemic change, for example, boosting the practices of reuse and making single-use abnormal.

This discourse envisions a future that is a shift from a linear, unfair, polluting economy to a circular, toxic-free and fair society. The term *circular society* is referred to as an alternative circularity approach that envisions socio-ecological transformation beyond growth-focused and market-motivated techno-fixing solutions (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2021). Particular attention will be paid to societal prosperity, participation, and redistribution of wealth and power. The monetary-based capitalist value definitions will proactively be challenged to recognise multi-dimensional value-creation through many forms of work, such as care work and community work (ibid.). A post-growth-oriented circular society will actively strive for the well-being of both humans and non-humans (Bauwens, 2021).

	1. Plastic fantastic	2. CE will fly us to the moon	3. Even plastic flowers are dead in this system
Approach to plastics	Game changer material with fantastic properties, the synonym of resource efficiency	Workhorse material of the modern economy, unrivalled functions at low cost	The biggest unnatural polluter in the world, tangible face of the climate crisis
Approach to CE	Necessary for a resource-efficient and competitive Europe	Win-win: decoupling, better growth, jobs	Necessary but not sufficient, scepticism on social implications
Approach to SUP ban	Pity, wrong direction to take	Needed, timely action	Tip of the iceberg
Problems	The global competitive position of the European plastic industry Demonisation of plastics Waste and pollution	Inefficiencies of the existing plastics system, environmental externalities Resource security Waste and pollution	Technocratic, business-led circularity visions Increasing production Environmental injustices Waste and pollution
Causes	The shift of value chains to Asia Misperceptions of public Irresponsible behaviour of consumers	Linear economic model Scarcity of natural resources in Europe Problematic plastics in the market	Ecomodernist approach Restricted fossil markets Waste colonialism Wellbeing tied to growth
Discourse coalition	Main actors include Plastics Europe, European Plastic Converters	Main actors include European Commission, Ellen MacArthur Foundation	Main actors include Break Free From Plastic, Zero Waste Europe
Actors' positioning, division of roles	Industry/ business: Committed, already investing in cutting-edge technologies Policy: Need to support market players without creating barriers <i>Consumer</i> : Utility-maximisers, irresponsible, need to be educated NGO: Emotional, ignoring facts, can't see the bigger picture	Industry/business: Main actors and (moon-shot) innovators of CPE transitions Policy: Need to incentivise front-runners and systemic innovation without overregulating <i>User</i> : Rational choicer, ready to adapt to new business models NGO: Completes systemic change	Industry/business: Push for future carbon lock-in with plastics Policy: Need to regulate effectively, time to walk the talk <i>Citizen</i> : Performers of social practices, envision a just circular society NGO: Essential to create accountability for the plastic crisis
Future vision	Better material	Better plastics economy	Better socio-ecological system

Table 3. Comparative summary of three discourses.

2.4. Discussion

Our analysis demonstrates the existence of contested views on a CPE in Europe. What is problematised, how priorities and solutions are set, and which roles are assigned to different actors create the contrast between discourses. Actors who share particular storylines form discourse coalitions to set strategic actions that serve their interests and to reproduce or fight against given biases. We argue that the narratives of the second discourse (CE will fly us to the moon) are the most influential in the conceptualisation of the CPE as well as in institutional and organisational practices in Europe. It perpetuates the dominant ecological modernisation idea in policy circles (e.g. in the EU Green Deal) to build a win-win scenario of decoupling through technological innovations and new business models (Leipold, 2021). A depoliticised version of the CPE is being promoted through avoiding contested knowledge, silencing uncertainties, masking conflicts of interest, reducing circularity to technocratic management and transferring agency from governments to corporations (Kovacic et al, 2020).

For an explicit discussion on re-politicising the CPE debate through our findings, we draw on Hajer and Versteeg's (2005) study on the contribution of discourse analysis to the field of environmental politics. We discuss our findings in line with four points raised by these scholars on the usefulness of discourse analyses for revealing underlying political dynamics: the contested notion of nature; the deliberately limited process of thought and policy priorities; hidden assumptions and judgements; and the intertwining of power and knowledge. We share our reflections on these points while comparing the three discourses.

The first contribution of discourse analysis to the field of environmental politics lies in the appreciation of nature as a contested notion (Hajer and Versteeg, 2005). Our analysis confirms that each discourse assumes a different way of relationship with nature. The first one sets that relationship in an extractive way: nature is out there externally to provide resources for humans. It should be managed by experts using modern technologies to convert these resources into commodities. The second one refers to nature as ecosystem services that provide economic value beyond extractable resources. It sets conservation and planning targets based on the monetary value assigned through quantitative models. The third discourse builds a relationship with nature that is beyond economic gains. It tends to adopt a cooperative and caring way of interaction that brings along appreciation and inspiration. The interpretations of material/non-material interactions with nature by different actors inherently shape environmental decision-making and are conditioned by underlying power relations on whose nature counts (Berghofer et al., 2020).

Secondly, Hajer and Versteeg (2005) state that "discourses shape what can and cannot be thought, delimit the range of policy options and thereby serve as precursors to policy outcomes" (p.178). If we take the production and consumption of plastics in relation to the role of consumers as an example, the three discourses show differences in what can be thought and addressed. The first discourse argues that increasing production of plastics follows the rising demand of growing populations and economies. Consumers are seen as utility-maximisers and plastics provide the best resource efficiency to meet their demands. Accordingly, economic incentives appear to be key policies to shape consumption patterns. On the other hand, the second discourse calls for a shift in the production mindset through redesigning products and services. It sets a goal to eliminate problematic plastics (e.g. non-recyclable) but does not demand a reduction in general consumption. Instead, it promotes a shift towards innovative models that deliver the same functionalities. According to the second discourse, consumption patterns are a result of rational choices

of consumers, so empowerment tools should be used by policymakers to shape these patterns. The third discourse argues that the production of plastics must substantially decrease because the planetary boundaries are already exceeded. Underlying norms, practices and power dynamics that maintain unsustainable plastic consumption should be addressed. Consumers are performers of social practices that are shaped by infrastructure, skills, and emotions. So, policy interventions should target the interplay between everyday practices and socio-structural contexts such as addressing drivers of food-on-the-go lifestyles for a reduction in single-use packaging (Rabiu, 2022). Discourses exert what to include in or exclude from political agendas, thus, they give directionality to the policy outcomes that are experienced by all.

The third contribution point presented by Hajer and Versteeg (2005) is the analysis of assumptions, bias and judgements in the discourses and practices, drawing largely from the work of Dryzek (1997). Dryzek argues that discourses embody power by conditioning the perceptions and values which advance some interests over others. In the case of CPE in Europe, the narrative of growth might be “the largest elephant in the room” (Friant et al, 2020:4). It is left unquestioned: the problem is rather defined as how to decouple GDP growth from material footprint and environmental pressures. Despite an expanding body of empirical evidence against absolute decoupling, the proponents believe in technological advancements and large-scale circular strategies on helping to achieve that goal (Bauwens, 2021). These actors hardly mention the problem of entropy in recovery strategies or the rebound effects of sharing economy practices. In our analysis, these narratives are dominant in the first and the second discourses, while the third discourse openly states that CE is inherently incompatible with an ever-growing economy. It argues that closing and narrowing loops would require a downscaled, slow economy as opposed to a productivist one (Friant et al, 2020). Moreover, a post- or degrowth-oriented circular economy and society disputes the definition of societal prosperity through material consumption and economic activities, thus challenging capitalist value definitions (i.e. based on monetary added value creation and destruction). Instead, it seeks multi-dimensional concepts of value creations that nourish care, solidarity, participation, and connectivity with nature (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2021). It envisions an economic reorganisation where wealth, knowledge, power, and technologies are distributed more fairly and (im)material resources serve exclusively for social well-being within planetary boundaries (ibid.).

The last contribution to the field is the application of Foucault’s governmentality (1991) to the study of environmental politics. Governmentality is used to identify the modern arrangement of power to govern that is distributed across various sites (Hajer and Versteeg, 2005). In the case of CPE, a closer look at the indicators and standards are particularly relevant in the understanding of the mode of governance dominating CE policies in Europe. Cited in Kovacic et al (2019:112), Turnhout et al (2014) propose the term “measurementality” (to extend Foucault’s term governmentality) to signify the “art of neoliberal governance” that privileges scientific techniques for assessing the environment in standardized units. What is to be measured or left out is decided by experts through scientific argumentation while silencing societal disputes. In the CE for plastics, indicator development and standard setting processes require highly technical knowledge in multiple areas (e.g. chemistry, modelling) where corporates exert considerable influence using information asymmetries (Mah, 2021). These intensify eco-modernist discourses in European policy-making that tend to pursue a depoliticised, technocratic management of environmental resources. These ideas are mirrored in the first and the second discourses. Actors of these discourses frame circularity in terms of

industrial activity and economic growth with a technology-centred idea of innovation, therefore, promoting governing through command, control, and monitoring. The third discourse, on the other hand, argues that moving towards a just circular economy and society would require going beyond what can be measured through quantitative forms of knowledge. Circularity indicators and standards that stabilise Euro-centric focus and undermine global environmental justice with technical debates about measurement and data availability, are criticised (Kovacic et al, 2019). Actors of the third discourse call for creativity and improved transformation capabilities by asking: how can society develop and grow in quality (e.g. purpose, solidarity, empathy) in a more equitable way, rather than in quantity?

2.5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study shows that the CPE is inherently political and is actively imagined, built, and created through discursive mechanisms. It is crucial to recognise power struggles over how problems are defined, solutions are presented, and how actors position themselves and others. Arguments around plastics might sound technical and factual but they are also meaningful and suggestive as shown in the contested understandings of a CPE in Europe.

We hope that our analysis of different discourses on CPE may help shape the practices, policies, and strategies in a more reflexive, responsible, and accountable way. That might be possible through critical introspection by every actor (from industry, policy, civil society, research) and being explicit about the choices they make, including their assumptions and limitations (Kovacic et al 2020). A further step towards socially just and environmentally sustainable CPE in the EU requires, on the one hand, engaging with plurality of ideas and trying to govern that complexity, on the other hand, narrowing, slowing, redistributing, and democratizing resource cycles in implementation.

Lastly, it is crucial to mention that division of a highly ambiguous and fluid debate on plastics into three categories involves inevitable simplification. Narratives used or strategies proposed in these discourses are not mutually exclusive and there are differences in the shades of arguments within each discourse (e.g. variety of post-growth visions within the third discourse). The analysis is intended to provide a structured overview of such a complex societal debate in the hope to avoid deadlocks and stimulate pluralist discussions. Future research can look at the recent developments including the United Nations global plastics treaty and the European Parliament vote passing a full ban on plastic waste exports, in relation to how actors (re)position themselves and whether new discourses emerge because of these rapidly changing landscapes.

Chapter 3

Packaged science? Incumbent strategies of science capture from a power perspective

Abstract

Transitions to a circular economy in Europe have not accelerated despite being a priority of the Green Deal. One reason behind the slow uptake is the active resistance by incumbent actors. This article explores the case of Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation to uncover resistance and capture strategies of incumbent single-use and takeaway industry actors that succeeded in reducing the ambition of the policy. Building on lobbying databases, and document and media analysis, the article uncovers strategies of using the legitimacy of science to exert influence. It shows how incumbents created doubts about the evidence base and produced their own scientific messaging; presents the ways they legitimised their role as scientific stakeholders in institutional settings; and examines the approach they took to align their interests with the policymakers' expectations. It analyses these strategies from a power perspective to investigate the complexity of capture and to provide a discussion on the mechanisms that reinforce deep-rooted patterns of incumbency.

This chapter is published as *Yalçın N.G., Paredis E., Jaeger-Erben, M. (2025) Packaged science? Incumbent strategies of science capture from a power perspective, Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions, Volume 54, 100931, ISSN 2210-4224.*

3.1. Introduction

The circular economy (CE) has become one of the main building blocks of the European Union's (EU) Green Deal, which has the ambition to transform the EU into a modern, competitive, resource-efficient economy and to become the world's first climate-neutral continent by 2050 (EC, 2020). Many aspirations are put into the CE, such as decoupling economic growth from resource use, preserving materials, minimising waste as well as contributing to low-carbon transitions in Europe. However, moving away from linear production and consumption patterns to more circular ones is not happening at the rates deemed necessary (Circle Economy, 2023). A recent report from the European Court of Auditors warned that, so far action has been powerless, and the circular transition is almost at a standstill in European Countries despite two action plans and €10 billion in funding (ECA, 2023).

Several scholars have argued that a major reason that there is very little progress towards the goals of circularity in the EU is resistance and obstruction by incumbent actors (Leipold, 2021, Mah, 2021). Incumbent actors, typically involving established industries that have vested interests in maintaining their privileged position rather than enabling transitions, often act strategically to protect the status quo (Geels, 2014). Sustainability transitions literature provides a rich repertoire of studies to demonstrate how incumbent actors resist or delay transitions in different industries (e.g. energy, food, transport), with various strategies (Scott, 2008; Yalçın et al, 2024) and taking up diverse positions (Magnusson and Werner, 2022).

The role of power in incumbent resistance and dominance has been increasingly taken up by transition scholars (Avelino and Rotmans, 2009). Sovacool and Brisbois (2019) provided a well-structured review of the different conceptualisations (e.g. from Gramsci, Foucault, Giddens, Lukes) of how incumbent (or elite) power is exerted across disciplines as well as in the transitions literature (e.g. Avelino, 2017; Brisbois, 2019). They covered different ways of mobilisations (e.g. knowledge shaping, policy planning); diverse types of incumbents based on the resources at their disposal (e.g. coercive, financial, technical, regulatory) and defining characteristics of a wide selection of theories/concepts (e.g. disciplinary power, hegemony, resistance). Based on their analysis of the relevance of different power frameworks in studying transitions, they join other calls (Roberts et al, 2018; Kohler et al, 2019) for more empirical research on the ways that incumbents employ power to shape transitions. Bringing in the power perspective is particularly crucial for avoiding the risk of oversimplifying features of incumbency, for exploring the depth of reinforcing patterns (Turnheim and Sovacool, 2020)

In this paper, we respond to these calls and shed light on how incumbent industry actors employ power to capture regulations and resist circular transitions, and we provide a discussion of the dynamics of incumbency. The political project of transitioning towards the CE serves as our area of study and we particularly investigate the revision process of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR). PPWR aimed at tackling the increase in packaging waste generated in the EU, harmonising the internal market for packaging and boosting the circular economy (EC, 2020a) and has become one of the most intensely lobbied and debated files of the last political term (2019–2024) (EEB, 2023). We study lobbying in PPWR through capture strategies of incumbent single-use and takeaway industry actors. In particular, we look at how corporate lobbyists target spaces where science is produced as a source of evidence for policymaking (Saltelli et al, 2022). We uncover how incumbent lobbyists act strategically to create their own scientific messaging that feeds into policies and legitimises their role as stakeholders in scientific discussions (Legg

et al, 2021), building on deep discursive, institutional, and structural patterns of incumbency (Stirling, 2019). This helps us underline the ambiguous and longitudinal aspects of capture and show how incumbent actors used science to repoliticise and then depoliticise the debate; to push for reductionist agendas and divert from the main goals of revision; and purchase political leverage building on their control over confidential data.

Our paper contributes to transitions literature in three ways: first, it focuses on a particular set of capture strategies on how incumbents use science as a key mechanism to gain legitimacy and resist fundamental change; second, it provides an empirical study of the ways incumbent power is used in transitions and provides a discussion on the complexity of capture and reinforcing dynamics of incumbency; and third, it focuses on the packaging industry, expanding the empirical scope in terms of sector (i.e. beyond energy, transportation, food). The rest of the article develops as follows: the next section provides an overview of the theoretical blocks on power (Lukes, 2005), science capture (Saltelli et al, 2022), and incumbency (Stirling, 2019). Section 3.3 introduces the methodology followed in Section 3.4 by an overview of the case of the PPWR and its relevance. Section 3.5 presents findings on strategies of science capture from a power analysis perspective. Finally, the discussion reflects on the findings under the lens of deep incumbency before concluding with the contributions and limitations of this study and ideas for future research.

3.2. Theoretical framework

Much research has been done on lobbying strategies for 'capture' as a practice, which describes the result or process by which regulation is consistently directed toward the interests of the regulated industry, by the intent and action of the corporate interest groups themselves (Carpenter and Moss, 2014). Examples include the ways incumbent automobile companies created a delay in German environmental policies (Richter and Stegen, 2022) or how energy corporations slowed down the Capacity Market reform for electricity in the United Kingdom (Lockwood et al, 2020). At the supranational level, lobbying at the EU level particularly attracted scholarly attention (e.g. Gullberg, 2008; Laurens 2018). These studies looked at how political institutions became a significant target of influence for incumbent actors since the European decision-making process structures the internal market of twenty-seven member countries and every proposed regulation influences the way companies adjust their competitive industrial strategies at the EU level.

In this paper, we look at regulatory capture at the EU level but zoom in on a particular set of strategies in which incumbent actors skilfully use the image and legitimacy of science (Saltelli et al, 2022). We use the term science capture to name incumbent strategies of regulatory capture where science is used as a key mechanism of resistance in regulatory processes. These have been studied extensively in the tobacco and chemical industry (e.g. Oreskes and Conway, 2010), where strategies of creating doubt and misinformation to obscure industry practices and of resisting unfavourable regulations are presented.

There is an increasing number of studies that show the use of science as a key mechanism of corporate influence is more complex, multifaceted and widespread. For example, Legg et al. (2021) provide an overview of industry influence on science and the use of science in policy with nineteen comparative strategies across eight industries (e.g. alcohol, fossil fuel, pharmaceutical). Their 'science for-profit model' shows how, beyond influencing the production and reach of the evidence, incumbent actors target the use of science in policy and practice by creating increased reliance on themselves, for example by securing the use of regulatory

tools such as cost-benefit approach which implies dependency on industry data and prioritise economic evidence.

Similarly, Saltelli et al (2022) report that the strategy of lobbyists has gradually evolved from merely appropriating scientific evidence to shaping the relationship between science and regulation, influencing the governance of science itself, and ultimately affecting the interaction between science and society. Building on the words of Laurens (2018), they argue that science has become the new currency of lobbyists to purchase political leverage. The asymmetry of knowledge and resources between industry lobbyists and policymakers, often the requisite technical “European” data to design policy options and develop standards, secures industry actors early access to the decision-making and leverage in the system.

In this paper, we study science capture by looking at how lobbyists target spaces where scientific knowledge is produced as a source of evidence for policymaking, and we analyse how this is sustained by the control of the institutional mechanisms and aligning their interests with the policymakers’ expectations. This is partly covered by several scholars in their analysis of strategies of incumbents in transition literature. For example, Brisbois (2019) looked at how influence over relevant information and knowledge that is crucial to the policy process works as a structural power strategy in her Powershifts framework; Smink et al (2015) covered how incumbents utilised their technical knowledge for standard-setting as an institutional strategy in the Netherlands’ energy sector, and Suhlsen and Hisschemoller (2014) found how knowledge development was used to imply solutions in a technical manner by incumbent lobbyists and was presented in a way that could readily be adapted by policymakers in Germany’s energy sector. However, an exclusive focus on science capture strategies has not yet been brought to the transition literature. This is crucial not only to challenge incumbent resistance against transitions but also to bring the political role of and power dynamics within the scientific knowledge production and use to the fore, which this article puts great emphasis on. As more and more regulatory battles are fought in scientific arenas (Laurens, 2018), a particular focus on science capture is vital to understand and better address incumbent resistance and domination.

To bring that particular focus, we build on three strategies of science capture developed by Saltelli et al (2022). They argue that science capture has become a frontier of political and societal domination strategies, and they explore five case studies ranging from pesticide regulations to ethics guidelines for artificial intelligence. The proposed strategies suggest that lobby actors are not only co-opting scientific methodologies as extensively covered by academic research on the tobacco industry but are also actively shaping the governance of science itself and interfering with science-society relations. This is covered in three strategies for exerting power and influence in a complex and non-linear pattern. First are epistemic strategies that target criteria for science quality through questioning the evidence and its legitimacy or through influencing the methods that produce it; second are institutional strategies targeting the areas of science governance through dominating committee and consultation tables; and third are imprinting their own agenda for societal functions of science by targeting the framework or the context of the evidence or desirability of regulation. Table 4 provides an overview of the three strategies of capture and target areas in the use of knowledge and science adapted from Saltelli et al (2022).

Strategies	Target
Epistemic. Invalidating the inference or influencing the methods whereby the evidence is produced	Science quality criteria and epistemology
Institutional. Delegitimising or appropriating the institutional settings which produce the evidence	Science governance
Political. Changing the framework in the context of which the evidence or regulation is relevant or desirable	Relation between science and society

Table 4. Three strategies of science capture (adapted from Saltelli et al, 2022)

In this article, we look at science capture as one of the major strategies of incumbent resistance and domination. We build on Pel's critique (2015) among others (e.g. Meadowcroft, 2009) VoB et al, 2009) to the idealistic understanding of capture in transition politics as an undesirable exception or unfortunate failure of a system or policy. Transition ideas and policies are unavoidable parts of politics, negotiation and clashes of interests; thus, investigating capture requires going beyond the apparent failure in a policy outcome. Capture is a remarkably regular but complex, ambiguous, longitudinal phenomenon which needs to be explored through the processes of evolving meanings and strategies (Pel, 2016). To unearth capture in its complexity, we expand our analysis towards illustrating the mechanisms and strategies that lead policymakers to favour industry interests. That requires looking at the detailed dynamics that produce and reproduce the stability of incumbency as a source of power and influence (Johnstone et al, 2017). Stirling (2019) calls this "deep incumbency" which is "multiplexity of dynamics through which a particular trajectory in interacting social, economic, cultural, political, discursive, cognitive, technological and wider material phenomena, is reproduced by – and reinforcing of – associated power gradients" (Stirling, 2019:2). Looking at these dynamics is crucial to avoid oversimplifying the nature of incumbent actors and to explore deep-rooted patterns of incumbency (Turnheim and Sovacool, 2020).

These patterns can be understood by looking at the irreducible aspects of power dynamics that span entire polities (Johnstone et al, 2017). Lukes' (2005) three 'faces of power' are particularly helpful in revealing the dynamics that reinforce deep incumbency in political contexts, looking not only at visible but also at hidden and invisible power. Alongside the struggles in the decision-making process, three faces also incorporate actions and inactions that shape agenda-setting processes and perceptions and preferences of actors. Lukes defines power as the ability of "A" to make "B" do something B would not otherwise do. Power is relational and processual: it is both agent-centred and structure-centred in a dynamic set of relationships. The first dimension looks at visible power which is the overt and definable aspects of political power, and which includes the formal rules and procedures of decision-making. The second dimension covers exercising hidden power within (dominant) political, economic, and social structures that are sustained over time. It is often exercised through controlling the political agenda and increasing the visibility and legitimacy of powerful actors while excluding other groups. Lastly, the third dimension is described as the invisible power that shapes meanings and what is seen as acceptable in a social and political culture. It targets individual and collective consciousness, conformity to the status quo or imaginations about an (alternative) future. Table 5 provides an overview of Lukes's three faces of power.

Overall, for a more in-depth analysis of incumbent resistance against circular transitions through science capture, we explore capture strategies from a power perspective. Bringing the power lens allows us to reveal the complexity of capture strategies beyond the observable failure in policy outcomes and to highlight the underlying dynamics of political, discursive, institutional, and structural incumbency.

Faces of power	Manifestations
Visible power	Definable aspects of political power, the formal rules, structures, and procedures of decision-making
Hidden power	Power to influence who gets to the decision-making table, what gets on the agenda, and the legitimacy of voices and demands
Invisible power	The power that shapes discourses, social and political culture, individual and collective consciousness, defining normal and future alternatives

Table 5. Lukes' three faces of the power (adapted from Gaventa, 2006)

3.3. Methodology

Our data collection is based on document analysis, online databases of lobbying information, and media coverage. We followed a five-step process. First, to identify the actors who are actively engaging in the PPWR file we used the media platforms of EURACTIV² and Politico³. These platforms deliver coverage of EU politics and policies, interviews, reports as well as sponsored content and informed opinion pieces from various actors. We also used Contexte media's focus coverage of PPWR under the Environment section as well as investigative journalism pieces from the EuObserver. These documents provided a strong empirical base for our analysis. As a second step, we expanded our data collection through the official websites of the engaged actors and collected the reports, letters, position papers, and press releases that mention PPWR from these websites, using a snowballing approach. Third, we cross-checked our findings with the Influence Map⁴ database which is the world's largest database of corporate and industry associations lobbying for climate policy. Its' special query for PPWR under the Energy and Resource Efficiency division provides a detailed overview of the policy engagement of different actors and the "Live Lobbying Alerts" page gives updates on every position paper, press release, and joint letter from industry associations and corporations active on the PPWR file. In addition, we used the Corporate Europe Observatory, LobbyFacts, and EU Transparency Register for detailed data and information about the lobbying in Brussels. Fifth, we used online webinars, conferences, and panel discussions on PPWR as sites of argumentative exchange to better understand the narratives and the positioning of the actors themselves and others (Hajer 2006). As a next step, we analysed our data against a coding scheme using NVivo. We adopted an abductive logic (Yanow 2006), starting with an open coding phase, marking striking arguments under 10 main, and 34 subtopics. After having an overview of the arguments and positions of the actors, we created a coding scheme to look for the dynamics of the incumbent power building on the three forms of power of Lukes (2005) and mapped each of them

² For our paper, we focused on the news articles on Packaging and Packaging Waste and Sustainable Packaging sections under the Energy and Environment division mentioning PPWR.

³ We made a manual selection of results mentioning PPWR based on the results from the search function with a key word "packaging".

⁴ <https://europe.influencemap.org/policy/EU-Packaging-and-Packaging-Waste-Regulation-18797>

under three science capture strategies based on Saltelli et al (2022). In total, ~550 documents have been coded and analysed. Table 6 provides an overview of the coding and analysis.

A – Open coding main topics	B – Coding scheme for power analysis	C – Integration of power perspective into science capture strategies
Problem	Visible power	
Causes	(observable decision-making)	Epistemic strategy
Strategies		
Priorities		
Critics	Hidden power	Institutional Strategy
Impact assessment	(influence on the political agenda)	
Science		
Innovation	Invisible power	Political strategy
Definitions	(shaping meaning and what is acceptable)	
Standards		

Table 6. Overview of the coding and analysis

3.4. The Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation Case

The case studied in this paper is the revision process of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (Directive 94/62/EC) that was amended in 2018. In September 2022, the EC assessed the transposition of the PPWD under the Environmental Implementation Review and stated the practical and legislative divergences between Member States on reinforcing the requirements of the Directive, for example in essential requirement of packaging materials to be placed on the market.

Against this backdrop and the EU commitments taken in recent years, The European Commission (EC) proposed the revision of the EU legislative framework for packaging and packaging waste on 30 November 2022 as part of the European Green Deal, the New Circular Economy Action Plan and complementary to the Plastics Strategy. It set the goal to ensure that all packaging on the EU market is either reusable or recyclable in an economically viable way by 2030, to promote prevention, reuse, and refill in line with the waste hierarchy and to set mandatory recycled content targets in packaging as a substitute for virgin materials with a variety of measures (EC, 2022a). It proposed to turn the Directive into a Regulation to enable better functioning in the EU market and prevent fragmented rules that cause uncertainty and additional costs to the economic operators.

The proposal also highlighted the pressing need to address the all-time-high packaging volumes in the EU as packaging waste has grown more than 20% in the last decade. Per capita packaging waste reached a new record of 188.69 kilograms per capita in 2021 in Europe (varying from 73.8 kg per inhabitant in Croatia to 246.1 kg per inhabitant in Ireland). Paper and cardboard are the main packaging waste materials (34 million tonnes) followed by plastic and glass (16.1 million tonnes and 15.6 million tonnes, respectively) waste materials in 2021 (Eurostat, 2023).

The legislative journey of the PPWR started in November 2022 when the Commission introduced its draft regulation. In April 2023, rapporteur Frédérique Ries presented her draft recommendations for amendments. Technical discussions on the PPWR took place from April to July 2023 with concurrent meetings in both the Council and the European Parliament. The 22nd of November marked the plenary voting of the Parliament

and the start of the trilogue negotiations, and the agreement between the Council and the Parliament was adopted on 24 April 2024.

This paper focuses on incumbent strategies of regulatory capture in the process of revision of the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive. The PPWR proposal has been one of the most intensely lobbied and debated files of the current political term (2019–2024) (EEB, 2023). Environmental groups and several MEPs mentioned the intense lobbying and Pascal Canfin, at the time chairman of the Parliament's Environment, Public Health and Food Safety committee, MEP from Renew Europe, published an opinion piece to put the lobby strategies under light at Liberation, a French Media Platform. His quote below hints at the strategies of science capture by creating doubts about the evidence base and creating an echo chamber for their messaging, which is covered in the next section.

“A major lobbying battle is currently being waged in Brussels against our ambition to move towards a more circular economy. (...) At the helm of this no-holds-barred lobbying campaign are the giants of fast-food and single-use packaging. These companies do not hesitate to spread misinformation that they present as scientific. (...) They don't run large-scale campaigns, but rather ultra-targeted ones. (...) And they have joined forces in a coalition whose slogan is the opposite of their ambition: "Together for sustainable packaging" (Canfin, 2023).

The most active lobbying actors were the single-use packaging and takeaway companies, as also stated by Canfin. This paper focuses on these two groups of industry actors and umbrella business associations for packaging, including McDonald's, the European Paper Packaging Alliance (EPPA), the European Organisation for Packaging and the Environment (Europen) and BusinessEurope. There were many other actively involved actors in the revision process, such as environmental groups and consumer organisations but for this paper, we keep our focus on the incumbent industry actors and their strategies of capture and positioning in the debate.

3.5. Findings

This section presents the findings of this paper. It is structured through the three strategies of capture namely epistemic, institutional, and political (Saltelli et al, 2022). In each strategy, we reveal how visible, hidden, and invisible power is employed by incumbent actors.

3.5.1. Epistemic strategy

When corporate lobbyists contest the evidence or invalidate the methods whereby the evidence is produced, Saltelli et al (2022) call it an epistemic strategy (p. 9). In the case of PPWR, this was one of the most visible strategies of resistance. Very early on, industry lobbyists labelled the impact assessment accompanying the PPWR proposal as not rigorous, realistic or fact-driven (FEFCO, 2022), lacking depth and complexity, and not backed by science (BusinessEurope, 2023). As a response, they commissioned their studies, which started the “battle on whose truth counts” (Saltelli et al, 2022:9). The most heated content of the negotiations of the PPWR was the reuse targets that were turned into LCA wars between recyclable single-use paper packaging vs reusable plastic packaging to push for the exception that is given to divert from the waste hierarchy in the Waste Directive (4.2) in the case of a better environmental outcome. Several EU policymakers stated they were overwhelmed by alternative LCAs and conflicting findings (EEB, 2023).

The PPWR was proven controversial even before its official release. The first official draft was leaked to the public a few weeks before publication on 30 November 2022 and was welcomed by environmental groups, civil society organisations and some SMEs, including the European Environmental Bureau, Zero Waste Europe, and RECUP. The focus on the higher level of the waste hierarchy with binding measures on prevention and reuse was regarded as a critical opportunity to turn the tide away from a linear economy towards a circular one.

On the other hand, the proposal faced significant criticism from the industry, especially from the takeaway industry and single-use packaging industry. It was marked as a financially unworkable dramatic reorientation that overshadows the industry's ongoing investments towards achieving packaging circularity. In particular, reuse targets were branded as unrealistic and criticised for being built on an inaccurate assessment and a lack of evidence. According to industry actors, the disproportionate focus on reuse not only threatens the recycling facilities and investments but also poses a danger of turning the clock back on the Green Deal in terms of environmental, economic, and employment aspects.

“The EPPA supports a science-based approach (...) In our view, the impact assessment (of the Commission) suffers from methodological faults, lack of data, incoherent explanations of key reasonings, unsubstantiated assumptions and the omission of crucial considerations concerning packaging” (Rantanen, 2023a).

“Unrealistic and discriminatory targets that are not supported by scientific and empirical evidence do not create the positive investment climate needed to support the transition, and they make the industry question if to continue investing in this legislative setting is at all sustainable.” (Europen, 2022).

As a result of this backlash, reuse targets were watered down in the first official proposal several weeks after leakage, with some reduced by 50% (i.e. reuse quota of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages (excluding wine and spirits) by 2040 decreased to 25% from 75%). Other changes included removing a negative list for recycling processes, such as plastic sleeves.

Seeing the outcome of their visible power employed through the play of merchants of doubt (Oreskes and Conway, 2010) and strategically capturing the scientific uncertainty, lobby actors intensified their activities, mostly on the claim that the basis for prioritising reuse models was unscientific. ‘To bring science to the packaging debate’ (FEFCO, 2022), these actors commissioned three reports, launched two websites, and sponsored multiple media articles.

“I think the changes that we’re seeing in the new draft actually raise even more questions on how these targets were formulated in the first place. We remain with the same questions we had at the beginning: how these targets have been generated, what data is behind the impact assessment to propose what appears to be non-realistic” (Stevens, cited in Taylor, 2022).

The report commissioned by McDonald's with the consultancy firm Kearney, “No Silver Bullet”, brought tremendous impact. Based on the findings of the negative environmental impact (increase in GHG emissions, water, and energy use), significant upfront investment and operating costs, increased food safety risk, and impact on consumer experience, the report concluded that reusable models of consumption should not be

implemented in the takeaway sector. It also mentioned that reusable packaging will lead to a sharp increase in the use of plastic materials in Europe, 4 times more in dining and 16 times more in the takeaway sector. The findings of the report were presented in an event at the European Parliament organised by EPPA and hosted by Massimiliano Salini, MEP.

A coalition for lobbying against the PPWR was launched shortly after the publication of the report to signal a consensus behind the findings. “Together for Sustainable Packaging” had more than 20 members from the takeaway industry and the paper and cardboard packaging industry. The alliance members published an open letter inviting EU policymakers to pause the proposal on PPWR (Together for Sustainable Packaging, 2023). The letter asked for a reflection on the data and studies published by Kearney (commissioned by McDonald’s) and Ramboll (commissioned by EPPA), particularly on reuse targets.

Matti Rantanen, the general director of EPPA, argued that many policymakers have started from the misinformed position that reusable packaging is inherently more sustainable than single-use alternatives, and they were misreading the waste hierarchy. He urged the EC to ‘set ideological wars aside and pursue a science-based, truly circular economy’ for the PPWR (Rantanen, 2022). In an interview on Packaging Insights, he explained “how ideological thinking on the waste hierarchy threatened EU policies”:

“One of the reasons (that there is a strong focus on reuse) is misreading of the waste hierarchy on the waste regulation, where it goes reduction, reuse and recycle. But it is also very clearly stated that there is the exemption of the better environmental outcome based on the life cycle assessment. And that is often forgotten by both the Commission and the NGOs. Actually, the scientific background says that recyclable is better in specific such as quick service restaurants. (...) So, unfortunately, there is more space for ideology than science in some discussions (Rantanen, 2023b).

The alliance members employed hidden power to drive a reductionist agenda centred around the comparison of single-use paper packaging against reusable plastic packaging. The comparative study findings were used to push for the exemption of the Waste Framework Directive’s Article 4(2), which allows for deviating from the waste hierarchy based on proof of environmental benefits. Conflicting LCA results are not only used to show the better performance of single-use packaging over reusables but also utilised to close-down the discussions into reuse vs recycling, and to divert attention from the key preventive measures in the higher steps.

A deeper look at the narratives reveals the dominant discursive ideas of these actors around circularity. The circular economy is framed at the material level (paper vs plastic), which is predominantly concerned with the material properties and efficiency in closing the loops through recycling, rather than engaging with systemic packaging innovations or socio-ecological impacts (Yalçın et al, 2023). Accordingly, paper packaging is presented to be the champion of reducing plastic waste, perfectly recyclable, and predominantly European. Invisible power is employed through a powerful discursive alignment on the wider scepticism around plastics in the EU: them being fossil-based material with toxicity impacts, having low recycling rates, and creating resource dependency outside the EU. When reusable packaging options are framed as a material substitution of paper with plastic, rather than as a system shift away from throwaway consumption models, single-use packaging options are presented as more favourable than reusables. These narratives were especially prominent in media campaigns, op-eds, and internet ads, as shown in the example in Figure 1.

However, record-breaking volumes of either material (Eurostat, 2023) were not mentioned in those campaigns.

Figure 1. An example media campaign by the Together for Sustainable Packaging Alliance⁵ building on the Kearney No Silver Bullet Report.

Witnessing the lobbying activities from incumbent industry groups and their impact on the policy targets, civil society organisations and reuse businesses issued an open letter to Parliament and the Council expressing their concerns about the 'misinformation and intense lobbying from the single-use packaging industry and takeaway sector to undermine goals of waste prevention and reduction in the PPWR'. The Kearney report has been a special target of criticism for the lack of transparency in data and methodology, and the absence of reflexivity in assumptions.

"The publication uses unclear data and assumptions to undermine the role of reusable packaging. (...) It's a bit disturbing that it's then presented as unquestionable science" (Musso cited at Carlile, 2023).

A joint letter by 58 Life Cycle Assessment Scientists also urged EU policymakers to be cautious about the results of some packaging environmental impact assessments (Gala et al, 2023). The LCA scientists advised checking the robustness of an LCA through several criteria, including whether the study is peer-reviewed, independent, follows ISO standards, and has a comprehensive description of scope and inventory data to assess the maximum possible number of indicators. The EC's Impact Assessment for the PPWR is highlighted by the group as a comprehensive starting point to assess the environmental impacts of different packaging options.

A closer examination of the assumptions underlying Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) that produce conflicting results reveals that these differences largely stem from varying perspectives on consumer behaviour (such as return rates, home washing and dedicated return journeys). For example, McDonald's study estimates that the reusable packaging would only rotate 2 or 3 times in takeaway consumption. The EC impact

⁵ <https://forsustainablepackaging.eu/the-facts/>

assessment does not give an exact return rate, but in a given example, a reusable cup is assumed to be returned 15 times⁶. Positioning the consumer as individuals driven by utility maximisation or individuals who demand changes in packaging levels and are willing to adopt new models creates significant divergences (Yalçın et al, 2023).

Despite the warnings against the misleading reports and the demand to keep the ambitions of the revised proposal, the reusable packaging targets in the takeaway sector were removed, mirroring the requests of the incumbent industry lobbyists. The deletion of targets was justified by the lead policymaker Frédérique Ries, referring to the challenges in demonstrating the environmental advantages of reuse within the takeaway industry and arguing they were not adequately addressed in the Commission's impact assessment.

“We have this constant desire to strengthen our environmental ambitions on a whole series of points, but we’re also listening to the many sectors who have expressed their opinions in a sector which is very fragile following the crisis. (...) The environmental benefits of reuse in the food and drink takeaway sector are difficult to prove and are not really addressed in the Commission’s impact assessment. (...) Taking this into consideration, in addition to the lack of a large-scale system within the Member States, specific targets for reuse in these sectors cannot be set without prior analysis.” (Ries, 2023).

All in all, the epistemic strategy was one of the main strategies of the single-use packaging industry lobbyists to reduce the ambition of the PPWR. They contested the evidence by creating doubts about the LCA for the PPWR of the Commission; conducted their own studies; set up an alliance to show consensus and close-down the agenda; and carried out targeted media campaigns. The epistemic strategy was so powerful that, with it, incumbent lobby actors mainly succeeded in diverting attention from the primary goals of revising the previous directive in accordance with the waste hierarchy and reducing packaging volumes in the EU.

3.5.2. Institutional Strategy

When incumbent industry actors influence the agenda of science governance through populating consultations and standard-setting committees or taking the role of the institutional settings which produce the evidence, Saltelli et al (2022) call it the institutional strategy. Alongside the heated reuse discussions in PPWR, the definition of recyclability has become a major contestation point. The criteria for packaging characteristics as well as for appointing the authority to set the standards created disagreements. Industry lobbyists pushed for their own guidelines to be adopted, claiming the Commission’s negative list of packaging characteristics was ‘conflicting with a science-based, comprehensive, non-discriminatory, future-oriented approach’ (FINAT, 2022).

The PPWR proposal suggested empowering the Commission to develop the definition of recyclability. However, Business Europe and other industry actors called for a mandate to European Standardisation Bodies (CEN) to develop the criteria ‘to guarantee sufficient expertise and ensure a transparent standardisation process’ (BusinessEurope, 2023). Mirroring these requests, the Industry, Research and Energy (ITRE)

⁶ “For example: In case of an assumed average number of rotations per year of a MU coffee cup of 15, and the average weight of the single use cup and multiple use cup are 21g and 51 g respectively, the coffee shop would, at a MU rate of the 30%, reduce packaging by 24.76%. The detailed calculation rules and reporting schemes will be established in an implementing act.” (EC, 2022c:26)

Committee also submitted the provision to move the definition of recyclability to CEN. However, environmental groups and consumer organisations supported the original proposal to mitigate the standardisation process being held in CEN, where business has the resources and economic interest to ensure the strongest voice' (ANEC, 2023).

Prior to the PPWR discussions, similar strategies of domination were observed in the standardisation request in 2022 for plastics recycling and recycled plastics under the implementation of the EU Plastics Strategy. The Circular Plastic Alliance (CPA) was established after the Plastics Strategy to boost the EU market for recycled plastics to 10 million tonnes by 2025 and is considered a relevant stakeholder initiative. It has been intensively consulted by the EC in the drafting and preparation of the Standardisation Request. However, with a membership of more than 330 organisations, the Alliance is dominated by industry actors, so the list of standards proposed by the CPA focused primarily on industry needs and ended up with a lack of ambition. Campaigners sent letters to question the opaque role of the Alliance that is given preferential treatment asking if the "World's top polluters are holding pen on new EU standards for recycled plastics?" (Rethink Plastic Alliance, 2022) and referring to the CPA as a missed opportunity to create a meaningful, ambitious initiative towards a circular plastics economy. They criticised the untransparent and non-inclusive process as civil society organisations were only consulted in the last stages of the standardisation process.

Beyond dominating stakeholder consultations and standardisation committees, building on the financial, technical, and institutional resource asymmetries, lobby actors employ more sophisticated institutional strategies. In his book "Lobbyists and Bureaucrats in Brussels: Capitalism's Brokers", Laurens (2018) explains how Brussels-based business associations are increasingly turning themselves into private research institutions. These associations invest heavily in the recruitment of scientific and technical experts and get involved in setting certain directions of the scientific field linked to their market operations. In them, bureaucratic and technical capital come together and act as a key to scientific bureaucracy. In parallel to their AISBL (international non-profit association) status, an increasing number of associations are also registered as industrial scientific organisations or take names promoting their expert statuses, such as institutes or research centres (as exemplified in the next strategy). It not only creates legitimacy of the expertise of their lobbyist in the eyes of the EU officials but also facilitates partnerships with universities, notably under the Horizon framework programmes and in novel areas where infrastructure costs are beyond the reach of public research alone.

Ownership of data and patents by their members gives these umbrella organisations another lobbying advantage. In the case of PPWR, the access to data allowed incumbents to act as gatekeepers of critical information. Incumbent actors branded the data supporting the PPWR as "outdated and misleading" (EPPA, 2023) however, alternative industry assessments based on "real world data" could only be challenged to a certain extent as "some sensitive primary data required commercial confidentiality to be in compliance with competition rules" (EPPA, 2023). As suggested by Laurens (2018) and Saltelli et al (2022), these actors used to access to confidential data and scientific knowledge as their new currency to purchase political access, prioritise their interests, and leverage in influencing the governance of science itself.

Another privileged use of data occurs when business associations develop new standards or measures based on their technical data before the Commission brings them into the agenda. This way, they become crucial for consultations with the EU officials planning to regulate the sector. Through strategic mobilisation of

scientific resources upstream and downstream of lobbying, these actors employ hidden power to promote ideas that are useful in maintaining a dominant market position. This also presents a shift in the role of standards from being measures used to regulate the industry to becoming additional filters that prevent lobbying on behalf of interests from outside the industry (Laurens, 2018).

This was also pushed in the PPWR. The negative list of packaging characteristics introduced by the Commission for setting the criteria for recyclability was criticised by industry associations, such as FINAT (European Association of self-adhesive labels) and Plastics Europe (European Association of Polymer Producers). Instead, they suggested the EC adapt to the industry-developed standards, stating they already demonstrate responsibility and commitment to “leading the circularity” (PlasticsEurope, 2023) Visible power is employed to ‘strongly oppose’ the negative list “which would act as an innovation brake failing to consider advances through current and future innovations in material composition, detection, infrastructures, recycling technologies” (PlasticsEurope, 2023:1). In their open letter, FINAT invited the Commission to refer to cross-sector guidelines such as RecyClass for plastic packaging, 4evergreen for fibre-based packaging and CEFLEX for flexible packaging as reference points. According to FINAT, the low compatibility category of the RecyClass Guidelines, which identifies the harmful and discouraged features for the criteria, would result in the same effect that is intended by a negative list, but it will provide a ‘more certain and science-based approach’, ‘will allow the use of new technologies’, and ‘foster innovation’. The incumbents asked the EC to create a supportive policy that ‘encourages the leading role of the European industry’ in the circularity transition:

“Our industry is fully engaged in taking action to bring packaging sustainability to the next level. For that to happen, we need a corresponding supporting regulatory framework to help us drive this change further. (...) The proposed prescriptive negative lists are not only unnecessary, but they will have as a sole outcome that of disrupting innovation and investment in further recycling facilities, with far-reaching environmental, employment and economic consequences.” (Europen, 2022)

Uncovering invisible power dynamics is crucial here to better understand how incumbents maintain such a powerful position in institutional settings. The changes in the latest Framework Program for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe, exemplify the central position given to the industrial actors. With a strong focus on technology-driven innovation, the Framework aims to boost the EU’s competitiveness in the global economy. It “embodies industry’s essential role in achieving all the Programme’s objectives” (EC, 2018:10) and brought “industrial competitiveness” and “global challenges” under one pillar despite concerns raised by a coalition of civil society organisations that “merging and blurring profit-oriented objectives with societal impact-oriented objectives” leads the social challenges to be given a lower priority and risks further excluding citizens and civil society from the areas of research and innovation (GHA, 2018:4).

The strong agency given to businesses and industry in CE practice and policy lies in the dominant ecological modernisation ideas in the EU (Friant et al, 2020; Yalçın et al, 2023). This discourse promotes a win-win scenario for both the economy and the environment through technological innovation and new business models. Seeing the circular future as a technoscientific challenge with an over-reliance on market mechanisms secures a key position for incumbent actors. They take over that strong agency building on their extensive resources, ownership of data, cutting-edge expertise in developing new technologies, and control over markets.

Overall, institutional strategies reveal that incumbent lobbyists use scientific knowledge as a form of currency to gain political access and exert influence over the governance of science. (Saltelli et al, 2022). With the latest Framework Program for Research and Innovation, industry actors are given a strong agency to influence the research and innovation directions in the EU. The increase in industry-backed scientific research comes with a strategy of utilisation of scientific knowledge to enhance corporate profitability and to minimise policies that are unfavourable to them. Incumbent actors enhance the reach and credibility of their scientific messaging through multiple strategies including participation in research consortiums and dominating stakeholder meetings. They go to an extent to create a bias towards the use of industry-favourable scientific evidence in policy and practice which will be covered in the next strategy.

3.5.3. Political Strategy

“Over the past years, we have been actively engaging with DG Environment on the revision of this key piece of legislation (PPWR), sharing our best practices and offering solutions to make this proposal both environmentally and economically successful. Yet despite our efforts, most of our key recommendations for ensuring food and products are adequately protected have not been taken on board. We therefore question whether the proposal is consistent with the *‘Better Regulation’* imperatives, principally whether an *‘evidence-based approach’* has been employed and whether the *‘evaluate-first’* principle has been met. We also believe that the *‘cost-effectiveness’* of various impacts and the *‘proportionality’* of key provision has not been adequately evaluated” (Europen, 2022, emphasis added).

When lobby groups attempt to change the framework or the context where regulatory processes take place, to the effect of the idea of regulating becomes undesirable or irrelevant, Saltelli et al. (2022) call this the political strategy. The opening quote above from the European packaging value chain statement on PPWR expresses concerns about the regulatory approach the EC has taken. Finding an industry alliance holding the Commission accountable against a regulatory framework (i.e. Better Regulation) hints at a different strategy than a well-known deregulatory advocacy. Incumbent actors operate the political strategy, not by promoting total deregulation but by supporting a re-regulation that increases reliance on industry-favourable evidence and gives access to early stages of decision-making. They do so by relying on their extensive knowledge of the European bureaucracy and matching the expectations of the policymakers. The political strategy nicely exemplifies the longitudinal aspect of capture beyond a specific policy failure and shows how capture ambiguities unfold over time (Pel, 2016). This strategy in the case of the PPWR is engraved into the EU’s Better Regulation agenda and its recently integrated innovation principle, which are introduced in the next paragraphs.

Better Regulation ideas go back to the 1990s, the times in which cost-benefit analysis was promoted by the tobacco industry and incorporated into the EU policymaking with the Treaty of Amsterdam (Smith et al, 2015). The Treaty served as a stepping stone and concerted efforts of lobbying intensified under the umbrella of the European Risk Forum (ERF). Since then, ERF, whose members include fossil fuel, pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, and chemical companies, organised a series of conferences and workshops and published policy notes and studies on Better Regulation (e.g. ERF, 2023). The Better Regulation agenda was formally introduced in the EU policymaking in the early 2000s and evolved and extended through guidelines and toolboxes into its current version.

Better Regulation is defined as “creating legislation that achieves its objectives while being targeted, effective, easy to comply with and with the least burden possible” (EC, 2021:3). The goals of efficient policymaking and reducing unnecessary burdens are mainly operationalised through evaluations, impact assessments, and stakeholder consultations. The evaluate-first principle requires existing legislation to be reviewed to check if it is coherent before proposing a new one in the same field. Impact assessments look at the potential economic, environmental, and social impacts of a new proposal or existing policy in a quantified manner. Stakeholder consultations invite stakeholders and citizens to express their opinions and provide policymakers with the best possible evidence base throughout the policy cycle. These core pillars have been extended under the Better Regulation agenda with new approaches including the “innovation principle”.

This new principle was also proposed by the ERF in 2013, which rebranded itself into the European Regulation and Innovation Forum (ERIF) in 2018. ERIF is registered under the category of think tanks and research institutions in the European Transparency Register⁷. As stated in the previous strategy, in parallel to its ASBL status, it works as a think-tank “dedicated to improving the regulatory framework of the EU institutions” through “original research, publications, and events” (ERF, 2013:3). The promotion of innovation principle to ensure the EU to maintain a regulatory environment conducive to innovation and growth is one of the main goals of the Forum (ERIF, 2022).

After years-long lobbying by ERIF as well as by BusinessEurope and CEFIC, the innovation principle, which aims to ensure that whenever policy or regulatory decisions are under consideration the impact on innovation as a driver for jobs and growth should be assessed and addressed (ERF, 2013), has been operationalised by the Commission through the Better Regulation Toolbox and integrated into the latest Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon Europe. “The second pillar on Global Challenges and Industrial Competitiveness will help realise Union policy objectives within the spirit of the Innovation Principle” stated the Framework proposal (EC, 2018b:10). According to the EC Factsheet on the innovation principle, the principle makes ‘EU laws smarter and future-oriented’ by increasing the prominence of innovation in all phases of the policy cycle (EC, 2022b).

The concerted effort continued for the wider integration of the principle into the EU. Lobbyists employed visible power by holding the Commission accountable against the Innovation Principle and Better Regulation. In his opinion piece “Innovation is the key to cutting packaging waste”, the Chief Executive Officer at Huhtamaki critiqued that restrictive regulations and bans ‘without the use of thorough impact assessments and without applying the innovation principle’ are becoming more prominent. He warned that this would make Europe less competitive and achieving climate ambitions more challenging:

“What Europe needs is innovation. That requires policymakers to have an unwavering commitment to evidence and science as part of Better Regulation. This will ensure we have the conditions and support that enable Europe’s businesses, including our own, to invest, innovate and produce goods and services, which have the highest environmental, economic, and social benefits. It is time for that commitment to be renewed” (Héaulmé, 2023).

The innovation principle under Better Regulation has been smartly pushed as a political strategy, but it could

⁷ERIF European Transparency Register (ID 52996964558-47).

not get away from criticism. For example, a coalition of civil society with 75 signing organisations sent a letter to the EC to state they do not support the innovation principle because it is an ‘unacceptable industry-created tool’ to ‘undermine key policies and regulations protecting human health and the environment’ (GHA, 2019). According to Holland (2018), the innovation principle is crafted to enhance the presence of incumbent interests in the early stages of decision-making. The additional layer of impact assessment prioritises economic quantification and impact over businesses and sidelines the precautionary principle. Unlike the precautionary principle, which is an established legal principle, the innovation principle is not a well-recognised law itself as it cannot be found in the EU Treaties, secondary legislation, or case law. Unless the innovation principle is properly defined based on a consultation with all groups and given a legal basis, it will continue to raise suspicion and mistrust rather than becoming a facilitator of innovation (Garnett et al, 2019).

The implementation of the innovation principle with extra layers of regulatory steps applied throughout the whole policy cycle (e.g. planning, design) is an excellent example of the hidden power of deciding who/what to include and/or exclude in the policy-making agenda. Even though the seemingly very idea that wanted to be eliminated in the first place was burdensome regulatory mechanisms, incumbent lobbyists secured reforms in policymaking that increased reliance on industry-favourable evidence where they used scientific knowledge as a currency to gain political leverage and utilised changes to upstream policymaking architecture which embeds the industry’s right to participate (Legg et al, 2021).

This also underlines the importance of being vigilant towards a political strategy that is employed in a slow, careful, and justificatory way. “When lobbyists and public officials embed their cultural understandings into regulatory institutions, (...) originally slow, deliberative reasoning begins to take on an automatic, unconscious character, buttressed by a growing body of law and knowledge (Li, 2023:1223). With a thorough understanding of the European bureaucracy, incumbent actors have succeeded in creating policy environments in which the use of science in decision-making is in the industry’s favour.

Lobby actors promoted their interest with narratives that precisely match the expectations of EU officials: innovation to promote growth, create jobs, and maintain the EU’s competitiveness at the global level. Invisible power aligned well with the dominant innovation narrative in the EU that builds on several assumptions: technological innovation leads to more societal benefit than harm and risk; it increases efficiencies and decreases the use of natural resources; and investment in science leads to technological advancement that brings societal wellbeing (Strand et al, 2018).

“Innovation is a defining characteristic of the modern economy.(...)In mature economies, innovation is the primary driver of prosperity, economic dynamism, greater choice, more jobs, and enhanced prosperity. It is mostly undertaken by the private sector, particularly large-scale firms” (ERIF, 2022).

All in all, the political strategy targeted the principles of policymaking, building on an alignment with the institutional culture of the EU, including the desirability of a certain type of economically exploitable innovation, the legitimacy of participation, and neutrality of impact assessments. That longitudinal and meticulous strategy secured a legitimate position for incumbent actors who used this in return to hold the regulators accountable. It demonstrated that regulatory capture strategies (co-)evolved from invalidating

evidence and bureaucratic expertise to rhetorical and societal functions of science (Saltelli et al, 2022). Without addressing the power dynamics within the boundaries of participation, choice of framing in the assessments, subjective value judgements of improved well-being or expediency of continuous growth and asking similar fundamental political questions it seems hard to escalate transitions towards better socio-ecological and democratic trajectories.

Science capture strategies	Epistemic strategy (Contesting the evidence or influencing the methods whereby the evidence is produced)	Institutional strategy (Delegitimising or appropriating the role of the institutional settings which produce the evidence)	Political strategy (Changing the framework of regulation and evidence which are seen as undesirable by the private interests)
	Incumbent lobbyists played merchants of doubt and diverted attention from the primary goals of revising the previous directive in accordance with the waste hierarchy	Incumbent lobbyists used technical and scientific knowledge as their new currency to purchase political access to influence the governance of science itself	Incumbent lobby actors hold the European Commission accountable against a regulatory framework and policy-making principles
Power dynamics			
Visible power (observable conflict in decision-making)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “The PPWR proposal is turning the clock back in the Green Deal with unscientific, non-realistic reuse targets” (McDonald’s) - Questioning scientific quality and realism, assuming definitory power over what science is and how the future will unfold 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Negative list conflicts with a science-based, non-discriminatory, future-oriented approach” (FINAT) - Criticising how processes have been designed and conducted, questioning the neutrality of institutional strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “We question whether the proposal is in line with the Better Regulation imperatives” (Europen) - Claiming legitimate stakes in procedures of policymaking
Hidden power (Who/what gets on the agenda)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reducing the discussion into LCA comparisons of single-use (paper) packaging vs reusable (plastic) packaging - Pushing for the exemption in the Waste Framework Directive - Excluding prevention and packaging waste volumes - Establishing an alliance to show this as a consensus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploiting resource imbalances for participation in standard-setting committees - Controlling data and developing their own standards and criteria - Increasing the industry’s presence in Horizon projects as research partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promoting not a total deregulation but a re-regulation that favours incumbent interests - Securing and utilising policymaking reforms to increase reliance on industry-favourable evidence and their right to participate
Invisible power (perceptions, meanings, discourses)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building the alliance campaigns on scepticism against plastic, aligning narratives of them being fossil-based material with toxicity impacts, low-recycling rates and creating dependency outside the EU - Promoting this messaging in the media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building on eco-modernist discourse, linking social, economic, and environmental concerns directly to technical solutions - Utilising the strong agency of market mechanisms - Over-trusting the sufficiency of quantification - Depoliticising the debate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building on narratives of innovation to promote growth, jobs, competitiveness - Aligning with the EU evidence-based policy culture without power discussions on the desirability of innovation, legitimacy of participation, neutrality of impact assessments

Table 7. Summary of incumbent power dynamics in science capture strategies

3.6. Discussion

Our findings demonstrated how incumbent takeaway and single-use packaging industry actors performed epistemic, institutional, and political strategies that target science for policymaking to resist change in the case of PPWR. The impact of these strategies has been reflected in reduced ambitions through the removal of targets, and in the addition of derogations and exemptions to the key waste prevention measures, for example, exempting paper and cardboard packaging from market restriction measures and deleting reuse targets for the takeaway sector.

However, the impact of capture strategies is not only constrained to the failure to keep the necessary ambition in the final policy proposal. In this paper, we explore capture as an ambiguous and longitudinal phenomenon by bringing the power perspective to the analysis. Going beyond the visible to explore hidden and invisible power contributed to studying capture in its complexity and to uncovering dynamics that produce, reproduce, legitimise, and sustain incumbency. To provide further insights, we discuss our findings on the capture of science in two overarching ways under the lens of deep incumbency to show how industry actors shape and are shaped by the dominant discourses, institutional mechanisms, and structural agency.

First, incumbents used science in a dual function to repoliticise and then depoliticise the debate. Incumbent industry actors strategically used visible power to exploit scientific uncertainty to their advantage. They used science in dual function to serve their interests. Initially, science has been used to repoliticise the debate with the play of merchants of doubt. The Commission's proposal has been critiqued for 'not placing science at the heart of the circular economy' (Le Lay and D'amato, 2022) as extensively covered in epistemic strategy. The EC urged to 'take more time to listen to the science brought to the packaging discussion' by reports commissioned by industry actors (EPPA, 2023). Many of these reports concentrated on contesting upstream measures, in which policymakers have been criticised for "misreading the waste hierarchy" (Rantanen, 2023b). These comparative LCAs aimed to prove a superior environmental outcome for single-use packaging over reusable alternatives, advocating for exemptions from the waste hierarchy as outlined in Article 4(2) of the Waste Framework Directive.

Subsequently, incumbents used science to depoliticise the debate with over-reaching claims of neutrality and objectivity of their assessments. They aligned their narratives with the centralised and standardised impact assessment culture of the EU institutions, overly relying on the perceived adequacy of quantitative models. The LCAs adopted a simplified framing of circularity at the material level, promoting the properties and functionalities of paper over plastic rather than exploring innovative packaging systems. These assessments are used to close-down the multidimensional challenge of packaging into a set of quantitative metrics.

By utilising science in a dual function, both to repoliticise the discussions by creating doubts in the evidence base and to depoliticise them by closing-down the debate, high ambitions of revising regulations in accordance with the waste hierarchy and incorporating upstream solutions have been lost in translation. Efforts to move away from throwaway applications are being systematically excluded from the discussions. The role of the single-use packaging industry and takeaway corporations in generating record-breaking volumes of packaging waste is made unaccountable. Incumbent actors leveraged their extensive understanding of the European bureaucracy to shape the agenda in ways that prioritise their interests.

Second, incumbents used science as a currency to purchase political leverage and hold strategic positioning in the debate. By leveraging their control over confidential data, incumbent actors secured political influence in resisting certain targets in PPWR that are unfavourable to their interests. Through deliberate investments in scientific research and participating in research consortiums, they developed a range of recyclability standards before the Commission made a regulatory proposal. They presented themselves as scientifically credible actors committed to evidence-based policymaking, as responsible front-runners of circularity and breakthrough innovators. As opposed to their self-positioning, the policymakers have been positioned as ideological (Rantanen, 2022), civil society actors as aspirational (Rantanen, 2023a), and consumers as utility maximisers (EPPA, 2023) to shape the narrative to their advantage in the PPWR debate.

The asymmetry of knowledge created dependency on these actors, and narrative realignment with growth-oriented techno-innovations created constant reinforcement of incumbency while excluding others from the processes. Incumbents' strategic positioning builds on the strong agency granted to industry actors by the eco-modernist ideas in policy packages and framework programmes. According to this discourse, science serves as an ever-expanding frontier, and the demand for circularity on a finite planet will be satisfied through anticipated abundant technological innovations in the future. Technoscience will continually provide contemporary humans with novel and advanced ways of life and drive growth, mainly relying on market mechanisms and industrial innovation.

Incumbent actors cleverly embedded themselves in policy environments and operated an invisible power play by closely matching the preferences and vocabulary of EU officials. These actors used their privileged position to influence not only the content of regulatory discussions but also the institutional mechanisms and regulatory framework within which these discussions took place to “justify decisions, command authority, foster trust, build legitimacy, manage blame, and secure acceptance” (Stirling, 2014:90). Their access to proprietary data and technical expertise became a form of currency, exchanged for influence and favourable regulatory outcomes.

All in all, despite increasing attention to the claims concerning the inclusive, efficient, and transparent participation of ‘all relevant stakeholders’ in research and innovation programmes, consultations, and standard-setting committees, there are no deliberative policy interventions yet been proposed by the European institutions to address vested interests and concentrations of power in knowledge. What is interesting to note is that the overt influence of power in the promotion of science and innovation towards particular ends, such as driving economic growth, creating jobs, or the EU being a global pioneer in circularity is explicitly mentioned. Especially in promoting competitiveness against the rising scientific and technological strengths of other countries, the dynamics of power are prominent in the EU policy documents.

Here, there is a vital role for transition studies to bring the power perspective in for opening-up and deconstructing these “forms of justificatory closure” (Stirling, 2014:91). Having more concrete cases of incumbent power strategies of exerting influence on the formal codification and use of science for policy is crucial to understand how processes of capture occur. Exploring capture in its complexity beyond the outcome in the policy, with the factors of agency, institutions, and interests in broader political dynamics would contribute to more effective anticipation of and dealing with capture. The challenge of accelerating the circular transitions towards better socio-ecological and democratic trajectories lies in questioning and resisting incumbency dynamics. Deliberative efforts and more critical and reflexive approaches can be

catalysts to more vibrant political debates over framings, questions, and interests under knowledge production.

3.7. Conclusion

This paper looks at incumbent strategies of science capture from a power perspective with the case study of the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation. It contributes to the transitions literature in three ways: first, it brings a novel perspective on the strategies of incumbent resistance that target science for policymaking; second, it focuses on the packaging industry which has not been covered extensively; and finally it brings the power perspective in to explore capture in its complexity and uncover deep incumbency to add greater nuance. It shows how political, social, institutional, and discursive structures create a circular reinforcement of incumbency beyond visible policy outcomes of regulatory capture.

To do so, it builds on secondary data from document analysis, media sources, and online lobbying databases. Future studies can engage with lobbying strategies of capture with primary data from interviews with engaged actors, such as policymakers and business association representatives. That can bring interesting insights about insider dynamics in private meetings or revolving doors. A detailed look at the strategies and positioning of actors other than industry, for example, non-governmental organisations, SMEs and members of the European Parliament can also provide interesting insights. Through presenting strategies of science capture, this research opens up ways to reflect, challenge and transform these mechanisms of capture and power relations in the production and use of science. Future research can engage with the practical implications of being more capable of noticing and avoiding science capture, for example through strengthening mechanisms of conflict-of-interest statements in scientific research to detect influence, connections, and financing by private actors or through revising procedures of stakeholder consultations to bring attention to asymmetric levels of influence and concentrations of power. Other opportunities for further research can arise with the following questions: How does the EU institutional context have to be reshaped to better address the power relations in knowledge generation? What are the strategies of resistance and counteraction against incumbent influence on scientific knowledge? How do incumbent actors employ power to shape scientific knowledge in other sectors or geographies? For profound socio-ecological transitions towards just and democratic futures, it is crucial to explore these questions and actively challenge the dynamics of deep incumbency.

Chapter 4

In search of a relational circular economy through art: the case of NaturArchy

Abstract

As circular economy (CE) discourse increasingly acknowledges systemic complexity, its implementation remains largely governed by technocratic, control-oriented approaches rooted in reductionist paradigms. This paper examines how relational thinking can reorient CE towards more integrated and transformative practices. Drawing on a case study of *NaturArchy*, a science-art initiative led by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre, this study explores how interdisciplinary collaborations between artists, scientists, and policymakers challenge dominant human-nature dualisms and open space for alternative ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics. Through qualitative analysis of semi-structured interviews, artistic interventions, and field observations, the research illustrates how artistic practices facilitate embodied, affective, and situated engagements with complexity. By foregrounding more-than-human agency, socio-ecological justice, and practices of care and humility, *NaturArchy* offers a compelling lens through which to reimagine CE not only as a technical optimisation model but as a relational, ethical, and co-creative process. The findings contribute to a growing body of scholarship advancing a relational paradigm in sustainability science, with implications for policy, governance, and transdisciplinary knowledge production.

Yalçın, N.G (2025) This chapter has been submitted to the *Journal of Sustainability Science*, awaiting decision.

4.1. Introduction

Transitions to a circular economy (CE) can be conceptualised at multiple levels, ranging from changing material flows within systems to profound shifts in the meaning-making processes. As the existential dimensions of the global ecological and social crisis become increasingly apparent, there is growing attention among social science researchers on more structural, fundamental changes to systems and societies (Bauwens, 2021; Jaeger-Erben, 2021), however, they maintain a relatively minor position within both academic and societal discussions that are dominated by technocratic eco-modernist ideas, policies and business practices.

While CE emphasises systems thinking and the interdependence of economy, society, and environment, dominant approaches often remain rooted in reductionist paradigms (Kovacic et al., 2020; Hartley & Kirchherr, 2023). Mainstream approaches fall short of addressing the complexity surrounding CE beyond quantified models that remain captive to substantialist assumptions and categorical distinctions between humans and the world around them (e.g. human-nature, reason-emotion, fact-value, and mind-body) (Rask, 2022). While acknowledging systemic complexity, these narratives often fail to translate into transformative actions, hindering wider socio-political-ecological possibilities beyond techno-managerial solutions that maintain modernist ambitions of control (Arora et al., 2020).

Recent scholarship in sustainability science has increasingly engaged with relational approaches, emphasising dynamic interconnections and non-hierarchical ways of knowing (West et al., 2020; Walsh et al., 2021). Unlike reductionist perspectives that fragment reality into isolated entities and linear cause-effect relationships, relational thinking foregrounds a living, evolving assemblage of relationships and responsibilities (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2010; Mancilla Garcia et al., 2019). Relational perspectives offer alternative ways of understanding complexity and human-nature relations within CE, yet their integration into CE discourse and practice is yet to be explored (Jaeger-Erben et al., upcoming).

A promising avenue for exploring relationality in CE is art, which provides an epistemological space for rethinking human-nature interdependencies and engages with complexity holistically, integrating embodied, affective, and sensory ways of knowing (Heras et al., 2021; Vervoort et al., 2024). Artistic practices foster imaginative, speculative, and experiential engagements with socio-ecological systems, creating spaces where human and more-than-human interdependencies can be perceived, felt, and reimagined (Propper, 2017; Moriggi et al., 2020). Art cultivates empathy, care, and attentiveness to relational entanglements, offering new ethical and political imaginaries that challenge instrumental views of nature (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2010; Haraway, 2016). As such, art can help not only to reveal the limitations of reductionist models but also to explore relational, caring, and just approaches to CE.

To examine this potential, this study focuses on NaturArchy, a sci-art initiative by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. Through its interdisciplinary collaborations between artists, scientists, and policymakers, NaturArchy explicitly critiques hierarchical human-nature dichotomies and explores alternative ways of being and knowing. This paper explores how the project reflexively engages with relational approaches and its implications for opening up possibilities beyond modernist, control-oriented CE toward a relational, caring CE, one that foregrounds interdependence, humility, and socio-ecological justice. More specifically, this paper explores the following research questions:

1. In what ways can relational thinking challenge reductionist approaches in the CE and foster a more integrated understanding of human-nature interdependencies? Particularly, in what ways can relational thinking contribute to a nuanced understanding of complexity knowledge and action within the CE?
2. How does the NaturArchy project, through its art-science collaborations, facilitate the exploration of relational ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics in CE discourse and practice?

This article proceeds as follows: Section 4.2 provides an overview of the inconsistencies between complex systems narrative and practice in mainstream CE approaches; Section 4.3 introduces the relational paradigm; Section 4.4 elaborates on choosing art and NaturArchy as an approach to explore relationality; Section 4.5 presents the methodology and proceeds into the findings in Section 4.6. Section 4.7 discusses the research questions on how relational thinking offers a way to bridge human-nature divides and move beyond the Modernist, control-oriented approach to the CE by foregrounding non-hierarchical relationships, embodied interactions, and alternative ontologies explored in NaturArchy.

4.2. Complex systems and CE

The influential CE actor in the EU, EMF, explains how the systems perspective is integral to the CE concept in their “deep dive” article⁸.

“At its most basic level, an economy is the name we give to a process: society making use of natural resources to create products and services that people need or want e.g. homes for shelter, and food for nourishment. Viewed in this way, our economy, society and environment are interdependent systems, the vitality of one affects the vitality of them all” (EMF, 2019).

In the article, the linear economy is presented as an economic model that approaches the world as a machine that is “predictable, understandable, controllable”, separated from any connection to the natural and social systems that maintain it. It calls for thinking through systems, taking on the challenge of complexity, and understanding how parts of a system interact to produce certain dynamics and behaviour (EMF, 2019). It concludes with an invitation to think with a new metaphor, the economy not as a machine but as a forest based on the living system perspectives to achieve “a more accurate and nuanced understanding of the economy as one part of a much larger whole” (EMF, 2019).

EMF is not the only CE actor that presents an understanding of systemic complexity. On a discursive level, the majority of CE actors demonstrate an awareness of the complexity involved, acknowledging the intricate dynamics between the economy, society and the environment and the intricate relations between stakeholders (Zwiers et al., 2020). However, this understanding remains limited when it comes to defining concrete targets or implementing transformative actions. There is a disconnect that persists between the “sayings” that reflect systemic knowledge and the “doings” associated with transformational action (Zwiers et al., 2020; Friant et al., 2021).

⁸ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/systems-and-the-circular-economy-deep-dive>

One reason for this disconnect, among many others, is taking a reductionist complexity approach (Kovacic et al., 2020) that enlarges the analytical scope by increasing the number of observed entities, including more variables, and modelling more interconnections, but ultimately maintaining a mechanistic orientation. Reductionist complexity in CE broadens the boundaries of governed entities (e.g. ecosystem, infrastructure, behaviours) and signals interactions between different policy domains with an aim to reconcile economic interests with environmental concerns (i.e. win-win). Major policy decisions adopt a macro-level systemic perspective through quantified methods of material flow analysis, life-cycle analysis, etc, to provide simplified representations of the complex phenomena (Hartley and Kirchherr, 2023).

This particular mode of governance through quantification, modelling, and standardisation risks reifying the modernist, mechanistic assumptions that CE claims to move beyond and tends to prioritise circular strategies to control and manage environmental systems, treating nature as a collection of discrete units or services to be optimised (Hartley & Kirchherr, 2023; Arora et al., 2020). Even though the dominant CE framings theoretically emphasise the interconnectedness between humans and nature, nature is perceived either as an idealised source of inspiration for industrial and business practices (Kovacic et al., 2020), or as an object for human use (e.g. raw materials) and service requiring conservation (e.g. sink of waste and pollution) (Rask, 2022). This prioritisation of human benefits while treating environmental costs as externalities fails to adequately account for complex ecosystem interactions beyond simplified notions of stocks and flows, downplays the relational value of more than humans⁹, and fails to capture critical ethical considerations that shape human relationships with nature in diverse and complex ways (Raymond et al, 2013).

It is essential to reveal the underlying substantialist assumptions of modernist paradigms, which conceptualize the world through reifying categories such as human-nature, object-subject, value-fact in CE research, policy and practice. These dualisms perpetuate prediction and control through techno-managerialism and foster an instrumental view of nature that sustains human domination over nature. By perceiving more-than-human entities in nature as passive objects without agency and inferior to active subjects, ecomodernist ambitions to control are realised by using the 'right technologies' decided by the market and the state 'experts' to decouple humans from nature (Arora et al, 2020).

As a way to challenge substantialist assumptions and capture the complexity of human-nature relationships in a more nuanced way, sustainability scientists are increasingly engaging with research linked to the "relational turn" in the humanities and social sciences (West et al. 2020; Hertz et al. 2020; Walsh et al. 2020; Mancilla Garcia et al. 2020a, 2020b). Hertz et al. (2020) propose that shifting systems thinking from substantialist to relational assumptions can bridge the divide between humans and nature, enhance the understanding of complexity, and inspire innovative approaches to governance, management, and policy for sustainability. Can relational thinking contribute to CE in similar ways?

⁹ More than human as a theoretical concept acknowledges human life and society as being deeply interconnected with non-human entities, such as animals, plants, technologies, and natural systems. Referring to those as 'more than human' or 'non-human' recentres and reinforces the human as the main reference point and creates a dichotomy on its own, which is inherently problematic (Celer Mayer et al., 2020). We mark but do not aim to resolve these dilemmas for the purpose of this paper.

4.3. Relational paradigm

Relational thinking proposes that systems are not solely composed of individual parts and mechanical interactions but emerge through relationships and organisational processes that shape matter and its dynamics (Preiser et al., 2021). The interconnected components of systems generate emergent effects that differ from the sum of each part's individual effects. From this perspective, relationships and process interactions that shape system-wide organisation are recognised as having real impacts. This view stands in contrast to the mechanistic substantialist worldview, which denies ontological status to unobservable or immeasurable relationships and organisational patterns (Preiser et al, 2021).

Sustainability researchers are increasingly advocating for a paradigm shift to move the focus away from interactions between distinct entities; instead, they are emphasising dynamic, evolving processes and relationships (West et al. 2020; Hertz et al. 2020; Walsh et al. 2020; Mancilla Garcia et al. 2020a, 2020b). It refers to the embodied interactions and responses among all things (both human and more-than-human) in holistic contexts (West et al, 2020). In this view, complexity is not simply an increase in the number of variables but a reflection of interdependence, emergence, and co-becoming.

This “relational turn” refers to a shift in scholarship across various disciplines, encompassing diverse theories, commitments, and ideas rather than a single, unified approach (West et al., 2024). In their extensive review, Walsh et al. (2021) look at how relational approaches related to sustainability have been interpreted and conceptualised in the humanities, social sciences and natural sciences: *Relational approaches to ontology* assert that entities do not exist independently but emerge through the relationships that constitute them. This perspective challenges foundational dualisms, such as nature/culture and mind/matter, that underpin modern Western thought. Relational ontologies seek to bridge these divides, emphasising the co-constitution of human and non-human worlds. Theoretical frameworks like speculative realism, process philosophy, new materialism, and indigenous cosmologies offer rich insights into these relational dynamics (Walsh et al., 2021). *Relational approaches to epistemology* critique the objectivist, control-oriented stance of Enlightenment empiricism. Rather than separating subject and object, they emphasise embodied, situated, and interconnected knowledge systems. Agency is viewed as distributed across human and more-than-human, defined by the capacity to affect rather than by intentional consciousness. These approaches emerge from psychology, sociology, feminist theory, and science and technology studies, advocating for transdisciplinary methods that reflect the complexity of entangled systems (Gillard et al., 2016; Walsh et al., 2021). *Relational approaches to ethics* are central to ecofeminism, political ecology, posthumanism, and environmental justice, with an emphasis on non-anthropocentrism (i.e. they do not position human interests as a central moral concern). Ecofeminism, for instance, exposes the intertwined oppressions of women, marginalized groups, and nature, critiquing Western dualisms for reinforcing hierarchical power structures; and argues that dominant models of science, technology, and development perpetuate both social and ecological injustices through systemic control and exploitation (Plumwood, 1993, de la Bellacasa, 2017).

Donna Haraway's *Staying with the Trouble* (2016) offers an influential articulation of relational approaches. Haraway challenges the technocratic impulse to solve complex ecological crises with finality and instead urges to “stay with the trouble”, to remain in the thick of complexity, with all its entangled ethical, material,

and political dimensions. In this frame, systems are never fully knowable or controllable; they are ongoing, co-created, and relational. Haraway reframes sustainability as a relational ethic, emphasising multispecies interdependence, rather than anthropocentric optimisation, advocating for “making-with” rather than “making alone.” Her metaphor of tentacular thinking, drawn from organisms like spiders and octopuses, illustrates a lateral, multisensory, and non-linear engagement with the world. Rather than aiming to simplify or resolve complexity, Haraway's invitation is to sense, dwell in, and respond to it through practices of care, speculation, and storytelling.

In this article, I take an exploratory approach to relationality to study how it can enrich the understanding of complexity knowledge and action, and human–nature interconnectedness in CE. I turn to art to open up ontological and epistemological spaces of possibility (Vervoort et al., 2024): offering alternative, imaginative ways of engaging with the world, challenging substantialist assumptions that separate humans from nature, and expanding epistemological frameworks to acknowledge the qualitative, relational complexity of the world.

4.4. Why arts and NaturArchy?

One of the many powers of arts-based approaches lies in their ability to integrate diverse epistemologies, e.g. by bringing scientific, embodied, experiential, and indigenous knowledge together (Heras et al., 2021). Artistic methods incorporate emotional, sensory, and experiential ways of knowing, which can enhance understanding of the current socio-ecological crisis in its complexity (Propper, 2017). Art can stimulate unique learning opportunities that lead to profound shifts in self-perception, assumptions, and worldview and offer new ways of being and relating to the world. Critical reflection on the learnings can be transformative when channelled into shared consciousness, questioning dominant paradigms, and inspiring structural change (Vervoort et al., 2024).

Through creative engagement, art can cultivate empathy and foster a sense of connection, care, and responsibility toward the natural world (Moriggi et al., 2020). In making these connections perceptible and emotionally resonant, art can create a relational ontology by underlining the interconnectedness of all beings, repositioning humans within socio-ecological systems and opening space for the more-than-human agency. This shift in the perceptions of being and relating to the world can bring critical reflections on the implicit assumptions of the present and imagining alternative futures. In this sense, imagination plays a dual role: addressing the norms, structures, and institutions (e.g. modernist control mechanisms) that reinforce the current socio-ecological crisis and opening new collective horizons for action and alternative futures (e.g. relational-caring) (Moore and Milkoreit, 2020).

In this paper, I tap into the potential of art to explore relationality to enhance understanding of complexity knowledge and action and human-nature interconnectedness in CE. For exploration, I chose the NaturArchy project as a case study, which is the fourth edition of Resonances, the flagship initiative of the JRC Science Art Society (Sci-Art) team. The project aims to re-imagine the Western understanding of the relationship between humans and more-than-human and advocates for granting juridical rights to the natural world.

“Trees, forests, rivers, mountains, seas, stardust, DNA — imagine the environment not as the backdrop of our activities, imagine objects of nature not as items to be appropriated or exploited, but as subjects with intrinsic value and full juridical rights. Cancel the tired subject-object dichotomy between person

and environment, the obsolete opposition nature and culture that does not hold in view of modern scientific discoveries; do away with conditions of mastery, appropriation, and submission; reimagine human concerns as unreservedly dependent on the natural world, integrated within nature. Only such a shift in our conceptualisation of nature can change our deep relation to the matter, species, ecosystems around us. A real Green Deal requires a systemic change of ground.” (from *NaturArchy: Towards a Natural Contract* curatorial statement)

The NaturArchy project ran from 2022 to 2024. The artists were selected based on the open call for Resonances IV, and the projects were validated after the summer school in June 2022, which took place at the JRC Ispra site (Italy). Interested researchers and policymakers were invited to participate by the SciArt team. Residencies run from January to June 2023, followed by the production of 16 artworks and the final exhibition from May 25th 2024 to September 29th 2024, at iMAL, Art Centre for Digital Cultures and Technology in Brussels (Belgium).

NaturArchy serves as a highly relevant case study for our exploratory paper for three reasons: firstly, it builds on the explicit critique on the hierarchical dichotomies of human-nature, object- subject; secondly, it aims to reimagine different ways of being in relation to the natural world other than anthropocentric relationship; and lastly, it operates under the JRC’s Science for Policy unit of the European Commission which gives an opportunity to delve into the institutional mechanisms and reflect on “sayings” in complexity knowledge and “doing” in action in CE in the EU.

4.5. Methodology

For this study, I employed a four-step data collection process. First, I carried out comprehensive research of the NaturArchy project website to gain an overview of its thematic focus, curatorial statement, background information on the art projects, and participant details (artists, scientists, curators, policymakers, collaborators). Additionally, the project’s extensive media archive, including recordings from the summer school, interim residency presentations, and open-access panel discussions, served as a valuable source of secondary data. Second, I conducted semi-structured interviews, each lasting approximately one hour, with artists in residence, members of the curatorial committee, and JRC scientists involved in the NaturArchy project. Interviews were conducted via Microsoft Teams, and participants were invited through direct contact during the exhibition opening at iMAL and via the NaturArchy mailing list, accompanied by a research design document. The response rate was approximately 40%, resulting in 13 interviews. While the entire network was invited, I was unable to secure responses from participating policymakers. Table 9 provides an overview of the interview participants. Thirdly, before and after the interviews, I visited the NaturArchy exhibition at iMAL and joined in-person and online events concerning the exhibition. Lastly, I revisited the NaturArchy website to track updates following the end of the project. The data collection process concluded in December 2024. To analyse the data, I developed a coding scheme in NVivo with codes on relational ontology (subcodes on worldview and dualisms); relational epistemology (subcodes on modern knowledge systems and alternative ways of knowing); relational ethics (subcodes on shared roots of domination and more-than-human agency); and critiques and reflection (subcodes on complexity and human-nature interdependence) which formed the structure of presentation and discussion of the findings in the following sections.

Numeric code	Role in the NaturArchy project	Date
Interviewee 1 (I1)	Curator	03/04/2024
Interviewee 2 (I2)	Curator	23/04/2024
Interviewee 3 (I3)	Artist	03/07/2024
Interviewee 4 (I4)	Artist	03/07/2024
Interviewee 5 (I5)	Artist	04/07/2024
Interviewee 6 (I6)	Artist	04/07/2024
Interviewee 7 (I7)	Scientist	05/07/2024
Interviewee 8 (I8)	Curator	05/07/2024
Interviewee 9 (I9)	Scientist	10/07/2024
Interviewee 10 (I10)	Artist	11/07/2024
Interviewee 11 (I11)	Artist	11/07/2024
Interviewee 12 (I12)	Artist	22/07/2024
Interviewee 13 (I13)	Artist	23/07/2024

Table 8. Interviewees from the NaturArchy project

4.6. Findings

This section explores how relational thinking is experimented with in the NaturArchy, offering alternative ways of engaging with complexity, human–nature interdependencies, and transformative potential within the CE. This section examines how relational ontologies are explored through efforts to dismantle dualisms and foreground co-constitutive relations; how relational epistemologies emerged via transdisciplinary and experiential modes of inquiry; and how relational ethics are enacted through attention to non-human agency, care, and socio-ecological justice in NaturArchy. Together, these findings illuminate how art-science practices invite critical reflection on the assumptions underpinning CE and offer openings for a more situated, humble, and interconnected understanding of systemic transformation.

4.6.1. Relational approaches to ontology

“NaturArchy: Towards a Natural Contract explores different ways of being in relation to the natural world. (...) Embracing the arts for systemic change, this exhibition proposes to reconsider our attitudes towards nature and the non-human by probing issues of deep ecology, rights of nature, sustainability, decentring the human, and the decolonising of nature. (...) The artworks on show provocatively call to re-imagine a sense of place and belonging in the world and to respond to the entangled and symbiotic relationship between human and environment.” (Exhibition booklet)

Relational approaches to ontology are at the very core of exploration in NaturArchy. The projects focused on intricate interconnections between pollinators, plants, humans and non-humans (in *Anthos*), interdependence through forever chemicals in human bodies (in *These Relations are Forever*), opening-up space of confrontation with dominant value systems (in *Politics in Disguise*), kinship in indigenous cosmologies of Shipibo-Conibo community on relationships between territory, human beings, non-human forms, and the spiritual worlds (in *Invisible Seeds*) among others.

“Although all art-science projects under the umbrella of the NaturArchy are very diverse in terms of artistic methods or scientific themes, somehow they are also interconnected; they speak to each

other. Either they are connected through talking about complexity, or interdependencies about the human/non-human and questioning this division.” (18)

Figure 2. Ocean Connections, film still (Kristin Bergaust)

The *Ocean Connections* (Figure 2) project provides a nice example of questioning the hierarchical dualities and subverting human-centred approaches towards nature. In *Ocean Connections*, artist Kristin Bergaust reimagines an alternative representation of the oceans. Inspired by Laura Mulvey’s (1975) *Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema*, which critiques the male gaze that frames women as passive objects for male visual pleasure, the project exposes how dominant visual cultures similarly position nature as passive, scenic, and silent. In both cases, a hierarchical gaze creates a subject/object duality, reinforcing systems of control and exploitation. Instead of representing the ocean as a distant, abstract, blue void, *Ocean Connections* invites audiences into an immersive, multisensory experience that foregrounds the ocean as a dynamic, relational presence. Through sound, movement, and embodied engagement, artist Kristin Bergaust shifts the viewer’s role from detached observer to active participant to discover a kinship with life in the oceans. By decentring the human gaze and emphasising interdependence, the project resists the extractive, objectifying tendencies of anthropocentric worldviews. It calls for a more reciprocal and situated way of relating to the more-than-human world, one rooted in care, attention, and entanglement.

One crucial theme raised from the interviews regarding exploring, imagining, and experimenting with the relational ontologies and questioning hierarchical dualities of human-nature, object-subject through art-sci projects was how these engagements created spaces for reflection about individual perspectives and positionalities of artists, scientists, and the curators. Interviewees shared their experiences of questioning implicit assumptions, biases, and expectations they had through relational learning that emerged during collaborations. These learnings within the teamwork between artists, scientists, and policymakers took different forms as “sudden excitements” (12) or “longer reflection processes” (19), in the form of critical consciousness about the dominant worldviews and exploration of interrelations of all kinds:

“Taking a moment to situate oneself in the environment and getting aware that our (*humans*) way of seeing and perceiving is not the only one was very inspiring.” (I13)

“This kind of coming out of your own perspective and thinking where do I stand effectively with respect to the other beings in this world, is really important.” (I2)

“Because when you open up, you see a different way of connecting, other things also come into focus to care about.” (I8)

“I think imagination is something that helps you to get out of certain, routine ways of thinking. It's about being confronted with questions that you're normally not being confronted with, so there's also a speculative sign.” (I2)

Overall, relational ontologies were at the heart of the NaturArchy projects and explored to overcome human-non-human separation and hierarchies shaping the dominant modern worldview in all projects. Participants reported experimenting with the theme: leading to gaining perspectives they were unfamiliar with, learning from each other and from the co-creation processes, engaging with deeper reflections on how relations of all kinds fundamentally constitute their being, and greater acknowledgement of complexity.

4.6.2. Relational approaches to epistemology

Relational approaches to epistemology have been explored in NaturArchy through a transdisciplinary focus and using different creative art-based methods to integrate different ways of knowing. During these exploration processes, participants reported coming across “limitations of the dominant scientific rationale” and “hyper-specialisation” (I13) “to make sense of the complexity at hand” (I6). Art-based methods in NaturArchy created possibilities for experimenting with other ways of knowing, crossing disciplinary boundaries, space and freedom to experience more-than-cognitive approaches.

“There were some interesting conversations back and forth. Many of the artists had questions that span multiple disciplines and fields, which required complex answers from different disciplines. And this is something that the scientists were painfully aware of. You could see in the conversations they say, “Oh, I'm interested, but I don't know what to say” or “I'm interested, but I say this little thing, but it's actually like this (*big, shows with a hand gesture*), so you should maybe talk to someone from there or from there” (I7).

“The creative collaborations of artists and scientists offer ways to handle less extreme forms of specialisation and therefore allow cross-fertilisation of ideas. This deepens a shared understanding of how to encourage dialogue and collaboration between disciplines and ways of being. (...) Bringing art and science together allows ways of knowing complexity through engaging with all our senses” (Exhibition booklet).

Figure 3. *These Relations Are Forever*, film stills, 4 channel video (Jemma Woolmore)

Exploration of relational epistemology through senses and embodiment was central in several projects in NaturArchy, including *These Relations are Forever* (Figure 3). This project brought four researchers together, who work on endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) from different disciplines. Each researcher developed a ritual building on an embodied methodology in their scientific practice in agriculture, law, health and water policies. Reframing the researchers as "Wise Women," their scientific practices become acts of care, with rituals connecting bodies, scales, cycles, and disciplines. Addressing fertility, community, and more-than-human health, the project used storytelling and ritual to imagine alternative ways of being, offering hope and new possibilities for 'staying with the trouble' (Haraway, 2016).

Embodiment in *These Relations are Forever* connected diverse ways of knowing and understanding the world beyond cognitive approaches. It offered multi-sensorial means for experiencing reality through the active body and emotions. Saskia Vermeylen, lawyer and researcher at the University of Strathclyde reflected on her experience as part of the *These Relations are Forever* project. She used dance to understand the relationship between body & mind, and nature & society and to explore legal possibilities of the future in an embodied and sensual manner. Her dance ritual was curated as a 5 rhythms dance movement at Bitterfeld, a water treatment site near Berlin where polluted groundwater is purified, to explore the effects of EDCs on the body. In her reflection blogpost, she highlighted how the ritual transforms the human body into a legible site for interpreting the overlooked intersections between environmental contamination and regulatory frameworks, a perspective often absent in current environmental law. At the personal level, embodiment created a unique, lived experience through her own body, senses, and emotions.

"(...) dance is so much more than just a metaphor for a legal process, it is a practice that can create a space to think, but above all feel the law. It transcends the mind and reason and allows us to think with and through the body about legal alternatives that can regulate for a better future" (Vermeylen, 2023).

During our interview, another researcher shared her emotions about performing her ritual for the project. She concluded with self-reflexivity about slowing down and the discovery of sensorial and affective learning. This other-than-cognitive knowledge in rituals was mentioned by another participant as a critique of mainstream knowledge systems, who concluded with a suggestion to integrate embodiment into policymaking processes to create a shared emotional energy, a joint focus of attention, and physical co-presence with humans and non-humans who are subject to the discussion (e.g. soil in agricultural policy).

“The moments of performing were the most rewarding, being in a completely different environment than what we’re used to here (*JRC*). It was such a strong feeling that I felt like, wow, that was the actual artwork, not the movies in the exhibition. Of course, movies are amazing, they did a great job to elaborate sounds and light but performing the ritual was the most touching experience. (...) I think all the rituals have these elements of changing our way of thinking a bit. And yeah, for me it was the idea of slowing and learning from different senses.” (I9)

“I think it is also a critique of scientific practice or generally dominant knowledge practices that tend to exclude embodied knowledge or experiential knowledge. There's like a hierarchy that it's not as legitimate as rational, objective scientific methodologies that produce knowledge. (...) What would the future look like if we built ritual into some of the processes of policymaking? We don't have to totally change science or policy. What if there was a ritual of everyone meeting at the field, taking their shoes off and having the discussion touching the soil? Just adding that on, I don't see why that's such a crazy idea.” (I6)

Overall, relational approaches to epistemology brought the limitations of modern knowledge systems and disciplinary boundaries to the surface, awakened sensory perceptions leading to a richer understanding of complexity, stimulated new ideas and affective connections, and opened up new sources of reflexivity about humans' place and relationships with and within nature.

4.6.3. Relational approaches to ethics

Relational approaches to ethics are explored in *NaturArchy* by acknowledging that agency is distributed across networks, thus recognising non-human agency, and contextualising human-nature relations under a power lens to highlight shared roots of social and ecological injustices.

Scientist Caterina Cacciatori brought the inspiration to recognise non-human agency from her participation in *These Relations are Forever* to the scientific project she works on, *Gems of Water*” at the JRC. The project aims to build a co-created scientist-citizen approach to water quality monitoring around the world. Participants from local communities receive a kit and a protocol to collect samples and send the extracted pollutants to the JRC Water Laboratory. Scientists carry out the screening for contamination and water quality, which they send back to the communities. Caterina brought forward the idea of adding a line to the water sampling protocol to acknowledge the water body as an active participant in the project, which appears in the official publication as follows:

“(...) When you have arrived at the sampling site, check that the sampling can be performed safely, otherwise choose another location. *Acknowledge and thank the water body you are sampling from, in however manner you feel more comfortable with (with a thought, a drawing, a poem, and a*

dance). If you like, feel free to share it with us. Wear personal protective equipment, such as gloves. (...)" (Cacciatori et al, 2023:13, *emphasis added*)¹⁰

Acknowledging the non-human agency in the Gems of Water project challenges the prevailing scientific perspective, which often views water as an object or commodity rather than a subject capable of generating and acting upon non-exploitative relationships and meanings. It acknowledges that in sampling, humans are drawing from water bodies that generously grant access to the valuable information they hold and underscores the importance of gratitude, not only toward scientists and citizen scientists but also toward water itself (Cacciatori et al, 2023). One of the interviewees shared their reflection on the matter:

"There's this idea that in the name of science, it's OK to go on land and take samples because scientists are generally feeling like they're doing something good. Asking permission and giving thanks to the water before taking something, I think this kind of verbal acknowledgement of an ecosystem and a living being and adding in some small gratitude rituals and giving attention as care can create a different future." (I6)

Figure 4. Politics in Disguise, video still (Claus Schöning)

The *Politics in Disguise* (Figure 4) art-sci project also foregrounds the distributed nature of agency by centring a fungus as a political orator, symbolically speaking on behalf of animals, plants, and unicellular organisms. By granting political presence to a non-human, the project disrupts the anthropocentric assumption that politics is the exclusive domain of human rationality. The project reframes political legitimacy as something relational, emerging through networks of interdependence rather than rooted in isolated human autonomy. In foregrounding multispecies agency, the work critiques the historical continuity of political systems that reproduce exclusionary, hierarchical logics and systemic inequalities. It opens up a space for

¹⁰ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC133408>

imagining alternative forms of politics, ones that are responsive to ecological entanglement, ethical plurality, and shared vulnerability.

“Bringing in this non-human factor, which for me is a way to tackle all these racialised, colonial, and patriarchal power structures that are still in politics all the time, right? The way we make politics has stayed pretty much the same for a long time. It’s reproducing a lot of things that happened all over human history that led us towards big challenges. And this non-human element is really a way to point towards all this, and thinking about how we can invent and imagine a better form of politics that is more inclusive and future-proof. That was what we wanted to inspire people to think about” (110).

Figure 5. Installation view of *With Salt and Rocks in Our Veins* at IMAL (Penelope Cain)

With Salt and Rocks in Our Veins (Figure 5) continues this interrogation of anthropocentric assumptions by tracing the entangled ecologies and extractive politics of lithium mining in Chile’s Atacama Desert. Centring the contested rights to water within a salt-dependent ecosystem, the project explores how the EU’s green, circular transitions reproduce extractive dynamics that impact environments far beyond its borders. Through speculative storytelling and a gamified virtual landscape, the work makes visible the hidden interdependencies between the Atacama and Europe, where decisions made in one geography manifest materially and ecologically in another. A real-time web crawler links global searches on lithium and green

energy to signs of environmental degradation within the virtual world, collapsing spatial and political distance and drawing attention to the uneven costs of sustainability and circularity.

Rather than portraying geology as inert or passive, the project animates salt and rock as living archives, repositories of memory, extraction, and transformation. In doing so, it invites a sensuous, embodied engagement with the mineral world, where veins of salt, water, and metal mirror circulations of power, metabolism, and colonial violence. This multisensory approach cautions against the promise of green transitions as inherently just or reparative. By foregrounding the ecological and political entanglements that underpin them, it gestures toward alternative ways of inhabiting the world through listening, sensing, and being with the more-than-human, offering a relational ethic rooted in care, accountability, and co-existence, while making visible the danger of reproducing extractives and colonial logics under the guise of sustainability and circularity (Exhibition booklet).

“Creating other than human entry points into this artwork, telling the story, empowering this remote site and the ecosystem that depends on the groundwater, subverts this kind of dominant paradigm of human-centric. In the artwork itself, the rocks move and come to an act of resistance as the groundwater drops and the web hits on lithium continues. This imagined resistance from the Earth itself is a form of unlearning. Because, of course, you have to suspend your Western belief systems to come at that work.” (I11)

Overall, in NaturArchy, relational approaches to ethics have been explored by recognising and strengthening non-human agency, bringing the shared roots of domination of humans and nature to the surface, and underlining the socio-ecological justice impacts of past and present actions.

4.7. Discussion

This article explores how relational thinking can bridge human-nature divides and deepen understanding of complexity knowledge and action. It turns to the transformative potential of art to open up ontological and epistemological possibilities with a case study of NaturArchy sci-art projects. This section provides insights and experiences gained from the art-sci projects and discusses them under the guidance of the research questions formulated in the introduction: In what ways can relational thinking challenge reductionist approaches in the CE and foster a more integrated understanding of human-nature interdependencies? Particularly, in what ways can relational thinking contribute to a nuanced understanding of complexity knowledge and action within the CE? How does the NaturArchy project, through its art-science collaborations, facilitate the exploration of relational ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics in CE discourse and practice?

Opening up to relational ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics can foster deeper reflexivity on modernist, control-oriented practices in the CE. While many CE actors acknowledge the interdependence of living systems, significant gaps remain between their narratives of complexity and transformative actions as discussed in Section 5.2. A strong reliance on reductionist complexity approaches fosters a "concrete, science-based, objective" approach through quantification and modelling, which makes the complexity of CE "controllable" by focusing on the technological opportunities and downplaying uncertainties (Kovacic et al, 2020). However, the techno-managerial win-win approach poses epistemic implications by silencing

uncertainties in scientific knowledge, such as neglecting the inherent challenges of establishing a CE driven by the continued expansion of the economy. It perpetuates an instrumental view of nature where non-human beings are objectified and lack agency and overlooks power imbalances and environmental injustices, particularly those affecting communities in the global South (Kovacic et al., 2020; Rask, 2022). Ultimately, Modernist controlling CE policies and practices build on a techno-managerial win-win approach, face the danger of reinforcing current patterns of injustice, exploiting nature and vulnerable humans, and perpetuating dualistic assumptions.

Relational thinking challenges these approaches by considering circularity not only as a technical optimisation problem, but as a practice of living well with complexity, the interconnectedness of all life forms, and cultivating attentiveness to both human and more-than-human agencies (Hertz et al, 2020). Rather than seeking to fix the world through better models, relational approaches encourage ways of knowing with humility and coming to terms with uncertainty (Mancilla-Garcia et al, 2020). When engaging with complex systems and facing various uncertainties, the aim is not only to arrive at scientifically valid conclusions but also to address subjective, social, and ethical questions in the context of the CE. Practising humility is not only pointing out the gaps in knowledge and missing data, instead, it is recognising that uncertainty is inherent to all knowing and that reality is multiple and complex (Arora et al, 2020). In this way, relational CE departs from the Modernist assumption of objective knowledge (that humans gain knowledge by observing the world from an external standpoint) but emphasises that knowledge is shaped by the specific, practical ways humans interact with and experience the material world and reality is understood through embodied interactions with the social, material, and technological elements of dynamic, evolving contexts (West et al, 2020).

In constituting relational ways of knowing the multiple and complex realities with more humility, sci-art projects that are covered above bring forward a differentiated relational ontology. Understanding the interdependent relations between social and ecological systems without dichotomising or subsuming one into the other, what Plumwood calls the relationship of non-hierarchical concept of difference (Plumwood, 1993:60), entails recognising what has been backgrounded and acknowledging dependency, respecting the value and needs of others, and recognizing the complexity and diversity of those historically excluded. For example, the project *These Relations are Forever*, uses EDCs as active agents to demonstrate non-hierarchical difference. Their capacity to transgress boundaries, moving through food chains, water bodies, legal frameworks, and human and nonhuman bodies, dissolves clearly defined domains, in which difference does not imply isolation or opposition, but mutual implication and vulnerability. Rather than framing EDCs as external threats to be controlled, the project presents them as evidence of systemic entanglement, inviting reflection on how every action resonates across a web of relations. EDCs here become both a symptom and a troubling teacher of entanglement, co-responsibility, and the call for reimagined relations. In this light, the EU's circular economy can be reimagined as a practice of humility, one that listens across species, disciplines, and forms of knowledge on how value, harm, and care circulate.

Haraway (2016) refers to this caring, attentive commitment, and genuine curiosity for the interconnected needs of others as “response-ability” (Haraway, 2016). Rather than understanding responsibility as a duty imposed on an autonomous subject, she reframes it as something that emerges within relationships. It is the capacity to respond with others, individuals, communities, and the more-than-human world, in mutual

vulnerability and accountability. In *NaturArchy, With Salt and Rocks in Our Veins* performs a speculative engagement with relational response-ability by making visible the ethical entanglements between European green, circular aspirations and the ecological degradation of Chile's Atacama Desert. Rather than viewing materials like lithium as inert inputs in closed-loop systems, the project reanimates them as part of complex, living geographies shaped by histories of colonialism, ecological fragility, and resistance. The work dissolves geographical and perceptual distance, cultivating a space of co-presence through attentiveness, humility, and care, inviting viewers to stay with the trouble of being materially and ethically connected to these extractive processes. In doing so, it reimagines circularity not just as technical closure, but as ethical openness, an attentiveness to the social, ecological, and historical conditions that shape material flows. It challenges extractivist narratives by revealing that circularity and green progress are not straightforward win-win agendas, and that accountability begins in acknowledging and responding to those material and ecological relations.

Politics in Disguise extends the discussion of relational response-ability by staging a speculative political form where more-than-human beings are not only acknowledged but invited into the space of deliberation, rights, and recognition. Through the Parliament of Beings, the project resists instrumental inclusion and instead gestures toward a genuinely relational politics, one that confronts the structural asymmetries that relegate more-than-human life to the category of "the rest". It imagines a world in which nonhuman entities are not spoken for but encountered as co-constituents of shared futures. Yet the work does not avoid the paradoxes inherent in representation, it acknowledges the risks of reproducing anthropocentric hierarchies through well-intentioned second-order advocacy. As Celer Mayer et al. (2020) caution, without structural transformation, second-order forms of inclusion may reinforce existing injustices under the guise of progress. In this light, *Politics in Disguise* becomes a critical and imaginative intervention into CE discourse, showing that cultivating response-ability is not a matter of technical recalibration but of reconfiguring the terms of political engagement. The project underscores the importance of embodied practices, storytelling, and affective connection as vital tools for imagining circular futures rooted not in control or efficiency, but in humility, reciprocity, and care across difference.

The *NaturArchy* sci-art projects offer compelling interventions into CE discourse by foregrounding relational ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics that unsettle dominant techno-managerial paradigms. Rather than positioning circularity as a neutral process of material optimisation, these works illuminate the deeply entangled, uneven, and affective dimensions of human–more-than-human interdependencies. *The sci-art projects* enact forms of relational thinking that challenge reductionist approaches to complexity, inviting more situated, humble, and ethically attuned ways of engaging with socio-ecological systems. They expose the limitations of control-oriented models that obscure uncertainty, externalise harm, and silence historically marginalised perspectives, particularly those of nonhuman beings and communities in the Global South. At the same time, they offer imaginative and performative alternatives: practices of staying with the trouble, cultivating response-ability, and co-creating spaces of political and epistemic inclusion. As this discussion has shown, relational thinking does not promise simple solutions; instead, it reorients the CE as a living, ethical practice, one rooted in attentiveness to complexity, in care across difference, and in the ongoing negotiation of how to live and act together on a damaged, shared planet.

4.8. Conclusion

This study has explored how relational thinking bridges human-nature divides and enhances understandings of complexity knowledge and action within the context of the CE. Through a case study of the NaturArchy sci-art projects, it reflected on how relational approaches challenge reductionist paradigms and foster a more integrated perspective on human-nature interdependencies. It has demonstrated the potential of art-science collaborations to open-up to alternative ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics.

A central contribution of this research lies in illustrating how relational ontologies transcend hierarchical binaries, emphasising the co-constitution of human and non-human actors. The exploration of relational epistemologies underscores the importance of transdisciplinary methods that integrate scientific, artistic, and experiential knowledge. By foregrounding non-human agency and socio-ecological justice, relational ethics within CE point to an ethics of care and response-ability, one that actively recognises the interconnected needs and values of humans and the more-than-human world alike.

Future research can engage with entangled interconnections between relational ontologies, epistemologies and ethics for advancing a relational paradigm of CE. A possible relational CE research agenda can include legal recognition of nature's rights and multispecies justice frameworks; implications of relational ethics such as care and response-ability in CE discourses, practices and policies; and exploration of CE approaches that manifest relational being, thinking, and acting across diverse cultural, institutional, and geographical contexts.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

5.1. Discussion and conclusion

This chapter brings together the empirical and theoretical contributions of the three studies presented in this thesis to engage directly with the overarching research aim: to *repoliticise* the CE by challenging, questioning, and pluralising the circularity narratives to keep it socio-ecologically relevant and credible in the ongoing validity challenge period and to *open up* the critical socio-political debate to support the CE's transformative potential. Through an interpretive lens grounded in discourse and power analysis, the thesis has examined how meanings of the CE are constructed, stabilised, contested, and transformed across different sites of societal debates, policymaking, and institutional practices.

This section synthesises the key insights developed across the thesis to answer four research questions formulated in Chapter 1. It starts from a comparative discussion of the three sub-questions, weaving together theoretical reflections and critical interpretations with strong attention to empirical findings. It then moves to the overarching research question and discusses how this thesis “opens up CE as a site of socio-political reconfiguration”, from the perspectives of discursive opening; epistemic and institutional opening; and ontological and ethical opening.

RQ1: What are the main discourses on the CE in the EU? How can they be critically analysed and understood?

Chapter 2, Contested Discourses of a Circular Plastics Economy in Europe, directly addressed this question by unpacking the dominant and emerging discourses shaping EU CE policy with a case study of the plastics sector. Using argumentative discourse analysis, the study identified three distinct discursive formations: Plastic Fantastic, CE Will Fly Us to the Moon, and Even Plastic Flowers Are Dead in This System. These are not merely rhetorical variations but represent divergent and plural ways of knowing, valuing, and governing the CE. They articulate specific assumptions about the role of growth, the function of innovation, the positioning of actors, and the ontological status of nature (Friant et al, 2020). By mapping these discourses, the thesis highlights how CE narratives are deeply political, even when presented as technocratic or universally beneficial (Schroeder, 2020).

The Plastic Fantastic discourse frames plastics as necessary and manageable through improved consumer behaviour and incremental innovation. Here, industry actors are constructed as responsible and solution-oriented, while governance remains in a supporting position. The Moonshot discourse, largely institutionalised within the EU's CE policy, offers a more systemic framing. It recognises environmental degradation as a structural problem and strongly relies on digitalisation, market innovation, and public-private collaboration as the route to a high-tech, regenerative future (EMF, 2015). Both discourses are anchored in ecological modernisation, assuming that sustainability and economic growth are compatible, and that technological advancement can resolve socio-ecological crises. What unites these two discourses is their depoliticised orientation: they promise win-win outcomes, sidestep questions of power, and avoid addressing the structural drivers of environmental harm (Leipold, 2021). In doing so, they stabilise a vision of the CE as a means to depoliticise environmental governance, maintaining continuity under the guise of transformation.

The third discourse, *Plastic Flowers*, disrupts this consensus. It foregrounds the incommensurability between perpetual economic growth and ecological sustainability, advocating for sufficiency, degrowth, and socio-

ecological justice. This discourse is animated by civil society organisations, critical scholars, and some local government actors, and seeks to politicise CE by challenging its ontological and ethical foundations. For example, rather than treating nature as a resource or service provider, it advances a relational worldview where interdependence, care, and responsibility guide socio-material practices (Rask, 2022). Innovation is understood not as technological efficiency but as social transformation; governance is not about behavioural nudges but about redistributing power and agency (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2021).

The analysis across these three discourses demonstrates that CE is not a neutral, straightforward solution, but a contested political project (Friant et al, 2020). Each discourse constitutes a different vision of what circularity means, how it should be achieved, and who should play which role in it. Critically analysing CE through a discursive lens allows to identify which perspectives are legitimised, which are marginalised, and how these dynamics shape institutional priorities.

This analysis also intersects with the findings of Chapter 4, *In Search of a Relational CE Through Art*. While not focused on discourses per se, that study deepens the critique of dominant CE narratives by showing how they remain anchored in modernist, reductionist, and dualist assumptions, particularly about complexity and human-nature relations. Even as leading CE actors (such as the Ellen MacArthur Foundation) invoke systems thinking and complexity, their operational strategies tend to repack complexity into manageable categories via quantification, standardisation, and modelling. This mode of governance, what Kovacic et al. (2020) term "reductionist complexity", preserves the illusion of control while reinforcing substantialist assumptions: the separation of humans from nature, facts from values, and reason from emotion.

The analysis in *In Search of a Relational CE* challenges this by introducing relational ontologies, epistemologies, and ethics to pluralise CE debates. It shows how artistic practices can create new spaces of imagination and perception, enabling different ways of knowing and relating (Heras et al, 2021). These relational approaches do not reduce complexity into measurable units but embrace it as an ongoing, embodied, and affective entanglement of human and more-than-human life (West et al, 2024). They call into question the very categories and hierarchies through which dominant CE narratives operate (Rask, 2022).

Taken together, these insights demonstrate that the CE is subject to debate not only regarding its policy objectives and implementation tools but also in terms of how its meaning is constructed and how it shapes visions of the world. Discourses shape how problems are perceived, who is seen as responsible, and what futures are rendered possible. Through critical discourse analysis, this thesis has shown how the dominant framings of the CE in the EU foreground technological innovation, market mechanisms, and industrial leadership while marginalising more radical visions rooted in justice, care, and post-growth ethics.

Understanding CE discourses, therefore, is not an academic exercise in classification. It reveals how power operates through language, how governance is structured by assumptions, and how imaginaries of sustainability are shaped by who gets to speak, what is considered rational, and what is rendered invisible. Opening up these discursive dynamics is a step towards repoliticising the CE and reclaiming it as a space of plural futures.

RQ2: How do certain interpretations of the CE become dominant, and why?

The second research question addresses the mechanisms through which particular CE interpretations consolidate authority and become institutionalised, while others remain marginal or are actively excluded. This question was explored in depth in *Packaged Science? Incumbent strategies of science capture from a power perspective*, which offers a multi-dimensional analysis of how discursive dominance is produced, not simply through rhetorical force or policy alignment, but through the interplay of epistemic authority, institutional access, strategic positioning, and multiple forms of power (Stirling, 2018). In this study, dominance is shown to be not the result of neutral consensus or scientific validation, but the outcome of active processes of discursive closure.

Chapter 4 identifies strategies deployed by incumbent actors to maintain control over the scope and trajectory of CE debates. The chapter offers a compelling investigation into science capture as a mechanism for stabilising dominant CE interpretations. Through the case of the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), the study documents how industry actors such as fast-food companies and packaging alliances mobilise epistemic, institutional, and political strategies to shape the regulatory process in their favour. This includes contesting unfavourable evidence, producing and promoting alternative LCAs, embedding themselves in technical standard-setting bodies, and strategically aligning with EU-level policy narratives such as “innovation” and “Better Regulation.” These strategies do not merely reflect sectoral self-interest; they reveal a deeper logic of depoliticised governance, in which conflict is displaced by technocratic consensus, and structural questions are rearticulated as behavioural or managerial challenges (Saltelli et al, 2023).

These moves enable powerful actors not only to influence outcomes but to control the boundaries of what counts as credible knowledge and legitimate expertise (Kovacic et al, 2020). The dominant CE interpretations that emerge from these processes are framed in the language of innovation and feasibility. They are supported by quantifiable models, economic projections, and technical standards that convey objectivity and neutrality (Madelin, 2015). However, these instruments of governance, while appearing apolitical, are often used to frame the CE in ways that align with incumbent interests and marginalise more systemic or justice-based alternatives (Saltelli et al, 2023). This is especially clear in the case of single-use LCAs, which are repeatedly used to discredit proposals that challenge business-as-usual, even as they claim scientific rigour.

The thesis draws on Lukes’ (2005) three-dimensional view of power to make a deeper sense of these dynamics. In the visible dimension, actors participate in formal decision-making and public debates. In the hidden dimension, powerful actors set agendas, define terms, and determine what issues are brought to the table. And in the invisible dimension, dominant interpretations become naturalised through discourse and institutional design, shaping perceptions and preferences in ways that obscure conflict and contingency. CE governance in the EU increasingly reflects this third form of power: it presents circularity as a technical problem requiring expert input and scalable solutions, while excluding more radical critiques that question growth, challenge industry narratives, or call for redistribution of resources and power (Corvellec et al, 2021).

Chapter 3 also reveals how power operates pre-emptively, through upstream shaping of the policy environment. Actors not only respond to regulation but also shape the epistemic terrain on which regulatory battles are fought (Legg et al, 2021). By influencing the generation of evidence, the definition of standards,

and the design of stakeholder consultations, they create a policy architecture that favours certain solutions (typically efficiency-oriented, business-compatible ones) while foreclosing others. This form of pre-emptive power constructs the field of acceptable change in advance through knowledge production and strategic alignment (Glover and Muller, 2015).

Importantly, this study highlights how time and pace are also used as instruments of control. Delaying regulation, demanding further studies, or reframing proposals as premature are all strategies for managing the pace and direction of change (Mah, 2021). These "slow-down" tactics operate in tandem with discursive closure to preserve the legitimacy of existing systems while giving the appearance of adaptation. In doing so, they reinforce what Stirling (2019) terms "deep incumbency": a condition in which structural asymmetries in knowledge, resources, and access are reproduced even as new narratives of transformation emerge.

This paper demonstrate that dominance in the CE is not a passive state, but an actively produced outcome. It is not merely a matter of persuasive narratives or superior models, but the result of strategic interventions that shape who participates, whose knowledge is accepted, and which futures are rendered possible (Legg et al, 2021). Dominant CE interpretations succeed not because they are inherently more robust, but because they are better positioned within institutional architectures, epistemic networks, and policy cultures that privilege technocratic authority and industrial legitimacy.

These mechanisms are further illuminated when viewed in light of the discourses analysed in Chapter 2. The institutionalisation of the Moonshot discourse, characterised by its optimistic, data-driven, and high-tech vision of CE, is not simply the product of resonance with EU policy goals, but the result of concerted efforts by industry, consultants, and aligned policymakers to make this discourse appear both necessary and inevitable (Kowarsch and Edenhofer, 2015). Meanwhile, more critical discourses such as Plastic Flowers, which propose fundamentally different understandings of circularity rooted in care, sufficiency, and justice, are sidelined not only by a lack of institutional support but by structural exclusions embedded in how knowledge is governed.

Dominance, then, can be better understood as the outcome of discursive, epistemic, and institutional alignments, sustained by power asymmetries that are both visible, invisible, and hidden. In the case of CE, certain interpretations become hegemonic through their ability to articulate a coherent narrative of progress that appeals to policymakers, accommodates incumbent business models, and marginalises structural critique. Revealing these dynamics contributes to imagining and constructing circular futures that are not only materially restorative but also politically transformative.

RQ3: What are the alternatives to dominant approaches to CE? Specifically, how can relational thinking inspire alternative forms of CE?

The third research question turns to the possibilities for reimagining CE practices beyond the dominant models critiqued in earlier chapters. While mainstream CE approaches in the EU continue to emphasise technological optimisation, market efficiency, and incremental innovation, this research shows that there are alternative imaginaries, both in discourse and in practice, that challenge these foundations. Chapter 4, *In Search of a Relational CE Through Art*, provides an entry point into this exploration. It offers a critical departure from the technocratic rationalities of dominant CE narratives and opens up a different ontological, epistemological, and ethical terrain for interpreting circularity.

At the heart of this alternative vision is a relational paradigm. Whereas dominant CE framings rest on substantialist assumptions, treating the world as composed of discrete, manageable entities linked by linearity, relational approaches start from the premise that relations precede entities (West et al, 2024). In this view, systems are not defined by their parts but by the dynamic processes and interdependencies that constitute them. This ontological shift fundamentally reorients how circularity is understood. Rather than focusing on flows of materials or efficiency gains, a relational CE asks how humans and more-than-human beings are mutually constituted through ongoing, entangled relationships, and how these relationships can be reconfigured to support care, justice, and ecological integrity (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2025).

The relational approach developed in the third study does not remain abstract. It is grounded in the NaturArchy project, a sci-art initiative by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre, which brought together artists and scientists to engage with the theme of nature's rights. Through a series of experimental, collaborative practices, NaturArchy enabled alternative ways of sensing, knowing, and imagining human-nature relations, ways that resist instrumentalisation and instead foreground embodiment, affect, and empathy (Moriggi et al, 2020). Artistic practices function as epistemological and ontological interventions, opening space for new modes of knowing and being (Vervoort et al, 2024). The thesis explored three interrelated dimensions of relational alternatives. First, a relational ontology challenges the modernist dichotomies that underpin dominant CE framings—nature/culture, human/non-human, subject/object. By disrupting these binaries, it unsettles the control-oriented logics that treat nature as a passive resource and the economy as a separate sphere of management. In the NaturArchy projects, nature is not externalised or abstracted but is made present as a co-constitutive actor. For example, installations and performances worked with soil, chemicals, mushrooms, and water to evoke more-than-human agencies and to invite participants into multisensory encounters with ecological processes. These moments of experiential entanglement prompt a reconsideration of who and what matters in CE transitions, and what it means to act responsibly within them (Ashton et al, 2022).

Second, a relational epistemology contests the dominance of quantification, modelling, and standardisation in CE governance. It embraces diverse ways of knowing, including artistic, emotional, embodied, and indigenous knowledges, as essential to making sense of complexity (Moore and Milkoreit, 2020). Rather than seeking to simplify or render legible, relational epistemologies welcome ambiguity, contradiction, and emergence. In contrast to the reductionist use of complexity in mainstream CE (as discussed in Chapter 4), the relational approach sees complexity not as a problem to be tamed but as a condition of life to be engaged with attentively and humbly (West et al, 2024). Art becomes a practice of cultivating this attentiveness, of revealing hidden entanglements, surfacing neglected values, and expanding the horizon of possible futures (Vervoort et al, 2024).

Third, relational ethics reorients the normative basis of CE from efficiency and optimisation to care, reciprocity, and justice. It challenges anthropocentrism and instrumental rationality by recognising the agency and value of more-than-human beings and systems (Walsh et al, 2021). This ethical turn is not limited to abstract moral claims; it is grounded in practices of attentiveness, relational response-ability, and situated knowledge. The NaturArchy initiative illustrates how such ethics can be enacted through shared inquiry, creative experimentation, and collective reflection. These practices foster a sense of mutual vulnerability and interdependence that is largely absent from dominant CE framings.

Crucially, this relational approach does not simply offer a new model to be implemented; it opens up a different orientation toward transformation itself. It resists the blueprint logic of CE roadmaps and instead embraces transformation as a cultural, ontological, and political process (Stirling, 2008). It calls for reclaiming imagination as a political act, not to escape reality, but to see it otherwise, and to prefigure alternatives within the present (Moore and Milkoreit, 2020). Beyond the NaturArchy project, elements of this alternative CE imaginary resonate with the Plastic Flowers discourse analysed in Chapter 2. Both reject the premise that circularity can be achieved without confronting the growth imperative and the structural inequalities it reproduces. Both foreground sufficiency, justice, and ecological care as central to the transition. However, the relational CE goes further in challenging the epistemic and ontological underpinnings of modern environmental governance. It offers not just different goals, but a different pathway for thinking, knowing, and acting (Walsh et al, 2021).

While these alternatives remain marginal within the EU policy context, their value lies in their capacity to disrupt hegemonic assumptions and open new trajectories. They show that the CE is not a settled space, but a contested and evolving one. They expose the limits of dominant approaches and create room for experimenting with different ways of being, knowing, and relating. In doing so, they perform the critical work of re-politicising the present and the future, making visible the choices, conflicts, and possibilities that dominant framings seek to contain.

The alternatives explored in this thesis are not unified or prescriptive. They are diverse, emergent, and often experimental. What they share is a commitment to challenging the foundational assumptions of dominant CE governance and to cultivating more inclusive, responsive, and ethical pathways. Their contribution is not only to critique what is, but to imagine and enact what else could be. Following up on this, the next part discusses the overarching research question of the thesis.

ORQ: How can the circular economy be opened up as a site of socio-political reconfiguration?

This thesis builds on the critique that while the CE is often presented as a transformative agenda, its dominant articulation within EU policy remains deeply embedded in a depoliticised, technocratic, and eco-modernist framework (Friant, 2021). This iteration of the CE prioritises market mechanisms, techno-managerial solutions, and a win-win narrative that obscures structural inequalities, marginalises contested knowledge, and displaces complex socio-political dynamics (Leipold, 2021). Such an approach risks reinforcing the very injustices it purports to resolve, failing to confront the deeper transformations necessary for a just and sustainable transition (Ashton, 2022). Recognising these limitations, this thesis embraces a critical perspective that seeks to re-politicise the CE not merely by critiquing its limitations, but by actively opening up space for alternative discourses, epistemologies, and socio-ecological futures. It opens up this re-configuration from three perspectives: discursive opening, epistemic and institutional opening, and ontological and ethical opening, discussed in detail below.

1. Discursive opening

This thesis studies discursive opening in two interlinked layers, revealing the CE as a deeply contested field, shaped not only by divergent policy aims and practical measures but also by competing meanings and world-making visions. In doing so, it expands circularity into a plural arena of knowledge, values, and power relations.

a. Revealing the contested nature of CE

This thesis shows diverging interpretations of the CE are not neutral or isolated but are shaped by broader institutional settings, political systems, and socio-cultural imaginaries (Calisto Friant, 2022; Mah, 2021; Zwiers, Jaeger-Erben, & Hofmann, 2020). Each CE initiative, whether a policy, practice, or intervention, is embedded within these wider structures and reflects distinct assumptions about socio-ecological transformation and societal organisation. These underlying visions influence not only the rationale and objectives of circular transitions but also the governance models and technological solutions they promote. As such, CE configurations can either amplify or marginalise particular agendas and actors, depending on what/who is included in decision-making processes and how (Ashton et al, 2022). Recognising this, the thesis approaches CE as a complex political and social construct, whose meanings and implications must be critically examined in relation to the power dynamics, institutional arrangements, and value systems that shape its implementation.

b. Discursive pluralisation

In the second layer, the discursive opening is approached as pluralisation, expanding the space of the CE to allow multiple, coexisting ways of knowing, valuing, and imagining circularity. Rather than seeking a singular, unitary definition against contestation, it embraces ontological, epistemic, and ethical diversity (Friant, 2024). It resists premature closure around “optimal” solutions and instead acknowledges the multiplicity of values at stake, such as justice, care, sufficiency, and resilience. It invites openness to diverse pathways, enabling more inclusive, adaptive, and democratically accountable forms of governance. Ultimately, discursive pluralisation transforms the CE from a fixed policy tool into a dynamic and contested socio-political arena for reimagining transitions (Bauwens et al, 2020).

II. Epistemic and institutional opening

This thesis examined epistemic and institutional opening through four interrelated layers, each revealing distinct but interconnected mechanisms by which dominant policy paradigms may be contested and transformed.

a. Re-politicising expertise in political decision-making mechanisms

The thesis problematises the tendency to frame complex socio-ecological challenges as matters of objective expertise, thereby masking their inherently political character. It demonstrates how these framings limit democratic deliberation and reinforce technocratic authority. It recognises that what counts as legitimate knowledge is always influenced by specific contexts and necessarily involves a distinction between what is included in its construction and what is left out (Goeminne, 2012). The research argues that the legitimacy of scientific knowledge should be situated within broader deliberative processes, acknowledging the political judgments and societal values that shape evidence-based policymaking in the EU (Madelin, 2015).

b. Deconstructing techno-scientific closure in policy infrastructure

A second layer involved the critical deconstruction of the epistemic infrastructures that sustain techno-scientific closure. The thesis analyses the reliance on quantitative impact assessment practices within EU policymaking for standardisation and calculable certainty (Kovacic et al, 2020). These assessments do not

merely evaluate policy options objectively; they actively define what is understood as rational, feasible, or legitimate. Relying on a neoclassical toolkit, policy options are filtered through a single growth-centred paradigm, excluding alternative economic logics, such as sufficiency or degrowth, systematically from consideration (Saltelli et al, 2023). By illuminating how these methods reinforce a growth-oriented, techno-modernist paradigm, this research brings structural analysis into how EU policy infrastructures marginalise transformative visions and foreclose epistemic diversity at the decision-making mechanisms.

c. One step further, towards deep incumbency

The third layer of analysis situates epistemic configurations within wider socio-political contexts. The thesis shows that CE policy trajectories are stabilised not simply by technical impact assessments but by entrenched dynamics of social, economic, cultural, political, and discursive dynamics (i.e. linear narratives of circular innovations to promote competitiveness and create jobs) (Johnstone et al, 2017). These deep incumbency structures operate across multiple domains, reproducing regime stability through diffuse and entangled networks of actors, norms, and practices (Stirling, 2019). The findings suggest that incumbent resistance is not incidental to policy failure but is a constitutive feature of existing configurations, one that requires deliberate, systemic destabilisation for meaningful change to occur.

d. Exploring arts-based approaches for epistemic opening

The fourth layer explored how arts-based approaches can serve as powerful instruments of epistemic opening within CE discourses, practices, policy, and governance. The thesis examined how these approaches expand the modes of knowing available in circularity contexts, enabling sensory, emotional, embodied, and imaginative engagements with complex socio-ecological challenges (Vervoort et al, 2024). Where dominant scientific framings constrain what is considered knowable or actionable, the arts create space for alternative epistemologies and value systems. By foregrounding experiential, situated, and affective knowledge, these approaches open up new cognitive and normative possibilities for engaging with circularity, inviting more inclusive and reflexive forms of governance (Moore and Milkoreit, 2020).

III. Ontological and ethical opening

This thesis explored ontological and ethical opening through two interrelated layers, focusing on the relational processes through which care is enacted across entangled human and more-than-human worlds. These layers examine how mutual dependencies are sustained, vulnerabilities acknowledged, and ethical responsibilities are shared within socio-ecological systems.

a. Circular Economy as a relational challenge

The first layer reconceptualises the CE as fundamentally a relational challenge (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2025). It highlights the deep entanglements among social, material, and ecological cycles, which intersect, influence, and reshape one another in dynamic and ongoing ways. This perspective calls for a shift from mechanistic views of CE to ones that centre relationships between stakeholders, artefacts, and ecological systems (West et al, 2020). This framing encourages practitioners and policymakers to move beyond instrumental, extractive logics towards more reciprocal and restorative engagements with both human and more-than-humans: engagements that foster collaboration, attend to care, and address socio-ecological injustices embedded in society–nature relations (Jaeger-Erben et al, 2025).

b. Towards more-than-human care

The second layer extends the ontological and ethical opening to positioning more-than-humans as active agents in CE with their ability to affect and be affected by circular policies, priorities, and practices. It adopts an expansive and relationally attuned ethics of care in CE, one that takes seriously the needs, vulnerabilities, and agency of more-than-human entities (Plumwood, 1993). It opens up to Haraway's concept of *response-ability* as a critical lens through which to understand care not as a unidirectional act but as a co-constitutive and situated practice. In this view, beings do not simply provide or receive care, they become-with one another through acts of mutual responsiveness (Haraway, 2016). This relational ethic dissolves fixed boundaries between caregiver and care-receiver, emphasising entangled agency and shared vulnerability across species, bodies, ecologies and geographies. It also foregrounds relationality across both spatial and temporal dimensions (Moriggi et al, 2020): care is not confined to those nearby but extends to distant others, including vulnerable communities in the Global South and future generations, bringing the socio-ecological injustice impacts of dominant CE policy and practices to the heart of the critique. In this framing, ethical responsibility is not defined by proximity or immediacy but by an attentiveness to the complex and distributed webs of relation that sustain life, naturally inviting a justice-centred CE in the EU.

5.2. Theoretical contributions

This thesis makes a significant contribution to CE literature in four ways.

First, it foregrounds discourse and power as central to understanding the CE, rather than treating it as a self-evident policy framework or technological paradigm. In doing so, it challenges the dominant framing of the CE and instead positions it as a politically contested project. By applying an argumentative discourse analysis approach to CE policy in the EU, the research moves beyond descriptive accounts of CE strategies to examine the structuring assumptions, narrative logics, and epistemic hierarchies embedded within competing discourses.

Second, the thesis brings a more nuanced and critical approach to the role and agency given to incumbent actors in advancing the CE transition. Building on the sustainability transitions literature, it offers insights on how incumbent actors, while capable of driving change, can also impede progress by leveraging their resources, networks, and influence. It shows how these groups adopt fluid and strategic responses to social, economic, environmental, and political pressures, exercising visible, hidden and invisible power.

Third, beyond challenging the dominant CE approaches, it brings a structural analysis of why CE fails to realise its transformative potential. Rather than locating failure in implementation gaps or technical shortcomings, this analysis foregrounds deeper structural forces, discursive, institutional, epistemic, and political, that shape the parameters of what circularity can become in practice. Through this lens, it conceptualises CE as not simply a neutral or progressive policy instrument, but a terrain of contestation that is being actively shaped and constrained by the broader socio-political systems in which it is embedded.

Fourth, this thesis represents one of the earliest contributions to the emerging field of relational circularity and more-than-human agency. It expands relational sustainability studies by integrating ontological, epistemological, and ethical insights from diverse relational perspectives. By introducing relational thinking

into CE debates, the work offers a novel conceptual vocabulary for reimagining circularity as a matter of care, response-ability, entanglement, and mutual becoming. It conceptualises care through mutual interdependence, non-hierarchical difference, and reciprocal responsiveness among humans, between humans and more-than-humans, and across all forms of life and matter. This ontological and ethical reframing positions care as a collective, temporally expansive practice, challenging dominant assumptions of separability and instrumentalism, advocating for ecologically embedded and relationally accountable ways of living.

5.3. Empirical contributions

This thesis advances CE research not only through theoretical contributions but also by generating original empirical contributions. Two novel contributions from Chapters 3 and 4 are brought to light below.

The first empirical contribution emerges from a detailed, real-time study of the PPWR revision process as it unfolded between late 2022 and mid-2024. Unlike the majority of policy analyses that are conducted retrospectively, this study adopted a “transitions in the making” approach to capture the ongoing negotiations, conflicts, and reconfigurations that characterised a live EU legislative file. This temporal positioning allowed to track not only outcomes but the formation and contestation of problem framings, evidentiary claims, and institutional strategies as they occurred.

The study makes a significant empirical contribution by demonstrating how discursive and epistemic closures are actively produced and maintained within CE policy infrastructures. Specifically, it provided concrete evidence on science capture, addressing the use of science in the regulatory process to preserve market-compatible interpretations of circularity while foreclosing more sufficiency-oriented alternatives. The PPWR case thus offers a detailed, evidence-based account of how systemic constraints operate within EU governance structures.

The second empirical contribution is based on an in-depth study of NaturArchy, an experimental art-science residency programme hosted by the JRC’s SciArt project. The selection of NaturArchy as a case study was guided by its unique position: while institutionally embedded in the EC, it actively experimented with alternative ontologies, more-than-human ethics, and relational understandings of nature, topics that remain marginal within dominant CE discourse in the EU. This case contributes empirically by documenting how an art-sci project can function as a site of epistemic and ontological opening, facilitating reflection, learning, and engagement with plural, relational, and care-based imaginaries, as well as unlearning or questioning the dominant institutional culture within the EC.

5.4. Implications for policy and governance

The findings of this thesis carry important implications for policymakers, practitioners, and institutions involved in CE governance. First and foremost, the research challenges the assumption that the CE can be implemented through technical coordination and stakeholder consensus. While dominant framings tend to foreground collaboration and win-win solutions, this thesis demonstrates that the CE is a field of conflict and inequality, where different actors hold fundamentally divergent understandings of what sustainability means, what futures are possible, and who should lead the transition.

Recognising the CE as a depoliticised project allows for a reassessment of governance processes. Institutional reliance on standardised consultations, quantitative modelling, and techno-managerial instruments may create an appearance of neutrality, but they often obscure the power dynamics that shape whose voices are heard, whose knowledge is valued, and which pathways are funded and pursued. A more reflexive and inclusive approach to CE policymaking would require expanding the space for alternative knowledges and marginalised actors, including civil society, grassroots initiatives, and artistic or indigenous epistemologies.

This thesis also argues for a wider definition of innovation in CE governance. Innovation is often confined to technological advancement and circular business models. Yet the alternatives explored in this research demonstrate that social, institutional, and cultural innovations, such as community repair networks, relational ethics, and artistic experimentation, are equally vital for reconfiguring our relationships with materials, systems, and each other. A narrow focus on scalable technological solutions risks reinforcing existing inequalities and ecological harm, while missing the transformative potential of small-scale, situated practices.

The research suggests that policy instruments and evaluation frameworks should strive to account for complexity in more nuanced and non-reductive ways. The widespread use of tools like life-cycle assessments and cost-benefit analyses tends to prioritise quantifiable impacts and short-term efficiencies, often at the expense of justice, care, and long-term socio-ecological flourishing. Governance must be capable of holding space for uncertainty, ambiguity, and multiple value systems, especially when dealing with the deep transformations CE ostensibly aims to initiate.

What is important to note is that the research raises important questions about the legitimacy and direction of current CE agendas, but translating those critiques into actionable recommendations is challenging, especially within institutions invested in stability and consensus. The thesis does not resolve these tensions but embraces them as part of the broader challenge of doing engaged, critical research in the field.

5.5. Limitations and directions for future research

Building on the reflections and the discussion above, and considering the limitations of this thesis, I suggest several promising directions for future research.

First, this thesis only covers the EU CE discussions, policies and practice, which is a relatively well-studied geography in the field. Future studies can explore how the CE is discursively constructed and politically contested across different geographies, sectors, and governance levels. This would provide a rich and comprehensive picture of how dominant and alternative framings travel, evolve, or are resisted in diverse contexts. For example, how does CE governance unfold in Global South contexts? How do histories of colonialism and extractivism intersect with circularity in complex ways?

Second, there is scope to expand methodological experimentation in CE research. This thesis demonstrated the value of discourse analysis and interpretive inquiry, but further work could combine these with ethnographic, participatory, or practice-based methods. Engaging directly with CE practitioners, artists, or activist groups through co-research and co-design could generate more situated and transformative insights. This thesis studies art-based methods and their potential for opening up alternative ways of being, knowing, and relating, but it does not use art-based methods itself. Future research can apply art and creative methods

to plural imaginaries and nurture speculative thinking on what CE reconfigurations can entail. Alternatively, combining qualitative and quantitative methods can enrich the findings. For example, employing a longitudinal social network analysis in the discourse coalitions could bring interesting insights into how the positioning of the actors changes in relation to different policy proposals.

Finally, this thesis only engages with relational approaches in a first step. Future research could further explore the relational circularities. This includes investigating how care, interdependence, and post-anthropocentric ethics can be embedded in material practices, institutional design, and policy processes. Such work could draw on feminist political ecology, decolonial theory, or speculative design to open up the space for imagining and enacting circular futures. What would a response-able CE look like? How can more-than-human perspectives be taken into account in EU CE agendas?

References

- Acaroglu, L (2013). 'Paper beats plastic? How to rethink environmental folklore'. TED2013 retrieved from: https://www.ted.com/talks/leyla_acaroglu_paper_beats_plastic_how_to_rethink_environmental_folklore%3Flanguag e%3Den
- Ashton, WS, Fratini CF, Isenhour C, Krueger R (2022). Justice, Equity, Circular Economy: Introduction to the Double Special Issue, Local Environment, The International Journal of Justice and Sustainability, Volume 27, 2022 - Issue 10-11
- Ampe K, Paredis E, Asveld L, Osseweijer P, Block T (2019). 'A transition in the Dutch wastewater system? The struggle between discourses and with lock-ins a transition in the Dutch wastewater system?' *Environ Policy Plan* 22:155–169.
- Ampe, K., Paredis, E., Asveld, L., Osseweijer, P., & Block, T. (2021). Power struggles in policy feedback processes: Incremental steps towards a circular economy within Dutch wastewater policy. *Policy Sciences*, 54, 579–607.
- Arora, Saurabh (2019) 'Admitting Uncertainty, Transforming Engagement: Towards Caring Practices for Sustainability beyond Climate Change'. *Regional Environmental Change* 19, no. 6 (August 2019): 1571–84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-019-01528-1>.
- Arora, Saurabh, Barbara Van Dyck, Divya Sharma, and Andy Stirling (2020) 'Control, Care, and Conviviality in the Politics of Technology for Sustainability'. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy* 16, no. 1 (10 December 2020): 247–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2020.1816687>.
- Arts, B., & Buizer, M. (2009). Forests, discourses, institutions: A discursive-institutional analysis of global forest governance. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 11(5-6), 340–347.
- Avelino, F. (2017). Power in Sustainability Transitions: Analysing power and (dis)empowerment in transformative change towards sustainability. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 27(6), 505–520. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1777>
- Avelino, F., & Wittmayer, J. M. (2016). Shifting power relations in sustainability transitions: A multi-actor perspective. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 18(5), 628–649.
- Avelino, F., Rotmans, J. (2009) Power in Transition: An Interdisciplinary Framework to Study Power in Relation to Structural Change, *European Journal of Social Theory*, Volume 12, Issue 4. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368431009349830>
- Banner, J. (2023) No silver bullet: Ensuring the right packaging solutions for Europe. Politico, Op-ed. [No silver bullet: Ensuring the right packaging solutions for Europe – POLITICO](#)
- Bauer, F. and Fontenit, G (2021). 'Plastic Dinosaurs – Digging Deep into the Accelerating Carbon Lock-in of Plastics'. *Energy Policy* 156: 112418.

Bauwens, T (2021). 'Are the circular economy and economic growth compatible? A case for post-growth circularity'. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* Volume 175:105852.

Bauwens, T, Hekkert, M and Kirchherr, J (2020). 'Circular Futures: What will they look like?' *Ecological Economics*, volume 175:106703.

Berghofer, U, Rode J, Jax K, Forster J, Berghofer A and Wittmer H (2022). 'Societal Relationships with Nature': A framework for understanding nature-related conflicts and multiple values'. *People and Nature*, 4/2:534-548.

Biggs, Reinette, Rika Preiser, Alta De Vos, Maja Schlüter, Kristine Maciejewski, and Hayley Clements (2021) *The Routledge Handbook of Research Methods for Social-Ecological Systems*. 1st ed. London: Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003021339>.

Blaikie, N. (2010). *Designing Social Research: The Logic of Anticipation*. Polity Press.

Brisbois, M.C. (2019) Powershifts: A framework for assessing the growing impact of decentralized ownership of energy transitions on political decision-making, *Energy Research & Social Science*, Volume 50, 151-161.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.12.003>

BusinessEurope (2023) Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation- a BusinessEurope position paper
<https://www.besuisseurope.eu/publications/packaging-and-packaging-waste-regulation-besuisseurope-position-paper>

Cacciatori, C., Mariani, G., Carollo, A., Tavazzi, S., Elelman, R., Glowacka, N., Sullivan, T., Casado Poblador, T. and Gawlik, B., (2023) The gems of water - How to become a gem of water, EUR 31486 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-68-02653-3, doi:10.2760/334925, JRC133408.

Calisto Friant, M., Walter J.V.V and Roberta, S. (2020). 'A Typology of Circular Economy Discourses: Navigating the Diverse Visions of a Contested Paradigm'. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 161:104917.

Calisto Friant, Martin, and John Langmore (2015). 'The Buen Vivir : A Policy to Survive the Anthropocene?' *Global Policy* 6, no. 1:64–71. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.12187>.

Canfin, P. (2023) Pollution plastique: emballer n'est pas jouer. *Liberation*. https://www.liberation.fr/idees-et-debats/tribunes/pollution-plastique-emballer-nest-pas-jouer-20231017_EUJ24BNLDFE0XMLGIBECTHP24M/

Carbon Tracker (2020). 'The Future's Not in Plastics: Why plastics demand won't rescue the oil sector' available at: <https://www.carbontracker.com/insights/the-future-is-not-in-plastics>. The Future's Not in Plastics - Carbon Tracker Initiative.

Carlile, C. (2023) McDonald's at centre of lobbying blitz against EU packaging waste laws. *EUobserver*
<https://euobserver.com/health-and-society/157006>

Carpenter, D. P., & Moss, D. A. (2013). *Preventing regulatory capture: special interest influence and how to limit it*, Cambridge University Press

Catton, W.R., 1980. *Overshoot : the ecological basis of revolutionary change*. University of Illinois Press, Urbana and Chicago

Celermajer, Danielle, David Schlosberg, Lauren Rickards, Makere Stewart-Harawira, Mathias Thaler, Petra Tschakert, Blanche Verlie, and Christine Winter (2021). 'Multispecies Justice: Theories, Challenges, and a Research Agenda for Environmental Politics'. *Environmental Politics* 30, no. 1–2: 119–40.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2020.1827608>.

Chertow, M.R., 2000. Industrial symbiosis: Literature and taxonomy. *Annu. Rev. Energy Environ.* 25, 313–337.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.25.1.313>

Circle Economy (2023) *The Circularity Gap Report* <https://www.circularity-gap.world/2023>

Corvellec, H. Stowell, AF. Johansson, N (2021) Critiques of the circular economy. *Journal of Industrial Ecology* 2021;1–12.

Dryzek JS (1997). 'The politics of the earth: environmental discourses'. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Dryzek, J. S. (2005). *The Politics of the Earth: Environmental Discourses*. Oxford University Press.

Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2016). 'The New Plastics Economy: Rethinking the Future of Plastics' available at: The New Plastics Economy: Rethinking the future of plastics (ellenmacarthurfoundation.org)

Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2020). 'Upstream Innovation: A guide to packaging solutions' available at: <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/upstream-innovation/overview>

Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2013). *Towards the Circular Economy: Economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition*.

EMF (2019) Systems and the Circular Economy – Deep Dive <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/systems-and-the-circular-economy-deep-dive>

European Commission (2018). 'A European strategy for plastics in a circular economy' available at: [Plastics strategy \(europa.eu\)](http://europa.eu)

European Commission (2020). 'A new circular economy action plan for a cleaner and more competitive Europe' available at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

European Commission (EC) (2018) Communication from the Commission: A renewed European Agenda for Research and Innovation - Europe's chance to shape its future (The European Commission's contribution to the Informal EU Leaders' meeting on innovation in Sofia on 16 May 2018) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0306>

European Commission (EC) (2020) Communication and roadmap on the European Green Deal https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

European Commission (EC) (2021) Better Regulation Guidelines
https://commission.europa.eu/document/d0bbd77f-bee5-4ee5-b5c4-6110c7605476_en

European Commission (EC) (2022a) Proposal for a revision of EU legislation on Packaging and Packaging Waste
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-packaging-and-packaging-waste_en

European Commission (EC) (2022b) The Innovation Principle, factsheet https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/law-and-regulations/ensuring-eu-legislation-supports-innovation_en

European Commission (EC) (2022c) Commission Staff Working Document, Impact Assessment Report (Accompanying Document) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on packaging and packaging waste, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020, and repealing Directive 94/62/EC <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022SC0384>

European Commission (EC) (2023), ed. The Art + Science + Policy Nexus. Luxembourg: Publications Office.
<https://doi.org/10.2760/001452>.

European Court of Auditors (ECA) (2023) *Circular economy – Slow transition by member states despite EU action*
<https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2023-17>

European Environment Agency (2021). 'Growth without economic growth' available at:
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/growth-without-economic-growth/growth-without-economic-growth>

European Environmental Bureau (EEB) (2023) FAQ packaging regulation: Sorting through the trash talk
<https://eeb.org/library/faq-packaging-regulation-sorting-through-the-trash-talk/>

European Paper Packaging Alliance (EPPA) (2023) Letter to MEP Pascal Canfin, accessed from
https://www.politico.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/23/Letter-to-MEP-Canfin_2010202386.pdf

European Paper Packaging Alliance (EPPA) (2022) Commission takes more time to listen to the science on PPWD revision <https://eppa-eu.org/commission-takes-more-time-to-listen-to-the-science-on-ppwd-revision/>

European Regulation & Innovation Forum (ERIF) (2022) Innovation, Essentiality and Better Regulation
<https://www.eriforum.eu/publications.html>

European Regulation & Innovation Forum (ERIF) (2023) Competitiveness, Novel Regulatory Philosophies and Better Regulation <https://www.eriforum.eu/publications.html>

European Risk Forum (ERF) (2013) Communication 12: The Innovation Principle – Letter to the Presidents of the European Commission, The Europe Council, and The European Parliament
<https://www.eriforum.eu/publications.html>

European Risk Forum (ERF) (2013) Innovation and the Regulation of Risk <https://www.eriforum.eu/publications.html>

Eurostat (2023) Packaging Waste Characteristics, EU, 2010-2021 https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Packaging_waste_statistics#Generation_and_recycling_per_inhabitant

FEFCO (2022) Bringing science to the packaging debate <https://www.fefco.org/article-european-files-bringing-science-packaging-debate>

Feindt, P. H., & Oels, A. (2005). Does discourse matter? Discourse analysis in environmental policy making. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 7(3), 161–173.

Fischer, F., & Gottweis, H. (Eds.). (2012). *The Argumentative Turn Revisited: Public Policy as Communicative Practice*. Duke University Press.

Foucault, M (1982). 'The Subject and Power,' *Critical Inquiry* 8, no.4:777–95.

Friant, MC, Vermeulen, WJ, and Salomone, R. (2021). 'Analysing European Union circular economy policies: words versus actions'. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, Volume 27:337-353.

Frosch, R.A., Gallopoulos, N.E., 1989. Strategies for Manufacturing. *Sci. Am.* 261, 144–152.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/scientificamerican0989-144>

GAIA (2019). 'Discarded: Communities on the Frontlines of the Global Plastic Crisis' available at: [Discarded-Report-April-22.pdf](#) (wastetradestories.org)

Gala et al. (2023) Life cycle assessment scientists urge EU policymakers to treat some packaging environmental impact assessments with caution, open letter derived from: <https://eeb.org/library/faq-packaging-regulation-sorting-through-the-trash-talk/>

Garnett, K., Van Calster, G. & Reins, L. (2018) Towards an innovation principle: an industry trump or shortening the odds on environmental protection?, *Law, Innovation and Technology*, 10:1, 1-14, DOI: 10.1080/17579961.2018.1455023

Gaventa, J (2006) Finding the Spaces for Change: A Power Analysis. *IDS Bulletin* Volume 37, Issue 6 p. 23-33.

Geels, F.W. (2014) Regime Resistance against Low-Carbon Transitions: Introducing Politics and Power into the Multi-Level Perspective, *Theory, Culture & Society*, Vol. 31(5) 21–40.

Genovese, A and Pansera, M (2021). 'The Circular Economy at a Crossroads: Technocratic Eco-Modernism or Convivial Technology for Social Revolution?' *Capitalism Nature Socialism*, 32:2, 95-113.

Geyer, R. (2012). Can complexity move UK policy beyond “evidence-based policy making” and the “audit culture”? Applying a “complexity cascade” to education and health policy. *Polit. Stud.*, 60, 20–43. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9248.2011.00903.x

Gillard R, Gouldson A, Paavola J, Van Alstine J. (2016). Transformational responses to climate change: beyond a systems perspective of social change in mitigation and adaptation. *WIREs Clim Change*. 7:251–265. doi:10.1002/wcc.384

Global Health Advocates (GHA) (2018) Industrial competitiveness as 'societal challenge'? Ensuring accountability and societal impact in Horizon Europe <https://www.ghadvocates.eu/industrial-competitiveness-as-societal-challenge-ensuring-accountability-and-societal-impact-in-horizon-europe/>

Global Health Advocates (GHA) (2019) Last chance to safeguard citizen's protection by removing "Innovation Principle" from Horizon Europe <https://www.ghadvocates.eu/last-chance-to-safeguard-citizens-protections-by-removing-innovation-principle-from-horizon-europe/>

Glover, A. Muller JM (2015) Evidence and policy in the European Commission: towards a radical transformation. In: Wilsdon, J., Doubleday, R. (eds) Future directions for scientific advice in Europe, Centre for Science and Policy, Cambridge

Goedkoop, M.J., van Halen, C.J.G., te Riele, H.R.M., Rommens, P.J.M., 1999. Product Service systems, Ecological and Economic Basics. The Hague.

Goeminne, G. (2012) Lost in Translation: Climate Denial and the Return of the Political, Global Environmental Politics, Volume 12, Number 2, May 2012, pp.1-8

Guimarães Pereira, Ângela, and Andrea Saltelli (2017). 'Post-Normal Institutional Identities: Quality Assurance, Reflexivity and Ethos of Care'. Futures 91: 53–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2016.11.009>.

Gullberg, A.T. (2008) Lobbying friends and foes in climate policy: The case of business and environmental interest groups in the European Union, Energy Policy, Volume 36, Issue 8, Pages 2964-2972, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2008.04.016>

Hajer, M (1995). The politics of environmental discourse: ecological modernisation and the policy process. Clarendon Press, Oxford.

Hajer, M. (2006). Doing Discourse Analysis: Coalitions, Practises, Meaning. In M. Van den Brink & T. Metzger (Eds.), Discourse Theory and Method in the Social Sciences (pp. 65–76). Netherlands Graduate School of Urban and Regional Research.

Hajer, M. A. (1995). *The Politics of Environmental Discourse: Ecological Modernization and the Policy Process*. Oxford University Press.

Hajer, M., and Versteeg, W. (2005). 'A Decade of Discourse Analysis of Environmental Politics: Achievements, Challenges, Perspectives'. Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning 7, no.3: 175–84.

Haraway, Donna (2016). Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene. Experimental Futures. Technological Lives, Scientific Arts, Anthropological Voices. Durham London: Duke University Press.

Hardin, G., 1968. The tragedy of the commons. Science 162, 1243–8. <https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.162.3859.1243>

Hartley, K., van Santen, R., Kirchherr, J., 2020. Policies for transitioning towards a circular economy: Expectations from the European Union (EU). *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 155, 104634.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104634>

Héaulmé, C. (2023) Innovation is the key to cutting packaging waste. *EurActiv*, Op-ed
<https://www.euractiv.com/section/agriculture-food/opinion/innovation-is-the-key-to-cutting-packaging-waste/>

Heras, M., D. Galafassi, E. Oteros-Rozas, F. Ravera, L. Berraquero-Díaz, and I. Ruiz-Mallén. 2021. Realising potentials for arts-based sustainability science. *Sustainability Science* 16:1875-1889.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01002-0>

Hertz, Tilman, Maria Mancilla Garcia, and Maja Schlüter (2020). 'From Nouns to Verbs: How Process Ontologies Enhance Our Understanding of Social-ecological Systems Understood as Complex Adaptive Systems'. Edited by Barbara Muraca. *People and Nature* 2, no. 2: 328–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10079>.

Hickel, J., Kallis, G., 2019. Is Green Growth Possible? *New Polit. Econ.* 0, 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13563467.2019.1598964>

Hobson, K., and Lynch, N. (2016). 'Diversifying and De-Growing the Circular Economy: Radical Social Transformation in a Resource-Scarce World'. *Futures* 82:15–25.

Holland, N. (2018) The 'innovation principle' trap: Industries behind risky products push for a backdoor to bypass EU safety rules <https://corporateeurope.org/en/environment/2018/12/innovation-principle-trap>

Inigo, E. A., and V. Blok. 2019. Strengthening the Socio-Ethical Foundations of the Circular Economy: Lessons from Responsible Research and Innovation. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 233: 280–291.
doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.06.053.

Jaeger-Erben, M., Jensen, C., Hofmann, F., Zwiers, J (2021). There is no sustainable circular economy without a circular society. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 168, S.105476.

Jaeger-Erben, M., Bocken, N., Haase LM., Jorgensen, MS., Mosgaard, MA., Mugge, R. (2025) Circular Economy as a relational challenge - The importance of „Relate“, “resonate” and “Responsibilise” as guiding orientations for systemic circular transitions. *Resources, Conversation and Recycling*, Volume 220, 108367.

Jemma Woolmore IMAL Testimonial These Relations are Forever (2024) https://science-art-society.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/video-thumbnails/2024-09/NaturArchy__NaturArchy_These_Relations_are_Forever%20%281%29.mp4

Johnstone, P., Stirling, A., Sovacool, B. (2017) Policy mixes for incumbency: Exploring the destructive recreation of renewable energy, shale gas 'fracking,' and nuclear power in the United Kingdom. *Energy Research & Social Science*, Volume 33, November 2017, Pages 147-162

Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2023). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 221 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 146, 221–232.

- Kirchherr, Julian, Nan-Hua Nadjia Yang, Frederik Schulze-Spüntrup, Maarten J. Heerink, and Kris Hartley. 'Conceptualizing the Circular Economy (Revisited): An Analysis of 221 Definitions'. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 194 (July 2023): 107001. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107001>.
- Köhler, J., Geels, F. W., Kern, F., Markard, J., Onsongo, E., Wieczorek, A., Alkemade, F., Avelino, F., Bergek, A., Boons, F., Fünfschilling, L., Hess, D., Holtz, G., Hyysalo, S., Jenkins, K., Kivimaa, P., Martiskainen, M., McMeekin, A., Mühlemeier, M. S., ... Wells, P. (2019). An agenda for sustainability transitions research: State of the art and future directions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 31, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.01.004>
- Kothari, Ashish, Federico Demaria, and Alberto Acosta. 'Buen Vivir, Degrowth and Ecological Swaraj: Alternatives to Sustainable Development and the Green Economy'. *Development* 57, no. 3–4 (December 2014): 362–75. <https://doi.org/10.1057/dev.2015.24>.
- Kovacic, Z., Strand, R. and Volker, T. (2020). *The Circular Economy in Europe: Critical Perspectives on Policies and Imaginaries*. Routledge Explorations in Sustainability and Governance.
- Kowarsch, M. Edenhofer, O. (2015) Experts as cartographers of policy pathways for Europe. In: Wilsdon, J., Doubleday, R. (eds) *Future directions for scientific advice in Europe*, Centre for Science and Policy, Cambridge
- Latour, B. 2017. *Facing gaia: Eight lectures on the new climatic regime*. Translated by Catherine Porter. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press.
- Laurens, S. (2018) *Lobbyists and Bureaucrats in Brussels: Capitalism's Brokers*. Routledge, New York.
- Lawhon, M., & Murphy, J. T. (2012). Socio-technical regimes and sustainability transitions: Insights from political ecology. *Progress in Human Geography*, 36(3), 354–378.
- Le Lay, E., D'amato, A. (2022) Placing science at the heart of the circular economy. Politico. Op-ed. <https://www.politico.eu/sponsored-content/placing-science-at-the-heart-of-the-circular-economy/>
- Legg, T., Hatchard, J., & Gilmore, A. B. (2021). The Science for Profit Model-How and why corporations influence science and the use of science in policy and practice. *PLoS ONE*, 16(6 June). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253272>
- Leipold, S. (2021). Transforming ecological modernization 'from within' or perpetuating it? The circular economy as EU environmental policy narrative, *Environmental Politics*, 30:6, 1045-1067.
- Leipold et al. (2022). Lessons, narratives and research directions for a sustainable circular economy. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, Volume 27, Issue 1 pp. 6-18
- Leipold, S., & Winkel, G. (2016). Discursive agency: (Re)conceptualizing actors and practices in the analysis of discursive policymaking. *Policy Studies Journal*, 45(3), 510–534.
- Li, W.Y. (2023) Regulatory capture's third face of power *Socio-Economic Review*, 2023, Vol. 21, No. 2, 1217–1245, Oxford University Press <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwad002>

- Liboiron, M. (2021). *Pollution is Colonialism*. Duke University Press.
- Lockwood, M., Mitchell, C., & Hoggett, R. (2020). Incumbent lobbying as a barrier to forward-looking regulation: The case of demand-side response in the GB capacity market for electricity. *Energy Policy*, 140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111426>
- Lukes, S. (2005). *Power: A Radical View*, Second Edition, Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke.
- Madelin, R. (2015) Science as the fuel of the public policy machine. In: Wilsdon, J., Doubleday, R. (eds) *Future directions for scientific advice in Europe*, Centre for Science and Policy, Cambridge
- Magnusson, T., Werner, V. (2022) Conceptualisations of incumbent firms in sustainability transitions: Insights from organisation theory and a systematic literature review, *Business Strategy and the Environment*, Volume 32, Issue 2 p. 903-919, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3081>
- Mah, A. (2021). 'Future-proofing capitalism: the paradox of the circular economy for plastics'. *Global Environmental Politics*, 21/2:1–22.
- Mancilla García, María, Tilman Hertz, Maja Schlüter, Rika Preiser, and Minka Woermann. 'Adopting Process-Relational Perspectives to Tackle the Challenges of Social-Ecological Systems Research'. *Ecology and Society* 25, no. 1 (2020): art29. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-11425-250129>.
- Mathai, M. V., Isenhour, C., Stevis, D., Vergragt, P., Bengtsson, M., Lorek, S., Mortensen, L. F., Coscieme, L., Scott, D., Waheed, A., & Alfredsson, E. (2021). The Political Economy of (Un)Sustainable Production and Consumption: A Multidisciplinary Synthesis for Research and Action. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 167, 105265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105265>
- Meadowcroft, J. (2009) What about the politics? Sustainable development, transition management, and long term energy transitions, *Policy Sci*, 42:323–340, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-009-9097-z>
- Meadows, D., Meadows, DH, Behrens, W., Randers, J., 1972. *The limits to growth: a report for the club of Rome's project on the predicament of mankind*. Universe Books, New York
- Mennicken, A., Salais, R. (2022) The New Politics of Numbers: An Introduction. In: Mennicken, A., Salais, R. (eds) *The New Politics of Numbers. Executive Politics and Governance*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78201-6_1
- Moore, M.-L., and M. Milkoreit. 2020. Imagination and transformations to sustainable and just futures. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene* 8(1):081. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.2020.081>
- Moriggi, Angela, Katriina Soini, Alex Franklin, and Dirk Roep. 'A Care-Based Approach to Transformative Change: Ethically-Informed Practices, Relational Response-Ability & Emotional Awareness'. *Ethics, Policy & Environment* 23, no. 3 (1 September 2020): 281–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21550085.2020.1848186>.
- Morrow, O., Davies, A., 2021. Creating careful circularities: Community composting in New York City. *Trans. Inst. Br. Geogr.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/tran.12523>

NaturArchy Exhibition Booklet, JRC Si-Art and IMAL <https://science-art-society.ec.europa.eu/resonances-iv/exhibition>

NaturArchy: Towards a Natural Contract Curatorial Statement <https://science-art-society.ec.europa.eu/resonances-iv/naturarchy-towards-natural-contract>

Oreskes, N., & Conway, E. M. (2010). *Merchants of doubt: how a handful of scientists obscured the truth on issues from tobacco smoke to global warming*. 1st U.S. ed. New York, Bloomsbury Press.

Padilla-Rivera, A., Russo-Garrido, S., & Merveille, N. (2022). Circular economy and environmental justice: A review of the literature. *Ecological Economics*, 196, 107384.

Palm, E., Jacob H., Holmberg, K. and Nielsen, T. (2021). 'Narrating Plastics Governance: Policy Narratives in the European Plastics Strategy'. *Environmental Politics*, 1–21.

Pansera, M., Owen, R., & Raby, C. (2021). Politics, power and responsibility in sustainability transitions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 41, 1–10.

Peirce, C. S. (1931-1958). *Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce*. Harvard University Press.

Peirce, C. S. (1992). *The Essential Peirce: Selected Philosophical Writings*. Indiana University Press.

Pel, B. Pel (2015): Trojan horses in transitions: A dialectical perspective on innovation 'capture', *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2015.1090903>

Persson et al (2022). 'Outside the Safe Operating Space of the Planetary Boundary for Novel Entities'. *Environmental Science and Technology* 56/3:1510–1521.

Phillips, N., & Hardy, C. (2002). *Discourse Analysis: Investigating Processes of Social Construction*. Sage.

Plastic Recyclers Europe (2018). Plastics Recycling. Retrieved March 2022, from: <https://www.plasticsrecyclers.eu/plastic-recycling>

Plastics Europe (2022a). 'Major Step Towards Zero Plastic Pollution Future'. Press Release, Brussels, available at: Plastics Europe's Position on a Global Agreement on Plastics • Plastics Europe

Plastics Europe (2022b). 'The Circular Economy for Plastics: A European Overview' available at: <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/the-circular-economy-for-plastics-a-european-overview-2/>

Plastics Europe (2023) Recommendations on the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR) to accelerate circularity of plastics packaging <https://plasticseurope.org/knowledge-hub/ppwr-recommendations/>

Plumwood, Val, ed. *Feminism and the Mastery of Nature*. Opening Out. London New York: Routledge, 1993.

Preiser, Rika, Reinette Biggs, Alta De Vos, and Carl Folke. 'Social-Ecological Systems as Complex Adaptive Systems: Organizing Principles for Advancing Research Methods and Approaches'. *Ecology and Society* 23, no. 4 (2018): art46. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10558-230446>.

- Puig de La Bellacasa, María. *Matters of Care: Speculative Ethics in More than Human Worlds*. Posthumanities 41. Minneapolis (Minn.): University of Minnesota press, 2017.
- Rabiu, M (2022). Consumer practices in a circular society, *Micro-Teaching* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6598561>
- Ragaert, K (2019). 'Once upon a time there was a Plastics Rehab'. TEDxVlerickBusinessSchool, 2019-04-25, retrieved from: https://www.ted.com/talks/kim_ragaert_plastics_rehab?language=en
- Rantanen, M. (2022) Set ideological wars aside and pursue a science-based, truly circular economy. *Politico*, Op-ed. [Set ideological wars aside and pursue a science-based, truly circular economy – POLITICO](#)
- Rantanen, M. (2023a) Crunch time for the EU's packaging rules: Let's get real, not reckless. *Packaging Insights, Insider Views* <https://www.packaginginsights.com/insider-views/crunch-time-for-the-eus-packaging-rules-lets-get-real-not-reckless.html>
- Rantanen, M. (2023b) How ideological thinking on waste hierarchy threatens EU policies <https://www.packaginginsights.com/video/eppa-director-general-how-ideological-thinking-on-the-waste-hierarchy-threatens-eu-policies.html>
- Rask, N (2022). 'An Intersectional Reading of Circular Economy Policies: Towards Just and Sufficiency-Driven Sustainabilities'. *Local Environment* 27, no. 10–11: 1287–1303. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2022.2040467>.
- Rethink Plastic (2022). History in the making. Press Release, available at: <https://rethinkplasticalliance.eu/news/advances-on-a-global-plastics-treaty-and-a-toxic-free-future/>
- Rethink Plastic Alliance (2022) Standardisation request process Request to cease development of Standardisation Request on 'plastics recycling and recycled plastics' <https://rethinkplasticalliance.eu/news/worlds-top-polluters-holding-pen-on-new-eu-standards-for-recycled-plastics/?cmplz-force-reload=1706285823533>
- Richter, I., Stegen, K.S. (2022) A choreography of delay: The response of German auto incumbents to environmental policy. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, Volume 45, December 2022, Pages 1-13, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2022.08.002>
- Ries, F. (2023) European Parliament Live Streaming, accessed 24 October 2023, <https://multimedia.europarl.europa.eu/en/webstreaming?view=day&d=2023-10-24>
- Roberts, C., Geels, F. W., Lockwood, M., Newell, P., Schmitz, H., Turnheim, B., & Jordan, A. (2018). The politics of accelerating low-carbon transitions: Towards a new research agenda. In *Energy Research and Social Science* (Vol. 44, pp. 304–311). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.06.001>
- Saltelli, A., Dankel, D. J., Di Fiore, M., Holland, N., & Pigeon, M. (2022). Science, the endless frontier of regulatory capture. *Futures*, 135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2021.102860>
- Saltelli, A., Kuc-Czarnecka, M., Piano, S. Lo, Lőrincz, M. J., Olczyk, M., Puy, A., Reinert, E., Smith, S. T., & van der Sluijs, J. P. (2023). Impact assessment culture in the European Union. Time for something new? *Environmental Science and Policy*, 142, 99–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.02.005>

- Schlosberg, D. (2007). *Defining Environmental Justice: Theories, Movements, and Nature*. Oxford University Press.
- Schmidt, V. A. (2008). Discursive institutionalism: The explanatory power of ideas and discourse. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 11, 303–326.
- Schröder, P., Bengtsson, M., Cohen, M., Dewick, P., Hoffstetter, J., Sarkis, J., 2019b. Degrowth within – Aligning circular economy and strong sustainability narratives. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 146, 190–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2019.03.038>
- Schröder, P., Lemille, A., Desmond, P., 2020. Making the circular economy work for human development. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104686>
- Schumacher, E.F., 1973. *Small is beautiful a study of economics as if people mattered.*, Blond & Briggs, New York
- Schwartz-Shea, P., & Yanow, D. (2012). *Interpretive Research Design: Concepts and Processes*. Routledge.
- Scott, W.R. (2008) *Institutions and Organizations: Ideas and Interests*, Third ed. Sage Publishers, Thousand Oaks, CA, USA
- Simoens, M., & Leipold, S. (2021). Trading radical for incremental change: The politics of a circular economy transition in the German packaging sector. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 23, 822–836.
- Simoens, M., Vrancken, K. C., & Valenzuela, F. (2022). Beyond the CE utopia: Reframing circular transitions through plural perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 371, 133519.
- Smink M. M., Hekkert M. P. and Negro S. O. (2015), Keeping sustainable innovation on a leash? Exploring incumbents' institutional strategies, *Bus. Strat. Env.*, 24, 86–101, doi: 10.1002/bse.1808
- Smith KE, Fooks G, Gilmore AB, Collin J, Weishaar H. Corporate coalitions and policymaking in the European Union: how and why British American Tobacco promoted "Better Regulation". *J Health Polit Policy Law*. 2015 Apr;40(2):325-72. doi: 10.1215/03616878-2882231. Epub 2015 Feb 2. PMID: 25646389; PMCID: PMC4668595.
- Sovacool, B. K., & Brisbois, M. C. (2019). Elite power in low-carbon transitions: A critical and interdisciplinary review. In *Energy Research and Social Science* (Vol. 57). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101242>
- Star, S. L., & Griesemer, J. R. (1989). Institutional ecology, “translations” and boundary objects. *Social Studies of Science*, 19(3), 387–420.
- Stirling, A. (2008). “Opening Up” and “Closing Down”: Power, participation, and pluralism in the social appraisal of technology. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 33(2), 262–294.
- Stirling, A. (2014). Transforming power: Social science and the politics of energy choices. *Energy Research and Social Science*, 1, 83–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2014.02.001>
- Stirling, A. (2015) Power, truth and progress: towards knowledge democracies in Europe. In: Wilsdon, J., Doubleday, R. (eds) *Future directions for scientific advice in Europe*, Centre for Science and Policy, Cambridge

Stirling, A. (2019). How deep is incumbency? A 'configuring fields' approach to redistributing and reorienting power in socio-material change. In *Energy Research and Social Science* (Vol. 58). Elsevier Ltd.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.101239>

Strand, R., Saltelli, A., Giampietro, M., Rommetveit, K., & Funtowicz, S. (2018). New narratives for innovation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, 1849–1853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.194>

Sühlsen, K., & Hisschemöller, M. (2014). Lobbying the “Energiewende”. Assessing the effectiveness of strategies to promote the renewable energy business in Germany. *Energy Policy*, 69, 316–325.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2014.02.018>

SusChem (2020). 'Sustainable Plastics Strategy'. European Technology Platform for Sustainable Chemistry available at: <http://suschem.org/publications> .

Taylor, K. (2022) Brussels set to propose watered-down EU packaging law after industry outcry. EurActiv.
<https://www.euractiv.com/section/circular-economy/news/brussels-set-to-propose-watered-down-eu-packaging-law-after-industry-outcry/>

The European Association of Self-adhesive Labels (FINAT) (2022) A negative list of packaging characteristics can hinder a circular economy for packaging <https://www.finat.com/news/finat-expresses-concern-about-negative-list-in-draft-packaging-packaging-waste-regulation>

The European Consumer Voice in Standardisation (ANEC) (2023) Position paper on revised EU Rules for packaging and packaging waste <https://www.anec.eu/publications/position-papers/983-anec-position-paper-on-revised-eu-rules-for-packaging-and-packaging-waste>

The European Federation of Corrugated Board Manufacturers (FEFCO) (2023) FEFCO position on the Packaging & Packaging Waste Proposal <https://www.fefco.org/eu-policy/position-papers>

The European Organisation for Packaging and the Environment (Euopen) (2022) The European Packaging Value Chain expresses serious concerns about the European Commission's suggested approach to packaging and packaging waste legislation, Joint industry statement from the Packaging Value Chain derived from:
<https://plasticseurope.org/media/joint-industry-statement-from-the-packaging-value-chain/>

Tilsted et al (2022). 'Petrochemical transition narratives: Selling fossil fuel solutions in a decarbonizing world'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 94:102880.

Tilsted, J.P., Mah, A., Nielsen, T.D., Finkill, G., Bauer, F. (2022). 'Petrochemical transition narratives: Selling fossil fuel solutions in a decarbonizing world'. *Energy Research & Social Science* 94:102880

Timmermans, S., & Tavory, I. (2012). Theory construction in qualitative research: From grounded theory to abductive analysis. *Sociological Theory*, 30(3), 167-186.

Together for Sustainable Packaging (2023) Open letter: Pause the proposal on PPWR
<https://forsustainablepackaging.eu/open-letter/>

Trucost (2016). 'Plastics and Sustainability: A Valuation of Environmental Benefits, Costs, and Opportunities for Continuous Improvement' American Chemistry Council, available at: <https://www.americanchemistry.com/better-policy-regulation/transportation-infrastructure/corporate-average-fuel-economy-cape-emissions-compliance/resources/plastics-and-sustainability-a-valuation-of-environmental-benefits-costs-and-opportunities-for-continuous-improvement>

Turnheim, B., & Sovacool, B. K. (2020). Forever stuck in old ways? Pluralising incumbencies in sustainability transitions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 35, 180–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.10.012>

Valenzuela, F., & Böhm, S. (2017). Against wasted politics: A critique of the circular economy. *Ephemera*, 17(1), 23–60.

van Hulst, M. (2012). Storytelling, a model of and a model for planning. *Planning Theory*, 11(3), 299–318.

Vermeylen, Saskia (2023) Law and Arts: Dancing the Law
<https://www.strath.ac.uk/humanities/lawschool/blog/lawandartspart3of3dancingthelaw/>

Vervoort, Joost, Tara Smeenk, Iryna Zamuruieva, Lisa Reichelt, Mae Van Veldhoven, Lucas Rutting, Ann Light, et al (2024). '9 Dimensions for Evaluating How Art and Creative Practice Stimulate Societal Transformations'. *Ecology and Society* 29, no. 1: art29. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-14739-290129>.

Voß, J., Smith, A., Grin, J. (2009). Designing long-term policy: rethinking transition management, *Policy Sci* 42:275–302, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-009-9103-5>

Völker, T., Kovacic, Z., Strand, R., 2020. Indicator development as a site of collective imagination? The case of European Commission policies on the circular economy. *Cult. Organ.* 26, 103–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14759551.2019.1699092>

Walsh, Zack, Jessica Böhme, and Christine Wamsler (2021). 'Towards a Relational Paradigm in Sustainability Research, Practice, and Education'. *Ambio* 50, no. 1: 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-020-01322-y>.

West, Simon, L. Jamila Haider, Sanna Stålhammar, and Stephen Woroniecki (2020). 'A Relational Turn for Sustainability Science? Relational Thinking, Leverage Points and Transformations'. *Ecosystems and People* 16, no. 1 (January 2020): 304–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2020.1814417>.

West, Simon, L. Jamila Haider, Tilman Hertz, Maria Mancilla Garcia, and Michele-Lee Moore (2024). 'Relational Approaches to Sustainability Transformations: Walking Together in a World of Many Worlds'. *Ecosystems and People* 20, no. 1 2370539. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2024.2370539>.

Wittmayer, J. M., Avelino, F., Pel, B., & Blum, S. (2019). Narratives and change: How social innovation initiatives construct societal transformation. *Futures*, 112, 102433.

Yalçın, N.G., Ampe, K., & Simoens, M. C. (2024). Closing-down the debate instead of the loops? A nuanced consideration of established actors in the circular economy. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 203, 107445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107445>

Yalçın, N.G., Paredis, E. & Jaeger-Erben, M. (2023) Contested discourses of a circular plastics economy in Europe: prioritizing material, economy, or society?, *Environmental Politics*, DOI: [10.1080/09644016.2023.2192145](https://doi.org/10.1080/09644016.2023.2192145)

Yalçın, Nur Gizem, Erik Paredis, and Melanie Jaeger-Erben (2025). 'Packaged Science? Incumbent Strategies of Science Capture from a Power Perspective'. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 54: 100931. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2024.100931>.

Yanow, D. (2006). 'Interpretation and method: Empirical research methods and the interpretive turn' (pp. 67–88). New York: M.E. Sharpe.

Zero Waste Europe (2020). 'Response to the new Circular Economy Action Plan Consultation'. Position Briefing, available at: <https://zerowasteurope.eu/library/zero-waste-europe-response-to-the-new-circular-economy-action-plan-consultation/>

Zink, T., Geyer, R., 2017. Circular Economy Rebound. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 21, 593–602. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12545>

Zwiers, Jakob, Melanie Jaeger-Erben, and Florian Hofmann. 'Circular Literacy. A Knowledge-Based Approach to the Circular Economy'. *Culture and Organization* 26, no. 2 (3 March 2020): 121–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14759551.2019.1709065>.